

MDIS 2024

Orléans, November 19th-22nd
Symposium MDIS – FormaTerre 2024

Hôtel Dupanloup
1 rue Dupanloup
45000 Orléans

[https://www.brgm.fr/en/event/symposium/
mdis-symposium-formaterre-2024](https://www.brgm.fr/en/event/symposium/mdis-symposium-formaterre-2024)

MDIS 2024

Tuesday
November 19th

Organised by BRGM, CNES and ISDeform, the 6th edition of the MDIS - FormaTerre Symposium will address approaches for measuring land surface deformation using spaceborne imagery as well as exploiting these observations for various application domains such as seismic cycles, volcanic deformation, landslides, the cryosphere, hydrogeology and ground deformation triggered by human activity.

Training sessions Programme

Description of training courses:

FLATSIM

Learn to use the FLATSIM (FormaTerre Large-scale multi-Temporal Sentinel-1 Interferometry processing chain) service: a tool for systematically producing interferograms from Sentinel-1 data, as well as displacement time series, over large geographical areas.

SNAPPING

SNAPPING stands for Surface motion mapping, an on-demand service for Sentinel-1 multitemporal DInSAR processing based on the integrated SNAP and StaMPS chain.

MIC MAC

MicMac is a free open source photogrammetric suite (Cecill-B license) that can be used in a variety of 3D reconstruction scenarios. It is aimed primarily at professional or academic users, but ongoing efforts are being made to make it more accessible to the general public.

GDM SAR

GDM-SAR-In (Ground Deformation Monitoring with SAR Interferometry) is an on-demand calculation service for processing Sentinel-1 radar data, developed and operated by FormaTerre. The sequence of tasks, based on NSBAS software, is specific to the computing platforms (CNES or UGA) and automated.

09:00 - 09:45 **Welcome**

10:00 - 12:30

FLATSIM + InSAR VIZ
Salle Europe

SNAPPING
Salon Bleu

MIC MAC
Salle de réunion 1^{er} étage

12:30 - 13:00 **Lunch break**

13:00 - 15:30

FLATSIM + InSAR VIZ
Salle Europe

GDM SAR
Salon Bleu

MIC MAC
Salle de réunion 1^{er} étage

15:30 - 15:45 **Coffee break**

15:45 - 17:45

GDM SAR
Salon Bleu

SNAPPING
Salle de réunion 1^{er} étage

18:00 **End of training sessions**

19:00 - 20:15

Discover a "Mardis de la Science" lecture
"Why and how can we observe the Earth from space?"
by Félix PEROSANS, CNES researcher

MOBE, Grande orse
amphitheatre, 4th floor, 6 rue Marcel Proust, 45000 Orléans.

The Palu earthquake fault offset, Sulawesi (MW 7.6, 28 September 2018), calculated with Labdsat 8 © BRGM

09:00 - 09:30 **Welcome**

09:30 - 10:00 **Opening** (BRGM): Christophe POINSSOT

10:00 - 10:30 **Keynote Lecture** (ESA)

- Ciro MANZO
EO third party missions for environmental analysis

10:30 - 12:00 **Session “Tools and Methods”**

- E. DESCHAMPS-OSTANCIAUX *et al.*
Accès et traitements des données en Terre solide : les services du pôle Formaterre dans le paysage des infrastructures de recherche
- P. DURAND *et al.*
FLATSIM service: overview, updates and announcements of Opportunity
- C. DOUBRE *et al.*
ISDeform: The French National Service of Observation for monitoring ground deformation related to natural hazards by satellite imagery
- F. PROVOST *et al.*
New Image Correlation WEB services in the FormaTerre GDM Portfolio
- E. PATHIER *et al.*
GDM-SAR-In Opening of a new Formaterre on-demand service for Sentinel-1 InSAR processing
- C. THOMAS *et al.*
Tools for the visualization of InSAR data in the context of FormaTerre

12:00 - 13:00 **Lunch break**

13:00 - 13:30 **Keynote Lecture** (Telecom Paris)

- Florence TUPIN
Deep learning for SAR data with focus on speckle reduction

13:30 - 14:45 **Session “Tools and Methods”**

- F. ALBINO *et al.*
MANGO Toolbox: Mitigating Atmospheric Noise with GNSS Observations
- P. MEYER *et al.*
Atmospheric correction in extreme mountainous context: The Nang Parbat

- M. DALAISON *et al.*
Étude statistique de la phase de fermeture en Insar dans des contextes géographiques variés
- H. WATINE *et al.*
Down-slope solifluction movements and permafrost degradation in the northeastern tibetan plateau revealed by INSAR
- R THIEBLEMONT *et al.*
European coastal subsidence derived from the European Ground Motion Service

15:00 - 15:30 **Keynote Lecture** (ESA)

- Lorenzo IANNINI
Future Copernicus SAR Missions: Objectives and Status of ROSE-L and Sentinel-1 Next Generation

15:30 - 16:00 **Coffee break**

16:00 - 17:30 **Session “Volcanology”**

- A. HAUCK *et al.*
Capella Space SAR amplitude imagery and LiDAR DEM: an unconventional recipe to map
- D. SMITTARELLO *et al.*
3D ground deformation time series at Piton de la Fournaise
- P. BOUYGUES
Monitoring Topographic Changes and Ground Deformation of Semeru Volcano, Indonesia.
- S. GRÉMION *et al.*
Evolution of the merapi summit area related to the 2021-2023 effusive eruption, as revealed by radar and optical satellite imagery.
- S. LIZARAZO *et al.*
Deformation at tropical Colombian stratovolcanoes revealed by ALOS-2 data interferometry
- V. PINEL *et al.*
CIEST2 support during the ongoing volcanic crisis on the Reykjanes Peninsula in south-west Iceland

17:45 **End of presentations**

20:00 - 21:30 Dinner at the food trucks in the Youth Hostel, 3 rue Croix Pêchée 45000 Orléans

21:00 - 00:00 Night hike along the banks of the Loire. Don't forget your headlamp!

8:30 - 9:00 Welcome

9:00 - 10:15 Session "Volcanology"

- R. SERMET *et al.*
Automatic Detection of Volcanic Fissures in SAR Interferograms with Machine Learning
- Q. DUMONT *et al.*
Is stress monitoring able to forecast intrusions and slip events at the Piton de la Fournaise volcano?
- L. LOPEZ-UROZ *et al.*
Potential of deep learning for volcanic source inversion
- O. BODART *et al.*
Fictitious domains to resolve traction changes on magma intrusions
- C. NOVOA LIZAMA *et al.*
Modelling magma recharge dynamics during the 2016 Nevado de Chillan eruption

10:30 - 11:00 Coffee break

11:00 - 11:30 Keynote Lecture (IGN)

- Ewelina RUPNIK
Photogrammetric processing of historical images: focus on Earth Science applications

11:30 - 12:00 Session "Tectonics"

- P. DÉRAND *et al.*
Coseismic slip segmentation of the Kahramanmaraş earthquake doublet (Turkey, 2023)
- G. COSTANTINO *et al.*
Continuous monitoring of slow slip in cascadia through deep-learning-based denoising of GNSS data

12:00 - 13:00 Lunch break

13:00 - 15:00 Session "Tectonics"

- Z. LIU *et al.*
Shear Strain Evolution Across the East Anatolian Fault (EAF) Response to the 2020 Mw6.8 Elazığ and 2023 Mw7.8/Mw7.6 Kahramanmaraş Earthquake Sequence
- B. LOVERY *et al.*
Using Sentinel-1 Timeseries for Large-scale Tectonic Applications in Central Andes
- B. COSENZA-MURALLES *et al.*
Regional strain partitioning and fault coupling in northern Central America (Guatemala, el Salvador, Honduras) from sar interferometry Time Series analysis
- R. VILTRES *et al.*
Aseismic creep and strain partitioning accommodating the Nubia-Eurasia oblique convergence in northern Africa from INSAR
- C. POTHIER *et al.*
Exploring an unsupervised data mining approach to extract aseismic slip events along the Izmit section of the north Anatolian fault, based on FLATSIM time series
- Z. BAYRAMOV *et al.*
Dynamic triggering of mud volcanoes and aseismic slip in the fluid rich west Caspian region by the 2023 Kahramanmaraş earthquakes: a joint geodetic and seismic analysis

15:00 - 15:30 Coffee break

15:30 - 16:00 Keynote Lecture (CNES)

- Yannice FAUGÈRE
The SWOT mission and its applications to Earth Science

16:00 - 18:00 Posters session

19:00 - 21:30 Gala dinner at the hôtel Dupanloup

16:00 - 18:00 Poster session

- F. FAURE *et al.*
Automatic seismic fault scarp mapping with deep learning
- M. PARNAS *et al.*
New analysis of INSAR and seismology for kinematic reconstruction of the 1995 offshore Aigion m6.2 earthquake (Greece)
- D. NTWALI *et al.*
Assessment of soil loss in Rwanda based on satellite data
- A. CHEAIB *et al.*
Study of active coherent landslides in Lebanon using remote-sensing techniques
- L. MAURY *et al.*
Cartographie et cinématiques des déformations de pentes par InSAR et imagerie optique, Mustang supérieur, Népal
- R. BRYAN *et al.*
Detecting slow moving landslides in South America using convolutional neural networks and InSAR
- F. PROVOST *et al.*
Rainfall, anthropogenic activity or the chamoli flood? What triggered the reactivation of the Joshimath slope (Uttarakhand, India): insights from multi sensor satellite observations
- F. MOKHTARI *et al.*
Dynamics of the hydrological network in the karst of Fontaine de Vaucluse (SE France) from the quantification of the surface deformation using massive InSAR analysis
- L. MARCONATO *et al.*
Advances and challenges for ALOs-2 ScanSAR time-series analysis
- N. D'OREYE *et al.*
AMSTer goes 3D, but not only: what is new with this InSAR time series software
- D. EL HAJJAR *et al.*
Sequential Phase Linking: progressive integration of SAR images for operational phase estimation
- E. NEYRINCK *et al.*
A slow slip event cycle analysis based on InSAR flatsim time series: case study of the Izmit segment along the North Anatolian fault
- R. GRANDIN *et al.*
Deformation of Mayotte Island during and after the 2018-2021 volcano-tectonic episode

PLEASE NOTE:

The only format allowed for posters is A0 vertical.

- A. MERIDI *et al.*
Active straining of the Balkans peninsula: insights from spatial geodesy (InSAR and GNSS)
- W. YAO *et al.*
Dynamic earthquake rupture in Serpentinite: implications from the MW7.6 Elbistan earthquake during the 2023 Kahramanmaras, Türkiye, earthquake doublet
- F. MOKHTARI *et al.*
Slip dynamics along the creeping segment of the Haiyuan fault
- A-C LEGAL *et al.*
El pilar fault aseismic behaviour in Venezuela
- C. MARTINELLI *et al.*
How well can displacement be resolved close to earthquake surface ruptures using optical image correlation? A case study from the 2019 Ridgecrest earthquake
- J. K. REMOLADOR *et al.*
Understanding the deformation associated with the December 2020 Mw 6.4 Petrinja earthquake in Croatia through time-series InSAR images from the FLATSIM service
- T. MONTAGNON *et al.*
Sub-pixel displacement estimation from optical satellite images using a new hyper-realistic earthquake database and U-NET architecture
- M. RADIGUET *et al.*
Quantifying Interseismic deformation along the Mexican subduction zone from InSAR time series
- L. ZUCCALI *et al.*
Near real-time magma propagation forecasting with a particle filter
- K. BURROWS *et al.*
Change detection with InSAR coherence to identify rapid landslide movements in time and space
- M. GOUGEON *et al.*
Looking for onland surface rupture on secondary normal faults of the 1956 Ms7.8 Amorgos earthquake (Greece): insights from historical aerial images
- A. HAUTECOEUR *et al.*
InSAR time series and SVD decomposition unravel a dyke intrusion at a tropical volcano, Karthala 2021-2022
- C. SPRIET *et al.*
Crustal uplift in the Kerguelen Islands from SENTINEL-1 InSAR: a consequence of recent ice melting?

09:00 - 09:30

Welcome

9:00 - 11:15

Session "Gravitational Motion, including Glaciers"

- L. GUO *et al.*
Dynamics of small surging glaciers in the Qilian Mountains: Patterns and mechanisms revealed by long-term dense time-series observations
- J. BELART *et al.*
Monitoring glacier topography from space: past successes, novel observations using SWOT and perspectives from 4D-Earth
- D. CUSICANQUI *et al.*
Detection and reconstruction of rock glaciers kinematic over 24 YEARS (2000–2024) from Landsat imagery
- M. BERNAT *et al.*
Mass losses of the polar ice sheets, Antarctica and Greenland. New constraints from stereoscopic imagery and laser altimetry
- L. BERAUD *et al.*
An improved processing of aster elevation time series in high mountain Asia to study glacier surge dynamics, and test application to large landslides
- C. HOPQUIN *et al.*
Revealing landslide bi-monthly and annual dynamics using a combination of radar interferometry and structure-from-motion: the study case of Grand Eboulis
- F. LEDER *et al.*
Recent satellite-based radar and optical monitoring of slow-moving landslides in Nepal during monsoon
- A. BRALET *et al.*
Un nouveau jeu de données pour la détection d'instabilités gravitaires dans les Alpes à partir d'interférogrammes SAR
- J.-P. MALET *et al.*
Landslide deformation pattern of the la Belotte landslide from Sentinel-1 INSAR and in-situ GNSS

11:15

End of MDIS 2024

11:30

Coffee break

11:45 - 15:30

ISDeform General Assembly

(Lunch break at 13:15)

The Palu earthquake fault offset, Sulawesi (MW 7.6, 28 September 2018), calculated with Sentinel 2 © BRGM

MDIS 2024

Accommodation:

- Orléans Youth Hostel, 3 rue Croix Péchée, 45000 Orléans
- Jackhotel, 18 rue du Cloître Saint-Aignan, 45000 Orléans

If you have requested a room, contact the organizers to find out which room you have been allocated.

Transport:

- To travel to Orléans for the training Tuesday, November 19th, we recommend taking the 8:22 train from Paris Austerlitz to 9:27 at Orléans station.
- To come to the congress from Wednesday, November 20th, we recommend taking the 7:06 train from Paris Austerlitz to 8:20 at Orléans station.

If the journey is too long for you, you can take accommodation the day before at your own expense. Be careful. Don't get off at Les Aubrais station but stay on the train until the terminus at Orléans centre station.

On November 22nd, to return after the ISDform General Assembly, we recommend taking:

- The 15:34 train from Orleans to 16:42 to Paris Austerlitz
- Or the 16:34 train from Orleans to 17:39 to Paris Austerlitz.

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Proceedings of the MDIS 2024 symposium

Mésures des déformations de la surface de la Terre par Imagerie Satellitaire

MDIS 2024

ForM a Ter

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DOWN-SLOPE SOLIFLUCTION MOVEMENTS AND PERMAFROST DEGRADATION IN THE NORTHEASTERN TIBETAN PLATEAU REVEALED BY INSAR

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ABSTRACT

The Qinghai-Tibetan Plateau (QTP) is characterized by a high periglacial landscape. The average annual surface temperature is below 0°C over most of the Plateau, so permafrost (permanently frozen ground) is present over most of its extent [1]. Excess ice in the frost-sensitive materials of the active layer, above the permafrost, thaws during the summer and autumn months and freezes during the winter and spring months [2]. These freezing and thawing phenomena lead to cyclic vertical movements of the surface. On the slopes, solifluction phenomena also related to freeze-thaw activity take place, associated to permanent down-slope displacements [3].

Both movements can be measured by spatial geodesy techniques such as Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry (InSAR). However, InSAR measurements are limited to projecting 3-dimensional displacements onto the radar's Line of Sight. Here, a methodology to automatically map slope processes using multi-temporal InSAR data is developed and applied to characterize the distribution and the dynamics of solifluction in the north-eastern QTP.

InSAR time series of surface deformation from 6 years of radar measurements from Sentinel-1 (2014-2020) ESA satellite have been built over an 80,000 km² area to study the permafrost evolution of the northeastern Tibetan Plateau (38°N; 97°E). Time series of ascending (T099, T172) and descending (T004) geometries exhibit three trends, (parameter a) a linear trend of continuous deformation, (parameter c) an annual cyclical deformation whose amplitude appears to (parameter d) increase over time. These measurements correspond to one-dimensional (1D) sensor-to-ground distance change along the LOS. By combining ascending and descending geometries, it is possible to estimate the displacement in the directions parallel and normal to the slope using a two steps method: (1) the temporal decomposition of each pixel of the three tracks into reversible (c) and irreversible coefficients (a and d), following by (2) the spatial decomposition of each of this

variable into the parallel and normal to the slope (Fig1.a,b). Alternatively, by interpolating the LOS time series, we can directly apply the projection to the displacement time series in the local slope reference.

Based on synthetic tests, unfavorable pixels (south or north sloping cells) are masked as well as area where solifluction movement are not expected (flat areas). Irreversible down-slope and subsidence deformations are analyzed in relation to seasonal amplitude across two lithologies: unconsolidated and consolidated rocks.

Our change of reference frame strategy proved effective in automatically extracting hillslope processes and quantifying their dynamics. Downward movements are widespread and affect nearly all terrains (Fig1.c). The median down-slope rates are 4.2 and 5.4 mm/yr for unconsolidated and consolidated rocks respectively. For consolidated rocks, these movements correlate with slope, while for unconsolidated rocks, they correlate with both seasonal amplitude and slope, reflecting different dynamics (Fig1.d). Moreover, the time series in the slope reference frame allow us to quantify the links between downslope movements and the timing and the amplitudes of freeze thaw cycles. Irreversible isotropic subsidence rates are measured at 6.8 mm/yr for consolidated rocks and 2.3 mm/yr for unconsolidated rocks. This permafrost degradation correlates with high frost susceptibility areas, which are characterized by high seasonal amplitude, significant delays between peak temperatures and maximum thaw subsidence, and are associated with higher downslope displacements.

The rates and processes of solifluction are influenced by climate, hydrology, geology, and topography, all of which contribute to the spatial variability of this phenomenon [3]. This study, as along recent publications [4, 5, 6] illustrates the potential of InSAR measurements for large-scale analyses of this phenomena in remote areas. The proposed methodology can be applied to various contexts, and to any InSAR products derived from the available recent platforms (e.g. EGMS, LICARS, FLATSIM). It enables to quantify down-

Figure 1. (a) Top (left) and side (right) views of a theoretical mountain, showing the coefficients parallel ($U_{//}$) and perpendicular (U_{\perp}) to the steepest slope line of each pixel. The angle α represents the slope (clock-wise direction), and the angle Ω represents the aspect of the slope (determined from the east, clock-wise direction). (b) Schematic view of the descending observation geometry. The angle Φ corresponds to the azimuth between the east and the LOS vector projected in the horizontal plane at the target location. The angle θ represents the angle between the horizontal plane of the local ellipsoid and the satellite LOS vector 90° minus incidence angle. (c) Map of irreversible ground deformation velocities parallel to the slope [mm/yr] after the application of the automatic masking. Areas 1 and 2, represent the moraines and the siliciclastic sedimentary rocks, respectively. (d) Scatter plots showing the relation between down-slope displacement and the product of slope and seasonal amplitude perpendicular to the slope. Points correspond to median values within bins, and the shaded areas represent the respective \pm standard deviation.

slope movements and their relations with forcing environmental variables.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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5. REFERENCES

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ÉTUDE STATISTIQUE DE LA PHASE DE FERMETURE EN INSAR DANS DES CONTEXTES GÉOGRAPHIQUES VARIÉS

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ABSTRACT

Depuis 2015, la mission Sentinel-1 a marqué le début d'une nouvelle ère pour l'interférométrie radar à synthèse d'ouverture (InSAR), en offrant des acquisitions satellitaires gratuites et régulières couvrant l'ensemble des terres émergées du globe. Grâce à cette archive croissante d'images radar, l'InSAR permet théoriquement de quantifier les déformations millimétriques du sol, causées par des phénomènes tels que les activités tectoniques ou hydrologiques, avec une haute résolution spatiale. Toutefois, ces mesures ne sont réalisables qu'à condition de corriger les interactions entre les ondes radar, l'atmosphère et les caractéristiques du sol. Si des progrès considérables ont été faits pour atténuer le bruit atmosphérique, les effets des variations spatiales et temporelles des propriétés du sol et de son couvert sur le signal radar restent mal compris. En régions tempérées et végétalisées, comme en France, ces interactions, associées aux étapes nécessaires de moyennage spatial (*multilooking*), induisent des biais de plusieurs centimètres par an dans l'estimation des déformations du sol. Cependant, l'erreur de moyennage demeure inconnue et ne peut être estimée qu'indirectement, à partir de plusieurs images InSAR, par la mesure de la phase de fermeture (*closure phase*); le produit cyclique d'au moins trois interférogrammes.

Nous calculons et étudions les distributions de la phase de fermeture pour des piles d'interférogrammes,

réalisés à partir d'un burst d'images IW Sentinel-1 dans trois régions distinctes: en Normandie (France), en Ontario (Canada) et au Baloutchistan (Pakistan) [Figure 1]. Ces régions présentent une diversité de climats et d'usages du sol. Nous analysons les effets statistiques interconnectés de la cohérence, des types de couvertures terrestres, des variations saisonnières et de la taille de la fenêtre de moyennage sur la phase de fermeture. Nous considérons à la fois la cohérence entre les pixels en pleine résolution à l'intérieur de la fenêtre de moyennage et celle autour de la fenêtre de moyennage couramment utilisée pour guider le déroulement de la phase. Nous constatons que la distribution de la phase de fermeture peut être fortement non gaussienne, notamment pour une faible cohérence non nulle, des interférogrammes à petites baselines ou des fenêtres de moyennage de grande taille. En particulier, elle tend à être positive, asymétrique à droite, et présente des valeurs aberrantes. Comme attendu, les terrains végétalisés et agricoles sont les plus affectés par les erreurs systématiques, avec une phase de fermeture moyenne de l'ordre de 0,05 rad, tandis que les milieux urbains et les sols nus affichent les phases de fermeture les plus faibles. Néanmoins, les classes génériques de couverture du sol, telles que les cultures, prairies et forêts, ont des signatures contrastées suivant le climat. Un seuil inférieur sur la cohérence interne au pixel moyenné permet d'isoler la composante uniforme aléatoire de la phase de fermeture de l'erreur systématique.

Figure 1. Classification de la couverture terrestre pour les trois sites d'étude selon ESA WorldCover 10m (2021) (*à gauche*) et phase de fermeture moyenne dans le temps (*à droite*) en géométrie radar à la résolution de 8 *looks* en azimut. Alors que le site français est représentatif d'un paysage cultivé hautement anthropisé dans un climat tempéré, le site canadien est naturel et contient une quantité importante d'eau de surface. Le Pakistan, avec son sol nu, est pris comme référence, sur lequel l'estimation de la déformation basée sur l'InSAR est connue pour être performante.

Index Terms— InSAR, Sentinel-1, closure phase, error, bias, land cover

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Sequential Phase Linking : progressive integration of SAR images for operational phase estimation

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1 Abstract

In this paper, we address the topic of sequential integration of new Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images in interferometric phase estimation. When a newly acquired data arrives, the data set expands and can be partitioned to two distinct blocks, one representing the historical SAR images and the other representing the newly acquired data. The proposed approach exploits sequential estimation of the covariance matrix of SAR images and the interferometric phases, taking the existing data set as prior information. This approach simplifies the continuous interferometric phase estimation by incorporating new data into the existing context. Furthermore, it presents the advantage of reduced computation time compared to the traditional approaches, making it a more efficient solution for operational displacement estimation.

2 Context

The short revisit cycle of the Sentinel-1 mission (6 – 12 days) enables the acquisition of unprecedented SAR data volumes. Once a new image arrives, most classical methods require the replay of the algorithm on the entire of or part of the data set. The literature has not extensively explored robust sequential processing of this data, as indicated by the limited number of studies addressing this specific topic. The most known sequential approach was developed in [1] where the main idea is to partition the entire stack of SAR images into m mini-stacks. The algorithm starts by treating the first mini-stack and then compressing it into a single virtual image through principal component analysis (PCA). The virtual image obtained is then connected to the next mini-stack, and so on. This approach, based on the standard PL [2–4] (which uses the modulus of the Sample Covariance Matrix (SCM) as a plug-in for the coherence matrix), requires an extended period to form the adequate fixed size mini-stack. This constraint limits the method’s ability to respond to real-time needs.

3 Methodology

We propose an approach (namely S-MLE-PL) to tackle the difficulties arising from the growing volumes of SAR data produced by current and upcoming Sentinel-1 SAR mission. It enables the sequential integration of newly acquired data, yielding better results than classical approaches that process the entire data set at once. Additionally, the proposed

sequential method offers the advantage of computational efficiency compared to the classic approaches.

Figure 1: SAR data representation including both previous and recently obtained images. The local neighborhood of size n is denoted by gray pixels (sliding window).

We consider a stack of $l = p + 1$ SAR images, for a given pixel, we define a local homogeneous spatial neighborhood of size n , denoted $\{\tilde{x}^i\}_{i=1}^n$, where $\tilde{x}^i \in \mathbb{C}^l$, for all $i \in \llbracket 1, n \rrbracket$. We can assume that each pixel of the local patch is distributed as a zero mean Complex Circular Gaussian (CCG) with a covariance matrix [5], i.e., $\tilde{\mathbf{x}} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \tilde{\Sigma})$. Taking into account the phase closure property of the In-SAR stack, the covariance matrix adheres to the following structure [6]:

$$\tilde{\Sigma} = \tilde{\Psi} \circ \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{\theta} \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{\theta}^H \quad (1)$$

where the symbol \circ signifies element-wise (Hadamard) multiplication, $\tilde{\Psi}$ is the real core of the covariance matrix. The hermitian structured covariance matrix can be rewritten as

$$\tilde{\Sigma} = \begin{pmatrix} \Sigma & w_{\theta_l}^* \text{diag}(\mathbf{w}_{\theta}) \boldsymbol{\gamma}^T \\ \boldsymbol{\gamma} \text{diag}(\mathbf{w}_{\theta})^H w_{\theta_l} & \gamma_l \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where Σ denotes the covariance matrix between the previous SAR images, $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ signifies the correlation vector between the newly acquired data and the previous ones, γ_l represents the variance value of the newly acquired data, \mathbf{w}_{θ} indicates the vector of phase difference exponential of the previous SAR images, and w_{θ_l} is the exponential of the phase of the latest data.

Considering the covariance matrix structure in (2) and assuming that $\{\tilde{x}^i\}_{i=1}^n$ follows a CCG distribution, the as-

(a) Interferogram estimated by MLE-PL

(b) A posteriori coherence estimated by MLE-PL

(c) Interferogram estimated by S-MLE-PL

(d) A posteriori coherence estimated by S-MLE-PL

Figure 2: Comparisons of interferograms and a posteriori coherence for MLE-PL and S-MLE-PL.

sociated negative log-likelihood for the entire dataset can be expressed as:

$$\mathcal{L}_G(\gamma, \gamma_l, w_{\theta_l}) \propto n \log(v) + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y^{i*} y^i}{v}. \quad (3)$$

where $y^i = x_l^i - w_{\theta_l} \gamma \text{diag}(\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{\theta})^H \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} \mathbf{x}^i$ and $v = \gamma_l - \gamma \text{diag}(\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{\theta})^H \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} \text{diag}(\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{\theta}) \gamma^T$

The PL problem [6] can be represented by a maximum likelihood approach for the covariance structure (1), assuming the Gaussian model for a given prior estimate of $\tilde{\Psi}$. In this work, we propose to estimate simultaneously the coherence parameters and the new phase.

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\gamma, \gamma_l, \theta_l} \quad & \mathcal{L}_G(\gamma, \gamma_l, w_{\theta_l}) \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \gamma, \gamma_l \text{ real}, |w_{\theta_l}| = 1, \theta_l = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

For simplicity, we adopt the convention $\theta_1 = 0$, which is equivalent to $|[w]_1| = 1$. The optimization of \mathcal{L}_G , defined in (3), will be addressed in a unified manner using a Block Coordinate Descent (BCD) algorithm, where each parameter will have an analytical update form.

4 Real data

We use a stack of 20 SAR images over the Mexico City acquired every 12 days, from 14 August 2019 to 10 April 2020, corresponding to 8 months to assess the performance of the proposed S-MLE-PL approach. The interferograms estimated by both MLE-PL and S-MLE-PL approaches, are illustrated in Fig. (2a), (2c). In both cases, the multi-looking window, denoted as $n = 8 \times 8$, remains the same. The MLE-PL and S-MLE-PL methods yield the same results, however the sequential approach demonstrates significantly more reduced execution time than the MLE-PL when applied to real data. The quality of the PL may be assessed by the goodness of the fit between the observed phases and the estimated Fig. (2b) and (2d)

$$\gamma_{\text{post}} = \frac{\text{Re}(\sum_{q=1}^l \sum_{i=q+1}^l e^{(\Delta\theta_{iq} - (\hat{\theta}_i - \hat{\theta}_q))})}{l(l-1)/2}$$

The closer the value of this parameter is to 1, the better the result. The sequential method shows values closer to 1 more often than the offline method, where a lot of noise and points colored in green and yellow can be seen, indicating values between 0.4 and 0.6.

5 Conclusions

We present a novel sequential PL approach that allows incorporating efficiently new SAR images in interferometric phase estimation in a PL framework. According to synthetic simulations and real data applications, the proposed S-MLE-PL approach presents the same performance and lower computational cost compared to MLE-PL.

6 Acknowledgement

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REGIONAL STRAIN PARTITIONING AND FAULT COUPLING IN NORTHERN CENTRAL AMERICA (GUATEMALA, EL SALVADOR, HONDURAS) FROM SAR INTERFEROMETRY TIME SERIES ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Tectonic deformation in northern Central America results from the interaction between the Cocos, Caribbean, and North America plates. This deformation is mostly accommodated by the sub-parallel Motagua and Polochic left-lateral faults, north-south-trending grabens south of the Motagua Fault, the Middle America subduction zone, and right-lateral faults along the Middle America volcanic arc (including the El Salvador fault zone and Jalpatagua faults in El Salvador and Guatemala, respectively). Large earthquakes associated with these faults include the destructive 1976 Mw 7.5 earthquake along the Motagua fault and the 2012 Mw 7.5 Champerico subduction thrust earthquake.

We show the potential of permanent scatterers and distributed scatterers (PSDS) InSAR techniques applied to a Sentinel-1 (S1) archive, to retrieve current deformation at large scale in this complex tectonic context. We analyze a time series of S1 radar images spanning from 2014 to 2022, along two ascending and two descending tracks covering most of Guatemala, El Salvador and western Honduras. The PSDS interferometry approach (based on Adam *et al.*, 2013, Ansari *et al.*, 2018, Parizzi *et al.*, 2020) includes corrections for tropospheric and ionospheric phase delays and solid earth tides. The resulting displacement time series are referenced to GNSS data (only one constant is adjusted per independently-processed frame) and decomposed into one linear and two seasonal terms. We present the InSAR-based velocity field for this region corresponding to the linear term dominated by tectonics, and analyze its spatial variations in map and along key profiles across the main faults. We also

decompose this linear term into horizontal (parallel to GNSS velocity vectors in ITRF) and vertical components.

Our results show a good first order agreement with GNSS data and with the most recent GNSS-based elastic-kinematic block models for the region (Ellis *et al.*, 2019; Garnier *et al.*, 2021; 2022). They highlight the North America and Caribbean plates' relative motion, accommodated mainly on the Motagua fault as well as on the Polochic fault. They also evidence significant internal east-west extension of the Caribbean plate between Honduras and western Guatemala, and show right-lateral slip across the Mid-America arc, with a clear velocity contrast across the El Salvador fault zone. The unprecedented high spatial density of our InSAR results allows to reveal a 40 km-long creeping section along the Motagua fault; we extract the along-strike variations of the creep and discuss them in regards of the local geology and of the co- and post-seismic slip distribution of the 1976 earthquake. Due to their sensitivity to vertical motion, our InSAR measurements also will allow more refined estimates of lateral coupling variations along the subduction interface. We illustrate such sensitivity through forward block models with varying coupling values and depths along the subduction.

Index Terms— InSAR, Active tectonics, Crustal deformation, Sentinel 1, Guatemala, Central America

Figure 1: Line of sight (LOS) velocity extracted from time series of Sentinel-1 SAR images from ascending tracks 63 and 136 (left), and descending tracks 26 and 128 (right). Circles show the horizontal GPS velocities from Garnier *et al.* (2022) projected onto line of sight direction. Gray lines represent the profiles such as those shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: LOS velocities along profiles 5 and 6 as shown in Figure 1, for ascending (left) and descending (right) tracks. Discontinuous black lines denote the crossing of faults as located by the block boundaries defined by Ellis *et al.* (2019). PF: Polochic fault; MF: Motagua fault; VAF: Volcanic arc faults. GPS velocities are projected as in Figure 1.

Figure 3: Example of a 2.5 km halfwidth profile crossing the Motagua fault. Velocities are in LOS direction. The step-like velocity change across the fault suggests the occurrence of creep. The magnitude of creep (red) has been estimated using linear regression on both sides of the fault.

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DETECTING SLOW-MOVING LANDSLIDES IN SOUTH AMERICA USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS AND INSAR.

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ABSTRACT

Gravitational instabilities, such as debris flows and landslides, are widespread phenomena occurring in any environment with slopes. These events exhibit a wide variety of mechanisms and forcings [1], with down-slope speeds ranging from slow-moving (\sim mm/year) to rapid, catastrophic failures (\sim m/s) that can transition unpredictably between the two. Indeed, landslides may creep slowly [1] or accelerate suddenly [1], underscoring the complex and intertwined nature of their dynamics, which makes anticipating their behavior difficult. Without more observations and case studies, envisioning the future activity of such events remains a challenge. Mapping and inventorying historical and active landslide areas, as well as zones of susceptibility, is crucial for understanding their behavior and constraining the potential triggers.

With the rapid growth of high-resolution imagery (such as Sentinel-1 & 2, Pleiades, etc.), we now have the opportunity to analyze and monitor large spatial areas, hence covering many landslide events in unprecedented detail. However, manually processing these events across different datasets is time-consuming and impractical. Moreover, field observations, which are critical for understanding the forcings and dynamics of landslides, remain scarce. This highlights the urgent need for automated methods to detect landslides efficiently, enhancing our ability to understand their underlying causes and improve their hazard assessment.

Several recent efforts [2, 3, 4] have considered the use of deep learning for landslide segmentation/mapping, identifying the pixels and areas in satellite images that correspond to landslides. However, due to the difficulty of labeling the training data, each study focused on small regions and had limited testing data images. Here, we propose a large landslide inventory and a more systematic approach to detect any small deformation due to landslides with a deep learning algorithm (U-Net) [5] using wrapped SAR interferograms

over South America. Across South America, many active landslides are either sporadically mapped or entirely unknown. Creating an inventory is far from complete, as it relies on fieldwork and/or visual analysis of remote sensing data by geological surveys. Thanks to regional studies and historical inventories such as in Fabrizio et al., 2022 [6], South America appears as a predilection site to build mass movement inventories given the large size of the natural objects that we can identify as well as their frequent occurrences, notably given the important seismic activity.

To train the U-Net algorithm [5], we use InSAR phase data information processed by the FLATSIM initiative [7,8] over several Sentinel-1 tracks in South America (Figure 1). We inspected the phase of all the 2-looks wrapped interferograms with a temporal baseline of 12 days over 2019 and manually contoured all the phase patterns that could correspond to landslide activity. We confirmed this mapping using optical images, InSAR phase gradient analysis [9], and digital elevation models [10]. For instance, we mapped more than 3000 landslide occurrences over the Sentinel-1 descending track 25 over 120 000 km² (Figure 1). Using this inventory, we created landslides snapshot inputs of size 160x160 pixels and their associated binary mask denoting the presence (or absence) of deformation (Figure 1). We apply several data augmentations such as random rotation (90°, 180°, 270°) and random horizontal and vertical flips to increase the training batch size virtually. The preliminary results of this analysis demonstrate the efficiency of the U-Net algorithm for the segmentation of SAR images to detect mass movements. We obtain preliminary satisfactory IOU scores (>0.6) (Intersection over Union), a metric that evaluates the overlap correspondence between predicted and ground truth regions in object segmentation.

Besides the evident use of this algorithm for rapid post-earthquake or extreme climatic event landslide disaster assessment, the freely open-database landslide data that this work will enable is an achievement on its own. Indeed, the

systematic identification and classification of landslides over South America will enable targeted mitigation of risk and hazard of unknown events. This study will illuminate and refine landslide forcings such as climate-driven (el niño/la niña) and anthropogenic (growth of cities, dam ruptures, etc.) activations, with simple large-scale statistics.

Further work is needed to assess the impact of possible other entry channels on the learning ability of the algorithm, such as the DEM, the interferometric coherence, and other labeled data objects (mining sites, cities, etc.). Still, we plan to refine the training by using inventories in different areas (such as

the French Alps) to get an algorithm capable of identifying any landslide independently of the area.

This study demonstrates the potential of CNNs for detecting landslide activity using wrapped interferograms. This successful application of AI to geosciences paves the way for more efficient and automated analysis of landslide activity in different contexts, thereby contributing to an enhanced assessment of natural hazards.

Index Terms— InSAR, Geodesy, Landslides, FLATSIM, Machine Learning, Convolutional Neural Network.

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Figure 1. A - Landslide inventory over the Sentinel-1 descending track 25 made out of the manual identification of fringe patterns in the 2-looks wrapped interferograms over 2019 produced from the FLATSIM initiative. The green rectangle delineates the area where the interferogram in Fig - 1B has been extracted. B - Architecture of the convolutional network, ingesting phase information from wrapped interferograms of 160x160 pixels and giving a binary mask as output.

ADVANCES AND CHALLENGES FOR ALOS-2 SCANSAR TIME-SERIES ANALYSIS IN EQUATORIAL REGIONS

AVANCÉES ET DÉFIS POUR LE CALCUL DE SERIES TEMPORELLES ALOS-2 SCANSAR DANS LES RÉGIONS EQUATORIALES

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ABSTRACT

Producing continuous ground motion measurements from InSAR in Equatorial regions is challenging due to the dense vegetation reducing the interferometric coherence. We demonstrate here the potential of a temporally dense L-band ALOS-2 ScanSAR archive to investigate subtle ground motions in densely vegetated areas. We face several issues in the InSAR time-series analysis processing stemming from the specificities of the acquisition mode and the extremely low-coherence over the Amazonian Forest. However, using an optimized workflow, we derive LOS velocities for a 350 by 350 km² area in Ecuador, with an accuracy of about 4 mm/yr. Further work is required to reconcile the velocities in the lowlands and in the cordilleras, by removing topography-dependent phase owing to mixed fading signals and tropospheric delays.

1. ALOS-2 SCANSAR DATA

The ALOS-2 satellite, loaded with the SAR sensor PALSAR-2 and launched by the JAXA in 2014 is intended to continue the trend of L-band observations initiated by ALOS-PALSAR. This mission was also designed to overcome the limitations of its predecessor: long revisit time, small swath-width and poor orbit control. Thus, the PALSAR-2 sensor features notably a ScanSAR mode, used predominantly in the ALOS-2 observation scenario. This acquisition mode offers the best compromise between a large number of acquisitions and a wide coverage with a single frame. ALOS-2 ScanSAR data is acquired mostly in descending mode, and each frame covers a ~350 by 350 km² area. I processed the frame 3650 of the descending track 139, covering a large part of Ecuador (Fig. 1), and for which I could access to 68 acquisitions spanning from April 2017 to December 2023, or about 10 acquisitions per year on average. For comparison, the average number of yearly acquisitions of ALOS-1-PALSAR was about 4. The revisit time varies between 14 and 42 days for this ALOS-2 ScanSAR dataset. Most of the perpendicular baselines are comprised within a ~300 m orbital tube, another

improvement compared to ALOS-1, which commonly had perpendicular baselines >1000 m.

However, this acquisition mode has some specificities, such as the fact that the SAR images divided into 5 sub-swaths in the range direction (Fig. 1a), named F1 to F5. Most of the interferometric processing is done independently for each sub-swath, but they must be merged before the phase unwrapping step. Moreover, each of the ScanSAR acquisition represents a large amount of data (~60 Gb), leading to very heavy computations during all steps of the processing, especially when compared to ALOS-1 (~1.5 Gb per image).

Thus, beyond the objective of deriving robust deformation maps in Ecuador, and more generally in vegetated areas, the use of the ALOS-2 ScanSAR data raises several methodological questions: *How to build a processing workflow for this type of data optimizing the quality of the time-series with the minimal computational burden? Has the ScanSAR mode a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio to derive robust ground motion measurements? Does the increase in revisit time with respect to ALOS-PALSAR actually allow to mitigate the residual sources of noise (mainly ionospheric)?*

2. METHODS

350 interferograms from the 68 available ALOS-2 ScanSAR acquisitions, with temporal baselines up to one year. The processing strategy used is a mix of the GMTSAR chain (Sandwell et al., 2016) and the NSBAS chain (Doin et al., 2011). GMTSAR is used for the pre-processing, the coregistration of SLCs, the computation of the geometric delay from a Copernicus 30 m DEM, the computation of interferograms, and the merge of subswaths. Note that the interferograms are multilooked by a factor 4 in range and 16 in azimuth. The GMTSAR workflow for ALOS-2 ScanSAR data had to be adapted to handle the processing of interferograms in parallel, to reduce the time of computation, and to perform the coregistration of all SLCs to a single reference. The NSBAS chain is used for the computation of colinearity, additional weighting by temporal coherence,

further multilooking by factors 8 in range and 32 in azimuth, unwrapping and time-series inversion.

Two main issues, arising from the ScanSAR acquisition mode had to be tackled. First, the coregistration step, which was not accurate enough in the low-coherence areas, was optimized by improving the pixel offset culling and inverting the offset fit parameters into a time-series. Second, the split-spectrum ionospheric correction was improved by refining the estimation of phase offsets between sub-swaths for sub-band interferograms. However, in the areas of too low coherence, part of this last issue remained and prevented to use the computed ionospheric phase screens to correct the data. Instead, a quadratic spatial phase fit proved to be more efficient in mitigating the ionosphere, which is spatially smooth in this dataset.

Further improvements were applied to the time-series: overweighting of long-baseline interferograms in order to reduce the impact of fading signals and removal of a phase-elevation relationship phase correlated to topography.

3. PRELIMINARY CONCLUSIONS

Our preliminary time-series analysis results confirm that ALOS-2 ScanSAR data can be used to derive velocity maps in densely vegetated areas. Several methodological challenges had to be overcome to produce a reliable time-series, which may explain why no time-series using ALOS-2 ScanSAR data for tectonic studies was published until now. Although some of these challenges may be specific to the equatorial location of the study area (poor coherence and ionospheric noise), tackling these issues is highly important, since it is in equatorial or low-coherence areas that the use of L-band InSAR is the most relevant.

The obtained time-series has a satisfying level of noise, confined below 4 mm/yr for the resulting velocities. More importantly, velocities could be computed even in the lowlands, including the Subandean domain and the Amazonian basin. This velocity field exhibits an ambiguous signal over the flank of the Cutucú Cordillera in the Subandean belt, requiring more work to confirm its tectonic origin. A map of the coseismic displacement associated with a $M_w 7.4$ intermediate depth earthquake which occurred in 2019 could also be derived.

Nevertheless, these results are preliminary and more work has to be done aiming to improve and validate them. First, the split-spectrum corrections computed here is still unsatisfying, due to inaccurate correction of phase offsets during the merging of sub-band interferograms, and could be further improved. Another main concern about the processed time-series is the strong dependence of velocities on elevation, with overall positive velocities on the cordillera and negative ones in the lowlands. While such pattern is generally interpreted as tropospheric delays revealed by the

Figure 1. Coverage of ALOS-2 ScanSAR used in this study, together with (a) topography, (b) interferometric coherence, (c) optical satellite image and (d) RMS misclosure of the time-series.

large topographic contrasts, I suggest here that it could stem from fading signals. Indeed, the land cover varies radically with elevation, going from a dense rainforest at low-elevation to specific Andean ecosystems (*páramo*) in the highest areas of the cordilleras (Fig. 1c). I show that these different types of vegetations have different mean velocities, probably due to fading signals. Therefore, fading signals may result in topography-correlated phase in the time-series which is difficult to discriminate from the stratified tropospheric noise.

Overall, these results illustrate the capabilities of a temporally dense L-band SAR archive to investigate ground motion in densely vegetated areas. However, they also highlight the challenges to overcome in order to process ScanSAR data in thus contexts and to isolate the deformation signals from other contributions. The sensitivity to ionospheric noise is known to be a main limitation of L-band SAR, yet, these results suggests that a large number of acquisitions is efficient at reducing the impact of random ionospheric noise on the final velocities. By contrast, fading signals will likely represent a major challenge for this type of data in the years to come due to the reduction of revisit time.

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AUTOMATIC DETECTION OF VOLCANIC FISSURES IN SAR INTERFEROGRAMS WITH MACHINE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose to explore the potential of machine learning techniques for automatic detection of volcanic fissures in SAR interferograms. A dataset of 334 interferograms over the Piton de la Fournaise volcano covering the period from 1998 to 2022, issued from multiple sensors, are available. Starting from frugal machine learning models, we focus on proper data preparation. The first results obtained with Random Forest confirm the interest of machine learning methods for volcanic fissures detection and open perspectives for exploring more complex machine learning model architectures.

1. INTRODUCTION

Interferometric SAR (InSAR) provides precise displacement measurements over large areas, making it a crucial tool for monitoring volcanic activity [3]. The identification of volcanic fissures on interferograms is particularly important for accurate volcano modeling. Currently, the localization of these fissures is mainly performed manually by experts. However, with the continuous increase in SAR data, there is a growing need for advanced methods that can automate this detection process efficiently. To address this challenge, we leverage the recent advancements in machine learning (ML), which have proven to be effective in numerous studies across various domains. For instance, ML techniques have been successfully applied to detect ground deformation in the built environment using real sparse satellite InSAR data [2], as well as in volcanic areas using synthetic InSAR data [1, 5]. In this study, we explore machine learning techniques, e.g. random forest, for automatic detection and precise localisation of volcanic fissures on interferograms.

2. METHODOLOGY

The dataset consists of 334 interferograms over the Piton de la Fournaise volcano [4] from the period between 1998 and 2022, with a total of 118 labeled fissures. The interferograms are derived from long-term analysis of 7 satellite data. Table 1 summarizes the characteristics of the database and gives the number of interferograms available per satellite.

Table 1: Satellite and available InSAR fissure-label.

Satellite	Band	λ (cm)	Nb InSAR
ALOS 1	L	23.6	12
ALOS 2	L	24.98	43
ENVISAT-ASAR	C	5.66	95
RADARSAT-1	C	5.66	18
RADARSAT-2	C	5.55	11
SENTINEL-1	C	5.55	88
COSMO-SkyMed	X	3.12	49
TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X	X	3.5	14
PAZ	X	3.5	4

We formulate the volcanic fissures detection as a classification problem. The methodology developed in this study is illustrated in Figure 1. For each satellite and spatial resolution, interferograms are divided into patches of specific sizes (8x8, 16x16, 32x32, 64x64, and 128x128 pixels). Each patch is then labeled based on whether it overlaps with a volcanic fissure or not. To ensure balanced classes during classification, the number of patches containing a fissure (label 1) and those without a fissure (label 0) is adjusted for each interferogram. In the same interferogram, the class with the highest number of representatives is randomly subsampled to have the same number of patches as the least represented class. This subsampling operation is performed 30 times to obtain a standard deviation of the classification performance. Finally, a random forest classification with 100 estimators is performed using leave-one-group-out training to guarantee the absence of patches belonging to the same interferogram between the train set and the validation set.

3. RESULTS

Results are shown in Figure 2 for both overall accuracy and fissure (label 1) class precision. Accuracy shows the proportion of all correct classifications with and without fissure with respect to the total number of classifications achieved. In all cases, the minimum accuracy is 50% and it reaches a maximum of 94%, with low variability in all experiments. Regardless of the satellite, the accuracy tends to decrease with increasing patch size, except for ALOS2 and ENVISAT-ASAR. Low accuracy with large

Figure 1: Overall methodology for fissure patches classification.

Figure 2: Performance metrics across different patch sizes for each satellite.

path size for ALOS1 and RADATSAT-1 show low fissure class precision under 40%. In this case, the majority of fissure detections by the ML model are incorrect, as false positives. The model has some difficulty in distinguishing real fissures from other terrain features, due to the low resolution and large patch size, which introduces more noise into interferograms. Conversely, PAZ, TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X satellites give higher spatial resolution and less data noise, benefiting the classification performance in terms of accuracy and precision.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The first results obtained confirm the potential of using machine learning techniques for automatic volcanic fissures detection. Later on, we will gradually progress towards more complex machine learning architectures in order to further improve the accuracy.

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UN NOUVEAU JEU DE DONNÉES POUR LA DÉTECTION D'INSTABILITÉS GRAVITAIRES DANS LES ALPES À PARTIR D'INTERFÉROGRAMMES SAR

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ABSTRACT

La détection d'instabilités gravitaires revêt de nombreuses contraintes à la fois liées aux phénomènes en question mais aussi aux données et aux outils à disposition. En effet, dû à la grande variabilité des phénomènes géophysiques en sous sol, leur compréhension et leur détection en surface, notamment à l'aide d'images de télédétection, est une tâche complexe. Une approche largement exploitée en volcanologie consiste à étudier des interférogrammes SAR pour prévenir les changements d'activité à l'aide d'apprentissage automatique [1]. Mais même si les interférogrammes ont déjà été exploités pour la détection d'instabilités [2], [3], il n'existe pas de jeu de données exploitable pour l'implémentation d'approches automatiques. Dans ces travaux nous proposons tout d'abord une nouvelle routine d'identification d'instabilités gravitaires lentes à partir d'interférogrammes. Cette routine est ensuite exploitée afin de créer en nouveau jeu de données ISSLIDE [4] (pour *Interferogram dataset for Slow SLIding area DETection*) pour la détection de régions en mouvement dans les Alpes à l'aide d'apprentissage automatique. L'exploitabilité de ce jeu de données est enfin démontrée en entraînant cinq réseaux de segmentations standards de la littérature. Un aperçu de l'ensemble des étapes est donné en Figure 1.

I. ROUTINE D'IDENTIFICATION MANUELLE

Afin de proposer une routine efficace d'identification d'instabilités gravitaires lentes à partir d'images satellitaires, le choix s'est porté sur l'utilisation d'interférogrammes générés à partir d'images SAR Sentinel-1. En effet, ce type de données permet de détecter des mouvements centimétriques malgré la résolution décimétrique des images SAR. Afin de rendre la routine d'identification la plus généralisable possible, la génération d'interférogrammes ne requiert que le Modèle Numérique de Terrain (MNT) SRTM HGT 1sec pour être appliquée. Ainsi, si le déphasage topographique est corrigé à l'aide de ce MNT, aucune correction atmosphérique n'est appliquée aux interférogrammes générés. Deux produits sont délivrés à la sortie de cette génération : une carte de cohérence ρ et une carte de différence de phases φ , formant l'interférogramme complexe $\rho e^{i\varphi}$.

Ces deux cartes ont ensuite servi de base pour la détection de régions affectées par des mouvements gravitaires lents. Une stratégie d'annotation a été mise en place en collaboration avec des géomorphologues des laboratoires EDYTEM et ISTerre afin d'assurer que les zones identifiées rassemblent effectivement les caractéristiques types de mouvements gravitaires tels

que des glissements de terrain et des glaciers rocheux. Cette stratégie consiste tout d'abord en l'identification de motifs dits de franges ou de bulles sur la carte de différence de phases. De tels motifs permettent de mieux cerner les régions de potentiels dangers car leur comportement diffère de celui des zones connexes. Afin de valider la détection, une série de vérifications est alors appliquée. Premièrement, la valeur de la carte de cohérence dans cette région doit être suffisamment élevée pour garantir la fiabilité de la phase, le mouvement n'étant pas suffisamment conséquent pour provoquer une perte de cohérence sur la zone. Deuxièmement, même si certains mouvements peuvent être sujets à des périodes d'inactivité, une continuité temporelle du mouvement est attendue d'un interférogramme à l'autre. Troisièmement, le mouvement détecté doit être visible sur des interférogrammes avec une base temporelle différente (e.g. 6, 12 et 18 jours). Enfin une vérification optique à l'aide d'images SPOT6-7 permet de filtrer les phénomènes qui ne correspondent pas aux caractéristiques géomorphologiques de surface des phénomènes étudiés.

II. ISSLIDE

La routine d'identification est appliquée à la détection de mouvements sur les produits SLC acquis par Sentinel-1 en mode IW et en polarisation VV durant des passes descendantes. Ces images ont été obtenues entre le 2 juillet 2018 et le 24 octobre 2018 avec une répétitivité de 6 jours. De cette façon, 19, 18 et 17 interférogrammes ont été générés suivant trois bases temporelles différentes : 6, 12 et 18 jours. Trois régions des Alpes françaises ont été particulièrement ciblées : le massif de la Vanoise, le nord-est du parc des Écrins ainsi que le parc du Queyras. Un total de 136 mouvements ont été détectés manuellement dans ces régions en appliquant la stratégie d'annotation. Afin de compléter ce jeu de données, 64 mouvements supplémentaires, identifiés en dehors de ces régions, ont été ajoutés afin d'apporter une plus grande variabilité aux données.

Le jeu de données résultant, baptisé ISSLIDE (pour *Interferogram dataset for Slow SLIding area DETection*), est mis à disposition sur IEEE Dataport (<https://iee-dataport.org/documents/isslide-insar-dataset-slow-sliding-area-detection-machine-learning>) sous deux configurations. La première, brute, contient les interférogrammes et les shapefiles des polygones. La seconde contient 13,230 imagettes de taille 100x100 pixels autour des mouvements, illustrées dans la boîte verte de la Figure 1. Ces imagettes annotées permettent une utilisation directe par des approches d'apprentissage automatique.

Fig. 1: Routine permettant la génération et l'exploitation du jeu de données ISSLIDE. Modifié de [4].

III. DÉTECTION AUTOMATIQUE

Afin de vérifier l'applicabilité de méthodes d'apprentissage automatique au jeu de données, plusieurs réseaux de neurones standards ont été implémentés dans le but de segmenter les mouvements sur les interférogrammes. Ainsi, cinq réseaux ont été testés : FCN [5] et DeepLabV3 [6] dont l'implémentation était disponible sous Pytorch, ainsi que trois versions de U-Net peu profondes avec des convolutions standards [7], des blocs résiduels [8] et des convolutions séparées [9].

Pour éviter les problématiques liées à la rotation de la phase, les interférogrammes sont fournis au réseau sous la forme d'une image à trois canaux contenant la carte de cohérence, le cosinus et le sinus de la différence de phase comme indiqué sur la droite de la Figure 1. L'entraînement des réseaux est configuré pour éviter le surapprentissage et assurer des comparaisons équitables.

Les résultats obtenus par ces réseaux permettent de démontrer non seulement l'exploitabilité du jeu de données ISSLIDE pour l'entraînement de réseaux standards mais aussi la complexité de la tâche visée. En effet, les réseaux pré-entraînés sur le jeu de données PASCAL VOC contenant des images standards en vision par ordinateur ne sont pas transférables au traitement d'interférogrammes. De fait, les réseaux de neurones ne peuvent pas bénéficier des connaissances d'autres types d'images ce qui limite donc l'utilisation de réseaux de neurones très profonds. Si les résultats montrent que FCN achève les résultats les plus intéressants, il est à noter que le réseau U-Net peu profond avec des blocs résiduels est particulièrement compétitif et beaucoup moins exigeant d'un point de vue computationnel. Ceci ouvre des perspectives d'exploitation de réseaux peu profonds pour le traitement de données interférométriques.

Mots clés - InSAR, ISSLIDE, Instabilités gravitaires, Apprentissage profond

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EVOLUTION OF THE MERAPI SUMMIT AREA RELATED TO THE 2021-2023 EFFUSIVE ERUPTION, AS REVEALED BY RADAR AND OPTICAL SATELLITE IMAGERY

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ABSTRACT

Time series of radar (TanDEM-X and Sentinel-1) and optical (Pleiades) images are used jointly to monitor topographic changes and surface displacements in the summit area of Merapi volcano, Indonesia, during the last effusive eruption. Precursors are detected in the form of topographic changes and flank sliding, and the volume of magma emitted during the eruption is quantified.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tracking the summit activity of steep-sloped vegetated stratovolcanoes is a challenge, as changes, including unrest, viscous lava dome growth or derived deposits, can be of various extents, amplitudes and durations. It is also a necessity, as they are responsible for most of the historical fatalities caused by volcanoes [1]. As ground-based instruments have limited spatial resolutions, satellite imagery is a promising tool to map both localized and spread deformation on hazardous stratovolcanoes [2]. In addition, the joint use of radar and optical satellite capabilities ultimately allows to partly overcome their respective limitations, notably by increasing the temporal sampling of observations.

Taking advantage of both high and medium resolution radar and optical satellite data, this study aims to provide the first comprehensive observations of surface changes at Merapi, Indonesia, associated with the eruption of the two summit lava domes in January 2021, one in the crater and one the Southwest flank rim.

2. TOPOGRAPHIC CHANGES QUANTIFIED BY DEM DIFFERENCING

Using 3m-resolution DEM differences with respect to 2013, produced from high resolution TanDEM-X and Pléiades, we measure the destruction of an old lava flow from 1997 in June 2020, co-located with the upcoming January 2021 flank dome. We also show that the new 2021 lava domes volume estimates are about 3 times higher than the 2018 eruption [3]. Similarly to 2018, the domes first undergo a rapid growth, until reaching a maximum constant volume of

$3.4 \pm 0.7 \text{ Mm}^3$ by July 2021. However, we demonstrate that the domes remained active after July 2021, with new lava supply balanced by gravitational collapses, thanks to the mapping of deposition areas below. We note that, contrary to the crater dome, our flank domes estimates do not fully agree with independent drone measurements: it highlights the challenges for satellite imagery induced by the steep topography of the crater rim.

3. SURFACE DISPLACEMENTS RETRIEVED FROM TIME SERIES OF OPTICAL AND SAR IMAGES

Taking advantage of additional Sentinel-1 LOS deformation time-series, corrected from tropospheric noise using a dedicated GNSS-based strategy, and Pléiades horizontal displacement time-series, we detect several important surface modifications on the upper flanks of Merapi prior to the January 2021 eruption. On the West flank, along with the destruction of the old lava flow from 1997, we measure a metric sliding of three other flows (1888, 1992 and one unidentified), and a centimetric sliding of the rest of the flank. On the East flank, we observe centimetric transient inflation of 3 cm/yr (see Figure).

4. INTERPRETATION & CONCLUSION

Challenges still remain in the understanding of the interplay between the volcanic activity and the aforementioned surface changes on the flanks, which can be interpreted as precursors: from the chronology of events, we suggest that the upper West flank motion was likely first triggered by explosions in June 2020, and further sustained by the shallow rising of magma between June-December 2020, as simultaneous small inflation was observed on the East flank. Moreover, we propose the 1888 flow might accelerate concurrently with successive rises of magma batches seen by shallow seismicity. We also suggest that the destruction of the summit 1997 flow is likely to have modified the direction of propagation of the shallow magma and its exit location, with the emplacement of an unexpected flank dome. Only further modelling will hopefully help address this scenario.

Overall, we state that the joint use of radar and optical satellite imagery is crucial to detect the widest range (cm to m) and extent (m to km) of deformation possible at continuously active and hazardous stratovolcanoes like Merapi. This study brings out that Merapi is a multi-hazard volcano, with both effusive eruptions and flank sliding that can occur jointly.

Index Terms— InSAR, Pléiades, TanDEM-X, Sentinel-1, time-series, lava domes, Merapi

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Figure 1. Summary of the spatial and temporal distribution of the deformation since 2018 at Merapi. Panel A: Panchromatic view from 2023-09-30, along with the contours of the main deformation measured in this study. On the West flank: in pink, the contour of the LOS displacement away from Sentinel-1; in orange, the contour of the non-filtered horizontal displacements above 3 m, seen by Pléiades pixel-offset tracking; in shaded orange, the 1888 and 1992 flows metric sliding; in shaded blue, the 50 m pit from 1997 flow, seen by DEM differences; in black and red, the respective contours from the 2021 flank and crater domes. On the East flank: the blue contour delineates the LOS displacement towards Sentinel-1. Panel B: (B1) BPPTKG drone lava dome volumes (red for crater, black for flank), (B2) ERA-5 precipitation rate, (B3) number of seismic daily rock falls (gold) and MP events (red), (B4) Pléiades horizontal displacement time-series (in m) of the 1888 flow, shown on Panel C, (B5) Sentinel-1 LOS displacement time-series (in cm) of points on the West (red, orange) and East flanks (blue). The 3 main magma rising episodes deduced from seismic data and lava volumes are indicated below. Panel C: Zoom over the 1888 sliding flow, delineated in black. Comparison of the date 2021-07-29 seen by both Pléiades (PL) and Sentinel-1 (S-1). Note the areas where InSAR loses information correspond to areas of metric displacement seen by Pléiades.

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SUB-PIXEL DISPLACEMENT ESTIMATION FROM OPTICAL SATELLITE IMAGES USING A NEW HYPER-REALISTIC EARTHQUAKE DATABASE AND U-NET ARCHITECTURE

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ABSTRACT

Estimating the ground displacement from non-rigid registration of two optical satellite images, separated from hours to months, is key in the study of natural disasters such as earthquakes. Compared to standard image registration and flow estimation tasks, a key challenge here lies in resolving very small displacements (typically cm- or m-scale) with sub-pixel accuracy and precision using coarser image resolutions (e.g. 15m for Landsat-8). Traditional block matching/sliding window methods, employing local windowed correlation techniques, are unable to reduce the effects of long-wavelength noise arising from differences in image lighting, vegetation, or acquisition artifacts. By using both local and global scales, fully convolutional deep learning registration models (U-nets) are able to better resolve ground displacements, less affected by multi-scale noise. Yet, no labelled database exists for ground deformation. Here, we develop a new synthetic database of 40,000 realistic satellite image pairs containing simulated earthquake displacements, along with their ground truth displacement maps, which are used to train state-of-the-art fully convolutional deep learning models (U-net). The results are improving the state-of-the-art, with a fast computation time (less than 1 second for a 256x256 image) and applicability on different real acquisitions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Precise estimation of ground displacement from the registration of optical satellite images is fundamental for the study of natural disasters. In the case of earthquakes, characterizing near-field displacements around surface ruptures provides valuable constraints on the physics of earthquake slip. Optical satellite geodesy, particularly through Optical Image Correlation (OIC), has transformed the characterization of ground deformation linked to natural hazards such as earthquakes. In earthquake studies, the displacements can often be relatively small compared to the image pixel size, and may also vary spatially in a complex manner: sub-pixel precision and high spatial detail are therefore crucial for accurately capturing the complex variations in displacement values associated with earthquake surface ruptures.

OIC methods for quantifying image displacement have traditionally employed a sliding window approach, in which the displacement is resolved at high frequencies using cross correlation. This may be achieved either in the spatial domain [1] or frequency domains as the COSI-Corr software [2]. Displacement field estimation between two images can also be efficiently solved by deep learning, e.g. treating optical flow estimation as a learning task. The large majority of deep learning image registration and flow estimation approaches are derived from fully-

Figure 1: Pipeline of the proposed method

convolutional U-net architectures. However, they focus on the estimation of large displacements (>1 pixel) from temporally dense datasets (e.g. typical of video feeds), while the estimation of smaller sub-pixel shifts from temporally limited and distant acquisitions (e.g. typical of remotely sensed images) has been little studied. Few recent studies have however demonstrated the potential of neural network architectures to also retrieve sub-pixel displacements [3]. In [4], we developed a deep learning method to estimate ground displacement maps with sub-pixel precision from optical satellite images. The approach relied on the same principle as state-of-the-art OIC approaches, by working at the local scale with small windows (typically 16×16 or 32×32 pixels), while making the assumption of a locally rigid and non-rotating transformation; the translational displacement between the two windows is evaluated using a CNN. While this method, called CNN-DIS, has improved the accuracy with respect to traditional OIC methods in discontinuity areas, thanks to a specific discontinuity simulated training dataset, it does not solve all their limitations; as such, we are still sensitive to image noise arising from differences in lightning, vegetation, anthropic changes, acquisition artifacts, etc.

2. METHODS

In this new work, we propose a U-net-based method to solve the sub-pixel displacement estimation problem at a global scale. Such architecture incorporates contracting and expansive paths, and is able to retrieve full scale surface displacement maps, making use of both global and local features, which allow to further reduce the displacement noise resulting from differences in the input images. To do so, we trained our model with a newly generated synthetic database: 1024×1024 real LandSat-8 acquisitions, warped with 40,000 different ultra-realistic synthetic displacement maps, representing realistic fault ruptures of varying magnitudes. The pipeline of the model is presented in Figure 1. We used a U-net architecture named FlowNet2-SD from FlowNet2.0 [3], which is built to tackle more specifically subpixel tracking. We trained the models for 40 epochs from 256×256 window sized input, but we can process larger windows at inference.

3. RESULTS

We can see from Figure 2 an example of results on a real case (Rigcrest Pléiades acquisitions). We can compare two U-net models, FlowNet2-SD and StrainNet-F, with COSI-Corr, MicMac and CNN-DIS. We can see that the two U-net approaches are giving cleaner results, which is what we can also see quantitatively over the whole synthetic test set: for small displacements, the mean EPE (endpoint error) is significantly lower for FlowNet2-SD (0.169) and StrainNet-F (0.169) than COSI-Corr (0.261) or CNN-DIS (0.694). Finally, in terms of computation time, our new approach running on 1 GPU and can process 30 times more displacement estimations each second than a 32cores CPU COSI-Corr, and 100 more displacement estimations than a 32cores CPU MicMac.

Index Terms— Optical correlation, deep learning

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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Figure 2: East-West component results from Pléiades Ridgcrest earthquake, in meters.

ATMOSPHERIC CORRECTION IN EXTREME MOUNTAINOUS CONTEXT: THE NANGA PARBAT

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ABSTRACT

The Nanga Parbat is a massif with an elevation of more than 8000m located in the northwestern syntaxis of the Himalaya. This massif is considered to be a crustal diapir that is currently undergoing an uplift acceleration of about 1cm/yr based on thermo- and geochronological data (Crowley et al., 2009; Guevara et al., 2022). Recent GNSS data also indicate asymmetric displacement, with the western side of the massif moving westward due to the presence of the active Liachar thrust fault, while the eastern side is stable (Jouanne et al., 2020). In addition to GNSS data, InSAR can provide good spatial coverage of the surface displacement over the entire massif to better understand the current dynamics of the region. However, the Nanga Parbat area is a complex region for the application of InSAR due to the snow cover, the high altitude and the highly variable topography.

1. INSAR DATA

To apply the InSAR method over Nanga Parbat, we used Sentinel-1 data from 2 ascending tracks (A100 & A027) and 2 descending tracks (D107 & D034). The selected images run from July to November, covering the period from 2014 to the end of 2022, to avoid winter scenes with too much snow. Using the NSBAS processing chain (Doin et al., 2011; Thollard et al. 2021), we processed interferograms with temporal baselines from 12 days to 2 years and spatial baselines smaller than 200 m. A large number of 1-year interferograms are computed to have sufficient connections over the 6-month "winter gaps". The 30 m spatial resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM) from the Copernicus mission is used to apply the topographic correction to the interferograms.

2. ATMOSPHERIC CORRECTION

Apart from the loss of coherence due to snow cover, the main problem with the interferograms we obtained is phase aliasing during the unwrapping process due to very narrow fringes in the valleys. The application of the usual ERA-5 atmospheric correction was not precise enough in the valleys

to correct the interferometric phase accurately. This may be because the spatial resolution of the model is too low and the extrapolation of the model in the deep and narrow valleys of this region is not accurate. To replace the ERA-5 corrections, we have used an empirical correction based on the relationship between the interferometric phase and elevation. The correction is estimated over a deliberately enlarged area around Nanga Parbat to have elevations between 500 m and 8100 m and to avoid correlating the surface deformation with the topography. These conditions limit the risk of over-fitting the phase/elevation ratio, which reduces the risk of removing the tectonic signal from the data. The empirical correction chosen is based on a linear fit as a function of elevation and azimuth of the phase/elevation ratio, inverting the coefficients obtained per interferogram to obtain coefficients less affected by noisy ratios. Once the correction is applied, we can see the reduction of the fringes, especially in the valleys, as shown in Figure 1. The interferograms are then multilooked with the collinearity method, gradient based filtered and unwrapped with a slope-based mask according to the procedure described in Doin et al. (2023).

3. FIRST RESULTS AND VALIDATION

Several temporal inversions allow some remaining unwrapping errors to be corrected using the Root Mean Square network misclosure maps. The first resulting linear velocity maps, extracted from the surface displacement cubes of ascending and descending tracks, are consistent with the expected surface deformations in the region. Nanga Parbat shows localised negative LOS velocities in the centre of the massif, which can be interpreted as uplift and/or westward displacement limited by the Liachar thrust fault and a very stable area around the massif.

Figure 1. Comparison of the different atmospheric corrections for the 20170915-20171009 interferogram: (a) raw interferogram, (b) empiric linear correction in function of elevation, (c) empiric linear correction in function of elevation and azimuth and (d) ERA5 correction.

Index Terms— InSAR, atmospheric correction, Sentinel-1, Himalaya, Nanga Parbat.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Sentinel-1 images are available on the CNES website. The Digital Terrain Model data products have been derived from the Copernicus mission.

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Coseismic slip segmentation of the Kahramanmaraş earthquake doublet (Türkiye, 2023)

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Abstract

Large continental strike-slip earthquakes usually present a complex rupture trace composed of several segments separated by discontinuities. Fault geometry may interact with stress concentration and rupture propagation and may have an influence on the distribution of coseismic slip and the termination of ruptures. Here we characterize these interactions in the case of the 2023 Mw 7.8 and Mw 7.5 Kahramanmaraş earthquake sequence that ruptured several fault segments of the East Anatolian fault in south-central Türkiye. It started on 6 February 2023, when the Mw 7.8 Pazarcık earthquake ruptured a 300 km portion of the East Anatolian Fault system after initiating on the Narlı splay fault. This earthquake was followed 9 hours later by the Mw 7.5 Elbistan earthquake that occurred on the nearby Surgu-Cardak fault zone. We model the coseismic slip distributions for these two earthquakes using geodetic data, including Sentinel-1 interferometry and pixel offset tracking, Sentinel-2 image correlation and GNSS offsets. We first compute a constrained least-squares solution in a 5-layer elastic medium and use it as a prior for Bayesian modeling with perturbed Green's functions. In our model, most of the slip occurs above 15 km depth, with a shallow slip deficit, and segmentation in the slip distribution coincides with geometrical complexities of the fault trace. We also build InSAR displacement time series spanning the first 10 months of the post-seismic phase and find that large coseismic slip patches and segments with relatively strong shallow afterslip and high aftershock density are often mutually exclusive. Furthermore, the segments with the most afterslip for both earthquakes are located at the northeastern end of the rupture trace, while the

southwestern ends of both ruptures only present relatively little shallow afterslip. Aftershocks also spread in a wide area around the southwestern tip of both ruptures compared to the rest of the fault. These observations may be related to the relative complexity of the southwestern termination of both earthquakes, where many splay faults or stepovers interact with the rupture, providing insights on the relationships between crustal damage, fault geometry and rupture propagation.

Coseismic slip distribution model of the 2023 Kahramanmaraş earthquake doublet

Keywords: Kahramanmaraş earthquakes, InSAR, coseismic slip, post-seismic slip, rupture segmentation

AMSTer GOES 3D, BUT NOT ONLY: WHAT IS NEW WITH THIS InSAR TIME SERIES SOFTWARE.

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ABSTRACT

AMSTer: “SAR & InSAR Automated Mass processing Software for Multi-dimensional Time series” (formerly named MasTer) is an open software dedicated to the processing of Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images [1]. It

is mostly designed to perform optimized mass processing of SAR differential interferometry (DInSAR) and automatic incremental production of ground deformation time series in one, two or three dimensions.

AMSTer can also be used to produce Digital Elevation Models (DEM), coherence maps and amplitude images time series e.g. for land cover or geomorphological changes, flood mapping etc...

We will describe the new functionalities of this software since its previous public release in 2022, that is mainly:

- 3D landslides tracking;
- 3D volcanic ground deformation time series;
- Multi-level masking;
- New tools for selecting interferometric pairs and testing baseline plots;
- New tool for geomorphological changes tracking (PickCraterSAR) [2]...

The most recent version of AMSTer also benefits from several efficiency improvements that are almost transparent to the user:

- More parallelisation at several steps;
- The possibility to split the MSBAS processing, so that only the most recent part of the time series is updated, without recomputing the unchanged beginning;
- The possibility to read compressed Sentinel-1 images to spare disc space;
- The stitching of only the Sentinel-1 bursts that overlap an area of interest (AoI) provided as a kml of any shape to spare disc space and computing time;
- The possibility to correct DEM from the geoidal heights (if the DEM is not referred to the ellipsoid yet) to improve geoprojection accuracy...

The code, the installer and the detailed manual are freely available at the GitHub repository under a CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 license (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International).

1. INTRODUCTION – WHAT IS AMSTer

AMSTer software [1] is made of three components:

1. An InSAR command line processor (the **AMSTer Engine**), written in C [3] ;
2. The **MSBAS** processor (for the computation of 2/3D time series of ground deformation), written in C++ [4];
3. A bunch of **shell and python scripts** automatizing all tasks (**AMSTer Toolbox**) [5].

It can process and combine data from nearly all the SAR sensor currently available (ERS 1 & 2, EnviSAT, ALOS, ALOS2, RadarSAT 1 & 2, CosmoSkyMed and CosmoSkymed Second Generation, TerraSAR-X, TanDEM-X (incl. bistatic and pursuit mode), Sentinel-1, Kompsat5, PAZ, SAOCOM, ICEYE...).

Launched with cron jobs, AMSTer can perform fully automatic processing from data download up to displaying 1, 2 or 3D time series results on a web page updated incrementally as soon as a new image (or orbit) is available. The incremental architecture allows updating the time series within the shortest time possible (typically a few hours) as soon as a new data is provided. Several steps are self-evaluating to ensure robust and reliable processing. Final amplitude, coherence and deformation maps (optionally detrended and/or interpolated to fill small gaps) are provided in standard Geographic Information System (GIS) format.

Among the specificities of AMSTer, one can remind the following tools (see [1,5] for more information):

- A coherence proxy to guide the pair selection optimization and balance the use of each image as *primary* and *secondary* image during DInSAR processing. This increases the processing efficiency and the signal-to-noise ratio of the time series [6] ;
- A tool to track possible unwrapping errors by checking the phase closure between triplets of DInSAR;

- A tool to select the best MSBAS inversion order and regularization factor [7] ;
- The possibility to manually or automatically quarantine image that are affected by unwanted characteristics (missing lines, artifacts etc.) ;
- The possibility to automatically recompute, as soon as a new (precise) orbit is made available, all the products already computed with the preliminary orbits ;
- The possibility to produce time series based on specific criteria (e.g. maximum spatial and temporal baselines) further filtered from pairs that would have a mean coherence (within an AoI) below a given threshold. This may be of interest e.g. for rejecting pairs affected by occasional or seasonal decorrelation (such as caused by snow cover etc) ;
- Tools to generate sequence of amplitude or coherence maps (including gif animations) to monitor ground cover or geomorphological changes over time...

2. NEW FUNCTIONALITIES

2.1: EW, NS and Vertical decomposition:

Because the SAR satellites are usually circling the Earth along subpolar orbits and looking only on their right side, InSAR measurements are nearly insensitive to displacements occurring in the North-South direction. This usually restrict the MSBAS inversion to the vertical and East-West components. This approximation was shown to be valid as long as the displacement in the North-South component is not significantly larger than in the other directions [8]. There are however two cases where one can hope to retrieve the full 3D decomposition: when one can assume that the displacements occur parallel to the surface (e.g. for slow-moving landslides or glacier flows) [4], or when there is enough diversity in the SAR looking geometries [9].

AMSTer is now able to routinely process these two cases. The first case requires to provide MSBAS with the DEM gradient maps in EW and NS directions as additional inversion constrain. This was achieved e.g. for the Funu landslide (DR Congo) as illustrated in Figure 1.

The second case is only achievable when the matrix made of all the Earth-to-Satellite vectors is of rank 3 and its conditioning number is small (< 100). This was achieved e.g. for the Piton de la Fournaise (Réunion Island) using ALOS2 images acquired in 27 different geometries combining right and left looking geometries along ascending and descending orbit (See D. Smittarello contribution; this issue).

2.2: Baseline plot selection: (M)SBAS inversion results strongly depend on the selection of pairs to invert, which are represented as a baseline plot. Several tools can be used to create the baseline plots:

- By selecting only the pairs with temporal (Bt) and spatial (Bp) baselines below given values. An option now offers the possibility to change the maximum Bt and Bp after a given date. This allows for instance to relax the pair selection criteria after a major change in

the orbital tube management policy (e.g. due to the loss of S-1B satellite or the S1-A orbital drift), without having to recompute additional pairs for the period prior to the change;

- By selecting all the pairs forming the most appropriate Delaunay triangulation graph. This implies to define as a parameter, an appropriate ratio between the units of the baseline plot axes (i.e. time and distances).
- By selecting the x shortest time connections between SAR images (where x is an integer).

Remember that any of these pair selections can be further filtered from pairs that would have a mean coherence (within an AoI) below a given threshold.

Figure 1: EW (blue), NS (red) and UD (green) double difference ground deformation time series between pixels in Funu landslide (DRC) marked by crosses in insets. Pixel to the right (yellow cross) moves toward the East, South and Up with respect to pixel to the left (white cross)

2.2: Adaptive masking:

AMSTer will combine several masks (that can be provided with different resolutions and footprints) and use them at different stages in different ways: some pixels may be defined as always masked (e.g. over water bodies), other can be considered as masked during the unwrapping, unless their coherence remains above a given threshold, and pixels that can be masked e.g. at the detrending step when there are located in a deforming area.

3. CONCLUSIONS

AMSTer is a versatile and complete tool for SAR/InSAR mass processing and time series production. It is freely available on GitHub at:

https://github.com/AMSTerUsers/AMSTer_Distribution.

AMSTer remains under constant development. Feedback, suggestions and comments are welcome.

Index Terms— SAR, InSAR, MSBAS, 3D Time Series

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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MASS LOSSES OF THE POLAR ICE SHEETS, ANTARCTICA AND GREENLAND. NEW CONSTRAINTS FROM STEREOSCOPIC IMAGERY AND LASER ALTIMETRY.

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ABSTRACT

Along with glaciers, polar ice sheets are a strong contributor to sea level rise and their losses are accelerating. Since 2012, intercomparison exercises have combined estimates of ice sheet mass change from various methods [1]. Their work relies on gravity data from the GRACE and GRACE-FO missions, altimetry (radar or laser) missions, or velocity maps from radar interferometry and image correlation. However, the consensus displayed in these inter-comparisons hides sometimes strong divergences between these different methods because each one presents drawbacks. In particular, the altimetry method, whether based on radar or laser measurements, has a resolution of, at most, one kilometer. This resolution, although perfectly suited in the central and flat areas of the polar ice sheets, does not allow to solve the complexity of the elevation changes of the coastal glaciers, especially along the sloping coasts of the Antarctic Peninsula and Greenland. Yet, it is at their margins that ice sheets respond dynamically to rising atmospheric and oceanic temperatures. The objective of the study is to build high resolution estimates of ice sheet elevation changes.

It exploits an archive of stereo pairs acquired by the SPOT5-HRS sensor mostly during the International Polar Year (IPY, 2007-2009)[2] to build a topography of the polar ice sheet periphery. A vertical correction of each digital terrain model (DEMs) is performed using the elevation measurements, partly simultaneous, of the ICESat laser altimeter (2003-2008). This IPY topography will then be used as a reference to estimate more than 15 years of volume changes of the ice sheet periphery by comparison with measurements from recent missions, in particular ICESat-2 and REMA (Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica) /ArcticDEM [3].

Initially, the Antarctic Peninsula is an ideal site to validate the methodology and then apply it to estimate 15 years of evolution. This is precisely one of the regions where recent estimates of mass loss diverge the most and where glacier dynamics are complex [4]. In a second step, the methodology will be deployed at all ice sheet margins. Total volume changes will be obtained by combining our new estimates for the coastal regions with estimates purely based on laser altimetry for the central parts of the ice caps. This revised estimate will contribute to resolve some discrepancies in ice sheet mass balance estimates and will reveal, at a high resolution, the spatial pattern of changes. It will help to better partition the drivers of the mass loss at the ice sheet peripheries between atmospheric and oceanic forcings.

1. GENERATION AND PRE-PROCESSING OF DIGITAL ELEVATION MODELS ON THE ANTARCTIC PENINSULA

Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) were produced using the software Ames Stereo Pipeline at a resolution of 20 x 20 m. A coregistration of each DEM was then performed using the TanDEM-X Copernicus 30 DEM as a reference. As very scarce ice-free terrain is available in Antarctica, no glacier mask was applied during the coregistration. DEMs were then filtered to remove artifacts and outliers caused by clouds and saturation. Same-day overlapping DEMs were grouped to form larger segments that can be vertically adjusted to synchronous ICESat data (2006-2008). The closest ICESat campaign in time to the DEM acquisition is selected and a minimum of 20 crossing points is required to perform the adjustment. An example of the vertical adjustment of a HRS DEM is shown in Figure 1.

**DEM 2006-12-02 Vertical shift with ICESat-1: summary
dx=0m, dy=0m, dz=1.71m (3266 points)**

Figure 1. Vertical adjustment of a HRS DEM acquired on 2006-12-02 with ICESat data from the 3G campaign (2006-10-25 to 2006-11-27)

2. COMPARISON TO RECENT DATA: REMA AND ICESAT-2 ON THE ANTARCTIC PENINSULA

After the pre-processing, the HRS DEM were compared to recent data. For each HRS DEM, intersecting stripes from the Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica acquired ± 1 month around the HRS DEM acquisition day were selected in 2021, 2022 and 2023. All REMA stripes were coregistered on the same reference DEM as the HRS DEMs (TanDEM-X Copernicus 30) and vertically adjusted on synchronous ICESat-2 data (± 20 days). Elevation difference maps (dh maps) were then computed and aggregated on common periods of time. The dh maps were eventually converted into rate of elevation change per year (m/y). The synchronous ICESat-2 data is used to compute an elevation difference point cloud. This dataset allows eventually a validation of the difference elevation values obtained with the REMA and HRS DEMs.

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FICTITIOUS DOMAINS TO RESOLVE TRACTION CHANGES ON MAGMA INTRUSIONS AND FAULTS IN A 3D HETEROGENEOUS CRUST

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ABSTRACT

We present a new method to invert variable traction changes acting fractures from InSAR ground displacements. Fractures can be either faults or magma intrusions, embedded in a 3D heterogeneous crust with prominent topographies. The method is based on a fictitious domain approach inspired by extended finite element method developed for cracks that do not follow volume meshes. The cost function involves the misfit between the solution of the physical problem and the observed data together with regularization terms. An algorithm is presented which relies on the forward and the adjoint problem. Synthetic tests, relying on the determination of the regularization parameters by L-curves, show that an initial solution is reliably determined. The method is then reformulated to be applied to InSAR data, which represent a challenge as field conditions lead to missing data, displacements are noisy and they are projected in one or several Earth-Satellite directions, leading to an incomplete knowledge of the displacement field. Synthetic tests demonstrate the efficiency and robustness of the method for one to four Line-of-Sight observations, with missing data and variable noise.

Figure 1. Synthetic test performed to validate the inversion method

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Index Terms— InSAR, GNSS, Finite Element Method, Optimal Control, Inversion.

NEAR REAL-TIME MAGMA PROPAGATION FORECASTING WITH A PARTICLE FILTER

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I. ABSTRACT

In this article, we propose a data assimilation strategy in order to forecast in near-real time hazards related to magma propagation. This strategy is based on a particle filter and a physical 2D model of magma propagation. The whole processing chain has been tested using synthetic simulations. Results obtained confirm the high potential of the particle filter for volcanic hazards forecasting.

II. INTRODUCTION

In a perspective of volcanic hazard assessment, it is fundamental to be able to determine as early as possible whether, where and when the magma that has started to propagate from the storage zone will reach the surface. The propagation phase is generally rapid, lasting from a few hours to a few days, but it induces seismicity and deformation signals recorded by continuous sensors and InSAR data. Furthermore, dynamic numerical models can be used to calculate the trajectory and the velocity of magma propagation as a function of the physical properties of the magma and the crust, and the initial conditions (local stress field and magma reservoir location).

Data assimilation is a set of methods that combines a dynamic model with current and past observations based on error statistics and predicts the future state of the observed system. This technique therefore appears to be an appropriate tool for addressing the need to predict the position and timing of a volcanic eruption based on available models and observations. Among the state-of-the-art data assimilation methods, the particle filter (or Sequential Monte Carlo method) is particularly noteworthy for its ability to handle nonlinear models and non-Gaussian error statistics.

Data assimilation with the particle filter proceeds in two major steps. Firstly, the forecast step gives a representation of the probability density of the dynamic model by a discrete set of model states. Secondly, by relying on the Baye's theorem, the analysis step includes the observations to give us the posterior probability density by a resampled set of model states.

In this paper, we propose for the first time to use particle filter for tracking magma propagation.

III. MAGMA ASCENT MODELING

To model the magma propagation, we consider in two dimensions, the case of magma propagating beneath a caldera in an extensional stress field.

The model includes 7 inputs parameters (called state vector of the model) : the initial position of the magma at depth, its viscosity and driving pressure, the volume of magma injected, the crustal rigidity and the local stress field characterized by the balance between tectonic extension and caldera unloading. All these parameters allow us to calculate the stress ([2]Jaeger, 1969, [5]Watanabee, 2002) and magma buoyancy which direct the global trajectory of the magma.

Fig. 1. Simulation of magma propagation beneath a caldera. Colors represent the amplitude of the principal stress, black arrows represent the direction of the principal stress which initially directs the trajectory (then the trajectory is affected by magma buoyancy). The positions of the magma at different time are represented in blue, yellow, green and red.

By running the dynamical model, at a given time, the position of the magma can be calculated (Fig. 1). The Okada model ([4]Okada, 1985) is then used to compute the surface displacements induced by this magma propagation. For this, the coordinates of the center of the dyke, the dip, the length and the opening are necessary.

IV. DATA ASSIMILATION WITH THE PARTICLE FILTER

Our objective is to determine when and where the magma will reach the surface. The method is based on the Monte-Carlo principle. By considering initially a

large number of random state vectors which produce different trajectories, we generate the particles to represent the probability density function of the model state. The optimal number corresponds to the minimum necessary to sufficiently represent the model parameters space. With data assimilation, only trajectories consistent with the observations are retained.

At the forecast step, the dynamical model is performed for a large number of state vectors which produce trajectories and theoretical surface displacements. Then, during the analysis step, particles are resampled according to observations. In a first time, likelihood is calculated by comparing the theoretical displacements to the observed displacement. Then, particles with the higher likelihood are retained, the others are replaced. In our study, we test two methods of resampling : the Metropolis-Hastings method ([1]Hastings, 1970) and the Stochastic Universal Sampling method ([3]Kitagawa, 1996). The whole processing chain is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Steps of an assimilation cycle

Initially, we consider 100-500 particles and 44 assimilation cycles. The model integration step is 60 seconds. From the initial condition, the particle propagate freely during 3600 seconds, the assimilation is performed every 600 seconds.

V. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

We first validate our assimilation strategy with synthetic data. Fig. 3 shows histograms of predictions of magma arrival location and arrival time at different moments of the simulation. The resampling algorithm of Metropolis-Hastings is used. Red lines represent the true location and arrival time. Initially, random draws give us inaccurate possibilities of arrivals. Then, by performing several assimilation cycles, arrival location and time become more precise. At the final assimilation cycle, histograms of predictions converge to the truth.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we proposed a data assimilation strategy based on a particle filter for magma propagation forecast. Results show the interest of data assimilation in a context of real-time management of volcanic hazards.

Fig. 3. Predictions of the arrival location and the arrival time of magma over time.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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NEW ANALYSIS OF INSAR AND SEISMOLOGY FOR KINEMATIC RECONSTRUCTION OF THE 1995 OFFSHORE AIGION M6.2 EARTHQUAKE (GREECE)

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ABSTRACT

During the transition from early to mature rifting different fault geometries and kinematics may form. In particular it is debated whether low angle normal faulting occurs during early rifting. It is therefore crucial to constrain how faults slip during earthquakes by thoroughly exploring the variability of the fault models derived from geophysical observations.

Greece and the gulf are the European regions with the most seismicity. The western part is confirmed to be the most active (Kaviris, et al. 2021) notably with the occurrence of all the latest $M > 5.5$, including the Aigion earthquake which was the largest since the February 1981 East crisis (M_s 6.6 February 24th; M_s 6.3 February 25th; and M_s 6.4 March 4th; Abercrombie, et al. 1995).

The Gulf of Corinth rift dated around 5 Ma (Beckers, et al. 2015; Bell, et al. 2018) and 100-130 km long in an East-West direction for 3-30 km wide (Koukouvelas, et al. 1996; Bell, et al. 2018) is in the western part of the Aegean region. The region's extension is driven by the back-arc extension of the Hellenic arc on the south that subducts below the Nubian plate and the rotation toward the west of the Anatolian plate pushed by the Arabian plate on the east (Tayzman, et al. 2007).

Here we study the M_w 6.2 Aigion earthquake that occurred in the Gulf of Corinth on June 15, 1995, using InSAR and seismic waveforms. The Gulf of Corinth is a continental rift in its early stages, currently extending at a rate of 10-15 mm/yr (Bell et al., 2008) in the N-S direction and characterized by normal faults defining a graben. The Gulf of Corinth can generate major destructive earthquakes, such as the magnitude 6.7 in 1981, and is heavily populated.

Therefore, it is key to understand the mechanisms of faulting in the Gulf of Corinth rift. The 1995 Aigion seismic sequence included a M_w 6.2 earthquake and an aftershock of M_w 5.2. However, the subsurface geometry and position of the fault is highly debated, including whether it dips to the N or S, and the fault dip angle. The majority of the deformation occurred offshore and analysis of the seismicity or geodetic (InSAR and GPS) data alone leads to non-unique fault solutions. On the contrary joint inversion of different types of geophysical data can give more robust fault models. In this work, we jointly invert InSAR and teleseismic data for the fault model of the M_w 6.2 Aigion earthquake. Preliminary results show the possibility of a low-angle normal fault, dipping to the north as a best-fit model. This multidisciplinary methodology could better constrain subsurface definition of faults in the Gulf of Corinth and other regions, both for past and future deformation events.

Figure 1. Ascending interferogram of the M_w 6.2 Aigion earthquake (Greece)

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LOOKING FOR ONLAND SURFACE RUPTURE ON SECONDARY NORMAL FAULTS OF THE 1956 Ms7.8 AMORGOS EARTHQUAKE (GREECE): INSIGHTS FROM HISTORICAL AERIAL IMAGES

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ABSTRACT

On July 9th 1956, a Ms 7.8 tsunamigenic earthquake occurred offshore Amorgos and Santorini islands. The causative fault was recently identified offshore Amorgos [1], and offsets the seafloor by several meters. One secondary structure, branched on the main fault, is cross-cutting the southern coast of Amorgos island [2]. A ~1-m high ribbon is visible at the base of the fault scarp, and has a fresh morphology [3].

Here, we try to estimate if this ribbon has been exhumed by slip during the earthquake of 1956, using historical aerial images. We present these scanned analog images, focused on the secondary fault, acquired before and after the earthquake. Visual inspection reveals several landslides, the fault scarp is also visible before and after the earthquake.

Structure-from-motion methods allowed us to produce DEMs and orthophotographs at a resolution ≤ 1 m, the latter needed to perform pixel-correlation. Pre- and post-earthquake DEMs are compared but are not resolved enough to evaluate if a vertical displacement occurred. Pixel-correlation results are discussed with respect to the resolution of the images and the expected displacement along the fault.

Index Terms — earthquake, Greece, Pléiades, historical images

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Figure 1. (A) Seismo-tectonic setting of the epicentral area of the Amorgos earthquake, 1956. Red lines indicate major faults. The different epicenters proposed in the literature of the 1956 earthquake are represented by red stars (summarized in Brustle et al., 2014). A focal mechanism according to Okal et al., (2009) is represented. The black arrows show relative velocities of ~ 4 mm/yr with respect to stable Naxos island (upper left-hand corner) inferred from GPS measurements (Briole et al., 2021). Red box corresponds to the location of the Chozoviotissa fault (figure 1B, 1C). The inset shows the location of the study area in the Cyclades, Greece. (B) and (C) are orthorectified aerial images from 1945 and 1960 respectively. The red lines represent the Chozoviotissa fault trace on Amorgos island (see Fig.1A for location). The white triangles point to the various surface processes activated between the 1945 and the 1960 aerial images.

AN IMPROVED PROCESSING OF ASTER ELEVATION TIME SERIES IN HIGH MOUNTAIN ASIA TO STUDY GLACIER SURGE DYNAMICS, AND TEST APPLICATION TO LARGE LANDSLIDES.

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ABSTRACT

Some glaciers display flow instabilities, among which surge events particularly stand out. Surges are quasi-periodic flow perturbations with an abnormally fast flow over a few months to years. It can result in surface elevation changes of more than 100 m in a few months.

The estimation of the mass transfer and the flow variation can be inferred from the glacier surface elevation and velocities. It is critical data to better understand the dynamics of a surge. While satellite-based DEMs provide useful information for studying surges, their use in previous studies was generally limited to a few DEM differences extending over periods of several years, prone to data gaps and irregular temporal coverage. To date, very few studies have leveraged the full time series of elevation data available since ~2000 which could help quantify the variations of mass transfer during the very short surge phases.

Here, we exploited the high temporal and spatial coverage of the ASTER optical satellite sensor to compute a dense time series of elevation suited for the study of surges. We used the DEM dataset produced by Hugonnet et al. (2021). Our case study area is the Karakoram range, in High Mountain Asia, where is one of the biggest clusters of surge-type glaciers. Some large landslides are also visible on our dataset, as Karakoram is a very active region for georisks. The elevation changes for such events can be up to several tens of meters, about the same order of magnitude as many surge events (Tsutsui et al., 2007). Our dataset then could be used to detect such large landslides with the ability to estimate the few months or the year in which the landslide took place.

1. TIME SERIES PROCESSING

We used non-filtered ASTER digital elevation models (DEMs) of 100 m resolution from Hugonnet et al. (2021). The time series range from about 2001 to 2019, with a median of 56 observations per on-glacier pixel over the whole period. We developed a specific method for filtering the elevation time series that preserves surge signals, as opposed to the original method that tends to reject this behaviour as outliers. A LOWESS method – locally weighted polynomial regression (Derkacheva et al., 2020; Cleveland, 1979) is at the core of this workflow. We iteratively filtered out observations out of a derivative-dependent threshold. Then, we predicted the elevation over a regular temporal and spatial grid from filtered data, with the B-spline method ALPS-REML (Shekhar et al., 2021).

2. PERFORMANCE AND ANALYSIS OF CASE STUDIES

We will finally present the results of this method applied to more than 1000 DEMs covering the Karakoram region to derive elevation time series at 100 m spatial resolution. The filter and the prediction performances will be discussed through specific examples. We compared the ability to preserve the surge signal with the original workflow of Hugonnet et al. (2021). The limits of the workflow are met on specific events and locations. We compared the output with those of other studies, in terms of surge onset and end dates, location or volume transported. We will finally look at a few large landslide events in the Karakoram.

Index Terms— Digital Elevation Model (DEM), time series, glacier, ASTER

Figure 1. Map of predicted elevation changes over two years, with two elevation time series at specific locations. The two glaciers with the most extreme changes are in surge phase, with the Hispar Glacier (bottom left) and Braldu Glacier (bottom right). The red areas show glacier thinning, and blue areas show glacier thickening. The time series illustrates the reservoir area of the surge (left time series, thinning) and the reception area of the surge (thickening, receiving the transported mass).

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DYNAMICS OF SMALL SURGING GLACIERS IN THE QILIAN MOUNTAINS: PATTERNS AND MECHANISMS REVEALED BY LONG-TERM DENSE TIME-SERIES OBSERVATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Glacier surge, an exceptional rapid mass redistribution process of glaciers, is one of the least understood dynamic processes in cryosphere. The Qilian Mountains in the High Mountain Asia host a specific center of surging glaciers, yet they remain underexplored. Spatiotemporal changes in elevation and flow velocity are crucial for assessing surge dynamics. However, existing methods are inadequate in accurately capturing abrupt surging changes and lack temporal details, especially for small surging glaciers due to noisy observations. In this study, we investigated the long-term kinematic changes of surging glaciers in Qilian Mountains, which are typically small valley glaciers with dynamics remain poorly understood. Utilizing continuous ASTER and Landsat imagery, we employed two newly developed methods specifically designed for surging glaciers to derive long-term monthly flow velocity and elevation time series. Our methods successfully captured significant variations in several surging glaciers over the past few decades, with notable detail and accuracy (Figure 1).

The results indicate a strong interaction between the patterns of elevation change and flow speed. Combined with evidence from other satellite imagery, we found that two glaciers experienced slow and gradual surges lasting over 10 years. The Gangnalou Glacier has been accelerating and slowly transporting mass downward in recent years, indicating a possible initiation of another surge. The most distinctive surging glacier experienced a significant surge from 2002 to 2005 and has since transitioned to a build-up phase. Considering the prolonged duration of surges, we conclude that glacier surges in this region are primarily thermal-controlled. However, we observed a two-stage initiation of the main surging glacier, which may suggest a potential impact from saturated soft sediment failure. This research demonstrates the potential of advanced time-series methods for capturing the surging behavior of small mountain glaciers and provides insights to enhance the understanding of surging dynamics in this region.

Figure 1. Derived monthly Elevation change (a) and Flow velocity (b) time series along the centerline of selected surging glacier

CONTINUOUS MONITORING OF SLOW SLIP IN CASCADIA THROUGH DEEP-LEARNING-BASED DENOISING OF GNSS DATA

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ABSTRACT

Slow slip has revolutionized our understanding of relative plate motions, shedding light on more complex processes of stress release in tectonic areas worldwide. Geodetic measurements have provided evidence for ubiquitous aseismic slip, suggesting that slow slip plays a crucial role in the seismic cycle [1]. Thus, detecting and characterizing the tiniest slow slip occurrences is key to fully imaging the slip spectrum. However, detecting slow slip in geodetic data is still challenging, since identifying small-amplitude signals is still hindered by an intrinsic detection threshold associated with the signal-to-noise ratio. Hence, denoising geodetic data is essential, yet often challenging, because the observations may comprise noise from different sources, including environmental signals and instrumental artifacts, which can be spatially and temporally correlated, thus hard to disentangle.

The first part of this study addresses the denoising of multivariate time series acquired by irregularly distributed networks of sensors. Specifically, our method deals with the denoising of geodetic position time series, which monitor the ground displacement worldwide with centimeter-to-millimeter precision, particularly GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) position time series. Albeit designed for this specific task, the developed framework is general enough to be applied to any time series denoising problem with multiple measurement sites (array of sensors) and multiple non-independent components or channels (multivariate), *e.g.*, GNSS data, seismic data, gravimeters, tiltmeters, strainmeters. Here, we design SSEdenoiser [2], a multi-station spatiotemporal graph-based attentive denoiser that learns latent characteristics of GNSS noise to reveal slow-slip-related displacement with sub-millimeter precision. It is based on the key combination of graph recurrent networks

and spatiotemporal Transformers. The proposed method is applied to the Cascadia subduction zone, where slow slip occurs along with bursts of tectonic tremors, a seismic rumbling identified from independent seismic recordings. The extracted events match the spatiotemporal evolution of tremors. This good space-time correlation of the denoised GNSS signals with the tremors validates the proposed denoising procedure.

The second part of the study leverages the denoised denoising approach presented in the first part [2] to extract daily slow-slip-driven displacement rates at 200 continuous GNSS stations in the Cascadia subduction zone. We then apply an inversion scheme to retrieve the slip history at depth, implemented as a static inversion for each epoch [3-5]. Inverting denoised displacements is advantageous since no temporal smoothing needs to be applied, thus accessing the space-time slip history with daily precision.

Thanks to our multidisciplinary approach, we access the Cascadia's continuous chatter with unprecedented temporal detail. This allows us to reconstruct the spectral properties of the 15-year-long moment rate function with augmented resolution, especially at low frequency. Compared to a compilation of single slow slip events, we provide observations to previous theoretical results [7] and new constraints on the self-similar behaviour of slow slip. Our analysis also sheds new light on the slow slip source time function, suggestive of temporal asymmetry: slip starts with accelerated moment release, followed by a longer relaxation time. Finally, we revisit slow earthquake scaling laws, providing observations to illustrate the detection bias from Ide & Beroza (2023) [7]. We demonstrate that slow slip event scaling laws are generally influenced by the signal-to-noise (SNR) threshold in GNSS data and are thus affected by a sampling bias.

Figure 1. Denoised GNSS displacement rates (E-W component) as a function of time. The displacement rate computed from the output of SSEdenoiser is shown for each GNSS station, sorted as a function of the latitude. Tremor epicenters are also shown as black points (we use the catalogue from Ide, (2012) [8] until August 5, 2009, and the tremor catalogue from the Pacific Northwest Seismic Network (PNSN) in the following period [9]). Denoised displacements are very well correlated with tremors in space and time, providing independent validation of the results.

Index Terms— time series analysis, denoising, deep learning, graph neural networks, multi-station, spatiotemporal, geospatial data, GNSS, slow slip events, geodesy, seismology

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CARTOGRAPHIE ET CINEMATIQUES DES DEFORMATIONS DE PENTES PAR INSAR ET IMAGERIE OPTIQUE, MUSTANG SUPERIEUR, NEPAL

MAPPING AND KINEMATICS OF SLOPE DEFORMATION USING INSAR AND DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION, UPPER MUSTANG, NEPAL

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ABSTRACT

The Upper Mustang region of Nepal has numerous large deep seated gravitational slope deformations associated with Tethyan shale bedrock and potentially influenced by permafrost. These have been long recognized, but never studied systematically, and their activity has never been quantified. While the area is sparsely populated, several villages are impacted by the landslides, including the important Hindu pilgrimage site of Muktinath, where deformation is damaging roads and buildings, including key portions of the temple complex. The high elevations of the slope failures, at 3500-4500 m asl, suggest that permafrost may play a role, but the state of permafrost in the region has been very little studied. This project will aim to improve our understanding of the mechanics of slowmoving landslides in shale bedrock, determine the rates and patterns of slope deformation in the Upper Mustang region, and evaluate potential spatial and temporal controls on deformation, including possible spatial (aspect, elevation), climatic (permafrost, snow melt, precipitation) or anthropogenic(irrigation) drivers, and place the slope failures within the longer-term context of landscape evolution, erosion, and carbon export in upper Mustang.

The first step will be a regional remote sensing-based investigation, using InSAR and Digital Image Correlation to evaluate deformation rates across the region, identify the slope failures and determine their degree of activity. We will then select a subset of slopes for which to measure time series of deformation using InSAR and/or optical imagery as needed, and evaluate temporal controls in detail.

Example of one of the slope deformations. Mean velocity is estimated from correlation of Sentinel-2 images from 2018, 2020, 2021, and 2024, using the GDM-OPT-SLIDE webservice developed and performed byForM@Ter, Solid Earth component of the Data Terra Research Infrastructure.

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NEW IMAGE CORRELATION WEB SERVICES IN THE FORMATERRE GDM PORTFOLIO

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ABSTRACT

Measuring terrain deformation is relevant for many applications in Earth Sciences (i.e. active faults, volcanoes, landslides or glaciers understanding). Nowadays, radar interferometry has proven its capacities to monitor a variety of slow-moving phenomena from local to continental scale with the European Ground Motion Service, [1]). However, the technique remains limited when the ground moves at faster rates. In these cases, offset tracking techniques are more suitable to monitor the ground deformation. FormaTerre, the French thematic hub of services in solid Earth, part of the Data-Terra Research Infrastructure, offers to the scientific community services for both techniques: the Ground Deformation Monitoring (GDM) services (Figure 1).

The GDM-OPT services were developed to offer a complete processing chain for performing multi-temporal offset tracking [2,3]. Three services were specifically designed for three main applications: 1) GDM-OPT-ETQ for measuring co-seismic deformation, 2) GDM-OPT-Slide for measuring landslides motion and 3) GDM-OPT-ICE for monitoring glacier surface velocity. Two new services are now completing the initial set of services: GDM-OPT-Survey for near-real time and systematic monitoring of specific areas in routine mode and GDM-SAR-cor, an on-demand offset tracking service for multi-temporal SAR images.

We present the development and the workflows developed for these two new services. Then, we present ground deformation field and time series obtained at two landslides: the Vitor Valley (Peru) and the Portuguese Bend landslide (USA) showing the new capabilities of the FormaTerre GDM offset tracking services.

1. GDM-OPT-SURVEY: NEAR REAL TIME AND SYSTEMATIC OF RAPID GROUND MOTION

With now eight years of operation, the Sentinel-2 satellites provide a global coverage of the Earth every 5 days at 10 meter resolution. This offers a great potential for systematic and near-real time monitoring and for designing early warning systems [4]. The GDM-OPT-Survey service has been designed for this purpose: processing automatically every new cloud-free Sentinel-2 acquisition over a designated area of interest in order to compute up-to-date time series of terrain motion. To achieve this goal, the GDM-OPT original workflow has been adapted in order to 1) detect the cloud coverage over the Area Of Interest (AOI) to include or reject the image in the processing, 2) automatically detect the tiles and orbits covering the AOI in order to compute all image pairs per tile and per orbit, 3) merge the images per orbit in order to provide a maximum coverage of the AOI and 4) invert the displacement time series for the archive and every new cloud-free Sentinel-2 acquisition. The service works with the MicMac photogrammetric library [5] and the time series inversion is performed with the TIO algorithm [6].

2. GDM-SAR-COR : RADAR OFFSET TRACKING WITH SENTINEL-1 IMAGES

Sentinel-1 offers nowadays ten years of archive with global coverage every 12 days (6 days between 2016 and 2021) at 5 m x 20 m spatial resolution. Radar images are less sensitive to clouds and atmospheric conditions in comparison to optical sensors. Consequently, the Sentinel-1 archive presents a significant interest to monitor fast motion with offset-tracking techniques. Moreover, if both a signal can be

Figure 1: Brief description of GDM services for image correlation.

measured in both ascending and descending direction, radar offset tracking provides the 3D vector of the deformation. Therefore, the GDM-SAR-cor service is designed to compute deformation time series from radar offset tracking. The workflow follows the main processing steps of the GDM-OPT services with an additional pre-processing of the Level-1 SLC images using the AMSTer mass processing chain [7, 8]. The correlation is performed with the MicMac photogrammetric library [5], with parameters adapted to SAR images. Finally, the displacement time series can be inverted with the MSBAS algorithm [9] and with TIO [6]. The current version of the service ingests Sentinel-1 images and can process images from the same orbit.

The performances of the two new services are tested on two landslides located on the Vitor Valley (Peru) and in California (USA). The results show a good agreement between all tested sensors (Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2) and the capabilities of these services to provide valuable information for disaster response.

The two services are implemented, operated and maintained on the EOSt/A2S High Performance Computing facility of University of Strasbourg, and accessible through the FormaTerre web portal. The services will be in evaluation mode for a serie of targeted users for a period of 6 months, and will then be released to the science community.

Index Terms— Image Correlation, offset tracking, Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2.

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calculations are performed on the EOSt/A2S High Performance Computing facility of University of Strasbourg

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POTENTIAL OF DEEP LEARNING FOR VOLCANIC SOURCE INVERSION

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I. INTRODUCTION

Neural networks provide new solutions to inverse problems in geophysics where we find a set of model parameters that best fit the observations. For example, in (1), authors used a ResNet model to estimate glacier thickness from glacier surface velocity measurements and a digital elevation model. Promising results confirmed the interest of deep learning methods. Compared to physics based traditional methods, neural networks have the capability of dealing with data complexity, nonlinearities and hidden regularities in the data. Moreover, they are free of prior knowledge and able to use generic models to be adapted to specific problems through automatic learning against training data.

In volcanology, surface displacement fields are often used to explore the subsurface feature beneath a volcano by means of inversion. State-of-the-art bayesian inversion, e.g. Markov Chain Monte Carlo, is often very computationally expensive (2). Therefore, in this paper we try to highlight the potentiality of deep learning methods in solving specific inverse problems in volcanology.

II. METHODOLOGY

We rely on the Mogi model (3). In this model, the surface deformation is directly driven by a (rapid) change in the volume of a spherical magma chamber at a given depth (equations below).

$$u_r = \frac{r\Delta V}{(r^2 + d^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \frac{1 - \nu}{\pi} \quad (1)$$

$$u_z = \frac{d\Delta V}{(r^2 + d^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \frac{1 - \nu}{\pi} \quad (2)$$

u_r denotes the radial displacement with respect to the magma chamber center, u_z denotes the vertical displacement. r represents the distance from the magma chamber center and d represents the depth of the magma chamber. ΔV is the volume change. ν is the Poisson coefficient. π is the ratio of a circle's circumference to its diameter.

200 000 interferograms are simulated by varying Mogi model parameters (d , ΔV) and data acquisition geometry

parameters (incidence angle θ). Moreover, simulations of spatially correlated noise (random over time) are performed to generate error-prone synthetic data. The whole dataset is divided into training, validation and testing datasets in an automatic way. In the following, the main objective is to estimate (d , ΔV) from simulated interferograms using a deep learning model.

The chosen ResNet model (4) builds upon four residual blocks and contains only 26, 864 parameters. It uses a fixed-size, single-channel input image representing an interferogram. Then the model splits into two prediction heads, one for depth (d) estimation and the other for volume change (ΔV) estimation.

Besides the baseline experiment where we vary only d and ΔV , several complementary experiments are also conducted to investigate the impact of data distribution, incidence angle, position of the Mogi source center and noise. The summary of experiments is given in Table I. For each experiment, 100 model and data sampling initialisation seeds are randomly generated to investigate the sensitivity of the model to initial conditions.

TABLE I. Experiments summary. *logn* denotes log-normal distribution and *unif* denotes uniform distribution.

Designation	Varying parameters	Noise
Baseline	d (logn.), ΔV (logn.)	No
Uniform	d (unif.), ΔV (unif.)	No
Position	d (logn.), ΔV (logn.), (x, y)	No
Incidence	d (logn.), ΔV (logn.), θ	No
Position + Incidence	d (logn.), ΔV (logn.), $(x, y), \theta$	No
Noise	d (logn.), ΔV (logn.)	Yes

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The estimated volume change and depth in different experiments are shown in Fig. 1. In the baseline experiment, the deep learning model found the linear relationship between the surface displacement and the volume change, but the volume change values are underestimated. For the depth, the underestimation problem is also observed for smaller and larger values. The impact of data distribution is significant. In case of uniform distribution, many experiments fail and give smaller values. Varying incidence angles does not change the results.

Fig. 1. True value versus predicted value for A) ΔV and B) d . The red line indicates where both values match perfectly. Blue envelopes ranging from unsaturated to saturated colors indicate distributions of the 100 models seeds (1th to 99th quantile, 5th to 95th, 10th to 90th and 25th to 75th respectively). The solid line in blue indicates the median value.

Changing the volcanic source center does not impact the median value, but increases the dispersion. Adding noise of fixed magnitude in the simulated displacement does not improve the underestimation problem.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a proof-of-concept study is conducted to explore the potential deployment of deep learning model to solve a volcanic source inversion problem. The first results obtained confirm the interest of using deep learning models for physical problems. Further efforts are necessary to improve the estimation accuracy.

V. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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CHANGE DETECTION WITH INSAR COHERENCE TO IDENTIFY RAPID LANDSLIDE MOVEMENTS IN TIME AND SPACE

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ABSTRACT

In mountainous areas, landslides are a major source of erosion and represent a significant risk to people and infrastructure. Detection of landslide movements from space plays a vital role in monitoring, early warning and furthering our understanding of these processes. However, for any landslide, the feasibility of observing its movements from space, and what technique is most suitable for this depends on its displacement rate, orientation, landcover and the prevalence of cloud cover in the region. Here we explore the potential of using InSAR coherence to detect fast movements and their precursors in complex large rockslide areas.

1. LANDSLIDE MONITORING FROM SPACE

Slow-moving landslides can be monitored using InSAR techniques such as persistent scatterer interferometry, but faster movements are not well captured by these techniques as the signal becomes aliased or decorrelated. These techniques are also dependent on the direction in which the landslide is moving, and whether or not it is covered by forest, which can also decorrelate the signal.

Faster movements can be detected using optical image correlation techniques, but cloud cover often obscures such images, limiting the temporal resolution of these techniques. This is particularly a problem for rainfall-driven landslide movements, since long periods of rainfall are generally accompanied by heavy cloud.

Change detection with InSAR coherence may present a solution to this problem, since coherence is both sensitive to rapid changes at the Earth's surface and, since it is derived from SAR, can be applied in cloudy weather conditions. In general, coherence is expected to be low for areas undergoing rapid change within the time window of the interferogram. Thus, while we cannot detect displacement rates using this technique, we can identify areas which have undergone rapid failure. Coherence-based methods have been developed to detect rapid, shallow landslides in the aftermath of an earthquake^[1] and tested at large spatial scales^[2]. Another

potential use for coherence methods would be to detect periods of activity for landslides of known locations. It has been shown that in some cases, precursory movements prior to catastrophic failures resulted in detectable coherence loss^[3]. Multi-stage failure during an earthquake sequence has also been detected using coherence^[4]. If coherence methods could be used to define active and inactive (or slow) periods for landslides moving too fast for traditional InSAR, this could be a useful risk management tool.

However, while it has been demonstrated that coherence is able to detect rapid landslides movements in space and time for some landslides, there is a need to better constrain what processes can and cannot be captured using InSAR coherence techniques. Here, we address this by studying how coherence varies in space and time for a well-monitored rockslide in the Italian Alps.

2. CASE STUDY: THE RUINON ROCKSLIDE

The Ruinon rockslide (Figure 1i) lies within a larger deep-seated gravitational deformation (DSGD) in the Italian Alps^[5]. Over the last 15 years, the rockslide has been monitored using a ground-based InSAR (GBInSAR) system, so that its activity is well-constrained during this time. This makes it an excellent test case for establishing what can and cannot be detected using coherence. During this time, the rockslide has undergone various stages of reactivation, particularly in 2019, when some parts of the rockslide experienced displacements of over 100 m, a 10-fold increase compared to other years^[5,6]. Figure 1ii shows the coherence of a 12-day interferogram during this active period, with the coherence loss clearly visible within the rockslide compared to the surrounding forest. As well as varying in time, the movement of the rockslide is spatially heterogeneous, with the upper part often moving more slowly than the lower part. We directly compare these GBInSAR measurements to Sentinel-1 coherence for 6-, 12-, 18 and 24-day interferograms in order to identify patterns in how this varies in space and time.

Figure 1. (i) High resolution optical image of the Ruinon Rockslide acquired in 2019 (ii) Coherence map for an interferogram formed from Sentinel-1 images acquired on the 24th of May and 5th of June 2019. GBInSAR measures displacements of 47, 15, 48 and 23 mm towards the sensor during this period at points A, B, C and D (panel i) respectively

3. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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RECENT SATELLITE-BASED RADAR AND OPTICAL MONITORING OF THE ACTIVITY SLOW-MOVING LANDSLIDES IN NEPAL DURING MONSOON

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ABSTRACT

The steep slopes of the Himalayas are highly susceptible to landslides, primarily triggered by earthquakes and monsoon intense precipitations. Along the Himalayan southern slopes, a specific landslide type involves old slided hillslope. These slopes are characterized by intense internal fracturing and are prone to rapid retrogressive erosion through deep gullies incision, eventually leading to catastrophic collapse of secondary landslides. Anticipating such events requires understanding if subsiding slices at the edge of the deeply incised talweg exhibit signs of acceleration preceding their rapid collapse and establishing a potential relationship between triggering factors (such as rain) and displacement amplitude.

While optical images are commonly used for rapid landslides (with displacements superior to 20 cm/yr), their effectiveness is hindered by cloud cover during the monsoon period, limiting sampling frequency and impeding the identification of transient deformation signals.

In this study, we integrate satellite-based optical and radar remote sensing data with high spatial and temporal resolution to characterize the dynamics of three slow-moving landslides located in the Marsyandi and Khudi valleys in Nepal, and to understand how they respond to monsoon rainfall forcing. The three areas show actively eroding gullies, which are entrenched into 1 to 2 km long slided hillslopes and which are overlain by 0.1 to 0.2 km² wide mobile panels associated to secondary slides within the fractured slided mass.

High-resolution Pléiades DSM are derived to track vertical variations on the landslide and precisely co-register high-resolution SAR images. We develop an open-source pixel-tracking processing chain based on the AMES Stereo Pipeline

(ASP) [1] for pixel tracking, and the AMSter Toolbox [2] for SAR processing. A comparison of pixel-tracking algorithms reveals that the More Global Matching (MGM) [3], which uses small correlation kernels is better suited for detecting small-scale movements compared to traditional block matching algorithms.

The processing chain is applied to a data set comprising spotlight PAZ and TerraSAR-X radar images (1m spatial resolution), as well as high-resolution Pléiades (1m amplitude optical images).

Multi-temporal SAR and Pléiades pixel-tracking displacement time series are then projected and combined in the line of steepest slope to derive average velocities in four identified periods. By incorporating a term proportional to the geometrical baseline in the decomposition, we correct radiometric variations linked to the geometry of the SAR sensors.

The high-temporal resolution displacements derived from SAR amplitude images display coherent cumulative displacement of the mobile panels of several meters (up to 15 m) during the 2022 and 2023 monsoons. They also reveal a non-linear response to the monsoon, which differs between the three sites. The SAR ground displacements time series in the Khudi valley are characterized by an apparent continuous evolution during the monsoon. In contrast, in the Marsyandi valley in 2022, the major displacement phase occurs at the very end of the monsoon after a 3-day episode of heavy rainfall (Figure 1). During both monsoons, the displacements begin at the base of the panels close to the central gullies and are followed later by large displacements in the mid and upper parts of the panels. These observations suggest a triggering role of the incision of the central gully in destabilizing the overlying panels and in driving retrogressive erosion within the slided hillslope [4].

Figure 1. Top-left : SAR amplitude pixel tracking cumulative time series in slant range and azimuth for three selected pixels on the Mathilo landslide using PAZ descending track 059. Displacement time series are modeled by linear trends in the four periods A-D. Bottom and right : Maps showing slant range and azimuth velocities for the four periods, superimposed on a panchromatic Pléiades image.

In addition, the combination of DSM comparison and optical pixel-tracking provides a comprehensive view of the 3-dimensional surface displacement fields across the three landslides. This enables the derivation of the failure geometry at depth, offering insights into the underlying mechanisms of these landslides.

Index Terms— SAR, image correlation, time series analysis, Pléiades

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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LANDSLIDE DEFORMATION PATTERN OF THE LA BELOTTE LANDSLIDE FROM SENTINEL-1 INSAR AND IN-SITU GNSS

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ABSTRACT

For several years, the urbanised slope of La Belotte (municipality of Embrun, Hautes-Alpes) is affected by slow sliding deformation causing numerous damage to buildings and infrastructures. Several decrees recognizing the state of natural disaster have been issued since 2018. Since 2021, a multi-organism working group is in charge of supporting the French state and the municipality by providing new knowledge on the landslide mechanism. One key aspect of the analysis is to provide high-resolution and multi-technique information on the surface slope deformation fields. A network of 18 permanent GNSS stations have been installed on site allowing to document the spatial and temporal variability of the displacement rates at an infra centimetric accuracy. The in-situ measurements are completed by an the analysis of a time series of Sentinel-1 imagery using both Persistent Scatterers Interferometry (PSI, using the SNAPPING service developed by [1]) and

Normalized Small Baseline Subset approach (N-SBAS, [2]) using the GDM-SAR-in service (an evolution of the FLATSIM service for on-demand processing, [3]). The very dense network of GNSS stations (taken as reference displacement measurements) at the site allow to discuss the best processing strategies for operational landslide InSAR monitoring. Copernicus Sentinel-1 images covering the period 2021 to 2023 have been processed, using specific strategies (processing of all the image pairs, processing of the image pairs per year, use of only snow-free images, use of several medium to high-resolution topography). The objective of the presentation is to discuss the best processing strategy for each interferometric processing algorithm to highlight the acceleration/deceleration pattern of the landslides and to compare the results to the in-situ GNSS velocity fields.

Figure 1: PSI velocity field calculated with Snapping FullRes over La Belotte landslide for years 2020-2021 and example of velocity time series.

Figure 2: PSI time series versus in-situ GNSS velocity field – example for 3 GNSS sensors.

Index Terms—Sentinel-1, PSI InSAR – Snapping, Small-baseline InSAR – GDM-SAR-in, GNSS, landslide

3. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Copernicus Sentinel-1 are available on <https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>. The fourth author is supported by a CNES post-doctoral fellowship (2023/2024). The calculations were performed on the AUTH High Performance Computing facility for SNAPPING, and through the GDM-SAR-in service of FormaTerre.

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**SLIP DYNAMICS ALONG THE CREEPING SEGMENT OF THE HAIYUAN FAULT
(GANSU, CHINA), FROM INSAR TIME SERIES ANALYSIS**

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Figure01 : (A) Average horizontal velocity map parallel to the fault in mm/yr. (B) Average vertical velocity (up-down) map in mm/yr. (C) Relative creep rate along the fault segment for the horizontal displacement map in mm/yr as a function of longitude. (D) Relative creep rate along the fault segment for the vertical displacement map in mm/yr as a function of longitude.

Advances in geodetic imaging and monitoring of faults have revealed slow deformation transients and complex interactions between slow aseismic events and rapid seismic events, highlighting the role of slow slips in the nucleation of large earthquakes.

The Haiyuan Fault in northeastern China is of particular interest to decipher fault slip behavior and the associated physical mechanisms, due to its dual slip modes, similar to that of the San Andreas Fault in California, with both locked segments prone to major earthquakes and segments where aseismic slip (or "creep") is observed. Here we focus on its 35 km-long creeping segment in the junction area between the western termination of the 1920 Mw7.9 earthquake and the eastern termination of a seismic gap [1], revisiting the spatial distribution and temporal evolution of creep from the joint analysis of ERS, Envisat and Sentinel-1 data.

We primarily use Sentinel-1 displacement time series over a seven-year period (2015-2022) processed by the FormaTerre FLATSIM service [2], corresponding to two tracks along ascending orbits and three tracks along descending orbits covering the creeping section of the fault. We first analyze the linear and seasonal components of the displacement time series, then decomposed them into fault-parallel horizontal velocity and vertical velocity fields. The creep signature and spatial extent are clearly identified in the line of sight and horizontal velocity maps. The surface creep rate distribution shows along-strike variations with peaks reaching up to 5 mm/yr for the horizontal component. Subsidence at a rate of 6,5 mm/yr is also observed in the extensional relay zone at the eastern end of the creeping section. We then invert InSAR line of sight velocity maps for the slip distribution along the seismogenic zone using the CSI software [3], using GNSS data from [4] as additional constraint. Creep distribution is compared with those derived from ERS and Envisat data to discuss the potential evolution of creep over decades.

Previous studies based on scarce Envisat data suggested the occurrence of transient bursts of creep along the studied section [5]. We also investigate such potential temporal variations in the creep rate. We analyze the temporal evolution of the cumulative relative creep, for each track independently, applying Principal and Independent Component Analysis as exploratory tools (separating the extensional relay zone from the western part of the creeping section). Preliminary results show specific spatial patterns associated with mixed creep/subsidence, consistent on all tracks, and possibly at least one transient at the end of 2019, which tectonic and/or hydrological origin needs further investigations.

Index Terms: InSAR, Slow slip events, Transient creep, Haiyuan fault

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Automatic seismic fault scarp mapping with deep learning

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Abstract

Mapping seismic faults is crucial for better identifying seismic risk. Over the past years, many promising machine learning methods have emerged for detecting geological objects from satellite data. However, even though some of these methods focus on objects similar to faults (such as rock cracks), they are relying on very different and easier features (e.g. difference of color of the crack). To detect the hardly visible fault scarps at a large scale, the combination of optical and Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) is crucial. There is currently no automatic method for detecting seismic faults. We thus developed the first automatic deep learning detector using Sentinel-2 RGB optical images and a TanDEM-X DEM. The model, based on a U-Net architecture, provides large-scale fault mapping of the Atacama Desert in southern Peru. For now, it still requires improvements as it produces numerous false positives. Nevertheless, this architecture and the selected data are promising for more advanced future work.

Introduction

When a rock structure is under mechanic stress, it may break, generating an earthquake. After the rupture, two rock compartments appear, creating a fault scarp. The latter is thus a marker of mechanic stresses in the rock i.e. a good indicator of past but also of future seismic activity. Mapping such faults is crucial for seismic risk management. However, it takes a lot of time and knowledge for geologists to identify them on satellite imagery and on the ground. Recent work by [Mattéo et al. \[2021\]](#) and [Chen et al. \[2022\]](#) has shown that it is possible to automatically

detect rock cracks and fractures in optical images. However, their work is limited to small areas known for their seismic activity and does not concern fault scarps. Large-scale fault mapping encounters three main difficulties. First, fault markers are difficult to spot and can be confused with other similar features (roads, valleys, rivers, etc.). Second, there is a lack of labelled data (i.e. known faults) to train a machine learning algorithm. Third, the closest detection methods are mainly limited to the use of optical images without considering Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) which contain important information. For this task, we thus developed a U-Net architecture [[Ronneberger et al., 2015](#)] using Sentinel-2 RGB optical images (10m resolution) and a TanDEM-X DEM (12m resolution). The model has been trained on large-scale fault mapping of the Atacama Desert in southern Peru.

Method

Data: We constructed a database by manually mapping more than 2000 faults over 140000 km² in the Atacama Desert in southern Peru. As this area is located in the desert andine subduction zone, it has many active faults and few clouds and vegetation, thus being a good pilot zone. It was then divided in three datasets for training, validating and testing the model. In order to be used by the network, RGB images and DEM are separated into 64x64 patches. The DEM is first interpolated to a 10m resolution and concatenated with the RGB image, creating a 4-channels 64x64 input image. The ground-truth mask, created by rasterizing the manual fault inventory, is then associated to this image to get input-target pairs. Larger patches

Figure 1: Designed U-Net - adapted from [Ronneberger et al. \[2015\]](#)

have been tested but metrics were lower. Faults are 3-pixels-width lines, making them under-represented on large patches.

U-Net segmentation model: This problem was treated as a binary segmentation task. The model used in this work is adapted from the original [Ronneberger et al. \[2015\]](#) U-Net (see figure 1). The input layer has been modified to process 4-channels images. The depth of the model, i.e. the number of convolutional blocks, was tested in order to maximize the IoU (Intersection over union) and the F1-score (synthetizing the precision and recall of the classification result) on the validation set. Table 1 demonstrates that an intermediate depth is the best configuration. Table 2 illustrates the importance of multi-modal input: metrics are nearly improved by a factor 2 when using RGB images and DEM together.

	3 conv. blocks	4 conv. blocks	5 conv. blocks
IoU	0.09 (for thresh. 0.67)	0.10 (for thresh. 0.67)	0.06 (for thresh. 0.67)
F1-score	0.17	0.18	0.12
Precision	0.14	0.14	0.09
Recall	0.23	0.27	0.18

Table 1: Influence of U-Net depth on validation dataset results

	Sentinel-2 RGB	DEM	Sentinel-2 RGB +DEM
IoU	0.06 (for tresh. 0.67)	0.05 (for tresh. 0.67)	0.10 (for tresh. 0.67)
F1-score	0.11	0.09	0.18
Precision	0.07	0.06	0.14
Recall	0.36	0.22	0.27

Table 2: Influence of different input data on validation dataset results

Training process: Our model has been trained on 3730 patches, with a batch size of 4, using an

Adam optimizer and a weighted cross entropy loss (weight=20). Learning rate starts at 0.01 and is multiplied by 0.1 every 5 epochs without improvement. Training is stopped after 10 epochs without improvement. Data augmentation has been added (random 0°, 90°, 180°, 270° rotation and random horizontal and vertical flip).

Preliminary results

As shown figure 2, even if some faults are well detected, some remain hard to segment. Moreover, the network produces numerous false positives. This is in accordance with table 2, where we can see that the precision is quite low, at 0.14 (and thus the F1-score is also low). Yet, we already identified potential faults that were not originally detected, paving the way for a tool able to help geomorphologists. Nonetheless, the improvement of the current network coupled with higher quality data could give promising results. Future work could use self-supervised learning (SSL) i.e. models that learn data patterns on a large amount of data and then learn a downstream task with less data, in order to overcome the limitation of the small size of existing labelled data. Another challenge would be to extend the application domain of the algorithm which is, for now, restraint to desert-like regions.

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Figure 2: Results on the test dataset. Ground truth (blue), segmentation result (red). Well classified fault on Sentinel-2 background 2a, 2b, on DEM background 2c, 2d. Bad classified fault on Sentinel-2 background 2e, 2f, on DEM background 2g, 2h.

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MONITORING GLACIER TOPOGRAPHY FROM SPACE: PAST SUCCESSES, NOVEL OBSERVATIONS USING SWOT AND PERSPECTIVES FROM 4D-EARTH

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ABSTRACT

Observing changes in glacial topography is important because glaciers are excellent climate indicators, and their melting contributes to rising sea levels, water resources in arid regions and can trigger glacier hazards.

The first global and comprehensive estimate of terrestrial glacier volume loss, for the period 2000-2019, has been made possible thanks to the opening of the ASTER/TERRA satellite's stereo pair database. This satellite will definitively run out of fuel in 2027 and will not be replaced. Modern optical sensors provide stereo images of higher resolution and precision, but mainly for the polar regions or specific targets, and with no free, systematic or global acquisitions. Radar satellites such as the German Aerospace Center's

TanDEM-X (or Harmony in the future) deliver highly-resolved elevations, but the data are ambiguous due to signal penetration into snow and ice and lack of easily interpreted visible images.

In this presentation, we will illustrate past, present and near-future efforts to continue glacier monitoring from space. We will show how the swath observations from SWOT are promising, not only for glaciology but also for other applications in geosciences, such as the measurement of the elevation difference produced by volcanic activity. Finally, we will present 4D-Earth, a satellite mission proposed to the French Space Agency to ensure frequent monitoring of the Earth surface.

Figure 1. Ten years of elevation difference over Vatnajökull Ice Cap, using elevations derived from SWOT (January 2024) compared with elevations from TanDEM-X (composite of winter 2013-2014)

RAINFALL, ANTHROPOGENIC ACTIVITY OR THE CHAMOLI FLOOD? WHAT TRIGGERED THE REACTIVATION OF THE JOSHIMATH SLOPE (UTTARAKHAND, INDIA): INSIGHTS FROM MULTI-SENSOR SATELLITE OBSERVATIONS

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ABSTRACT

It has long been recognized that river erosion at the toe of hillslopes can cause slope failures, triggering new or reactivating existing landslides. The impact of extreme flooding on slope stability has been studied only for some specific case-studies during the events [1,2] while flood impact on the longer-term lateral erosion and its impact on slope stability [3,4] has been rarely considered. This question is however of importance for our understanding of the impacts of flood events, as flood-driven erosion and slope failures are generally not considered in analyses of flood hazards, leaving potentially vulnerable populations unaware of their risk.

Recently, in the Joshimath area, a landslide connected to the Rishiganga River in Northern India has attracted a lot of attention [5,6]. Indeed, the slope faced major signs of slope instability in early 2022, about a year after an extreme flood event occurred in the region following the Chamoli rock and ice avalanche in February 2021 [7]. The triggering mechanisms invoked to explain this reactivation are precipitation rates [3] and/or anthropogenic activities [4]. However, the role of the Chamoli rock and ice avalanche in this reactivation has not been investigated. In this study, we performed a regional analysis of the slope movements along, and in the vicinity of the Rishiganga River in order to investigate whether or not the Chamoli flood had an impact on the landslides located at the banks of the river. We processed multi-sensor satellite image time series (Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2) using SAR interferometry (InSAR) and offset tracking techniques to measure both slow and fast displacement rates. Further, an archive of Pléiades images was also used to construct time series of Digital Surface Models (DSMs) and estimate the erosion and deposition rates before and after the Chamoli 2021 avalanche.

In total, we detected about 20 active landslides along, and in the vicinity, of the Rishiganga rRver. Some of them are located at the bank of the river, others in neighboring catchments that were not affected by the Chamoli flooding. For each active landslide, we analyzed the displacement time series and detected the occurrence of an acceleration onset and its date using Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

First, we show that the majority of the landslides are characterised by a constant velocity from 2016 to 2024 with no significant acceleration (PC1, Figure 1). Second, we show that two PCs present transient acceleration in fall 2021 (PC3, Figure 1) and in winter 2022-2023 (PC6, Figure 1) and are located in the Joshimath landslide and the neighbouring landslides at the East of the town. These results likely indicate that the landslides directly connected to the Rishiganga River were reactivated after 2021 while the other landslides in the region did not undergo significant reactivation. We discuss the possible mechanisms (e.g. water seepage at the toe, debuttressing due to river-bank erosion) that led to the Joshimath slope reactivation.

Index Terms— InSAR, offset tracking, landslide, Pléiades, Sentinel-1.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Pléiades images are distributed by Airbus DS, and were acquired with the support of CNES (French Space Agency) through the DINAMIS and CIEST² programmes. Copernicus Sentinel-1 and 2 data are accessible at <https://dataspace.copernicus.eu>. For the Sentinel-2 time series analysis, the calculations were performed on the

Figure 1: Results of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for the region impacted by the Chamoli ice and rock avalanche of February 2021. The location of the Joshimath slope and the Rishiganga River is indicated in the upper sub-figures. The active landslides are delimited with black lines on the figures in the right and were detected by inspecting the displacement time series obtained by processing Sentinel-1 with multi-temporal interferometry.

EOST/A2S High Performance Computing facility of the University of Strasbourg using the GDM-OPT-SLIDE service of FormaTerre. For the Sentinel-1 time series analysis, the processing was carried out using the ISCE software.

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GDM-SAR-IN: OPENNING OF A NEW FORMATERRE ON-DEMAND SERVICE FOR SENTINEL-1 INSAR PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

GDM-SAR-In is a new on-demand services for Sentinel-1 InSAR processing offered by the French research infrastructure Data Terra, developed and operated by its solid Earth hub, FormaTerre, in collaboration with ISTerre (OSUG), IPGP, CNES and the National Observation Service ISDeform of InSU/CNRS.

The service has been opened to French users in June 2024 and it is accessible through a FormaTerre account. The service web page <https://en.poleterresolide.fr/gdm-sar-in-service/> gives information about the access and the use of the services.

The service is deployed on the CNES computing center, it was set up with the support of CNES and CNRS/INSU. Based on the NSBAS processing chain [1,2,3] using a small baseline approach [4], GDM-SAR-IN allows an automated computation of single interferogram or a network of interferograms with its associated unwrapped phase time series giving access to measurement of ground deformations worldwide and with a revisit time down up to 6 days. This service allows non-expert users to run processing with simple option choices without having to worry about setting up and maintaining a complex processing chain (including downloading Sentinel-1 images, precise orbit data, digital terrain model and atmospheric model data, and the demanding TOPSAR mode processing of Sentinel-1 acquisitions) on a computing cluster.

It also offers expert users a simple and fast way to explore a new area or a specific phenomenon such as a volcanic or seismic crisis, while keeping a certain flexibility in the choice

of processing parameters. The availability of intermediate products and processing information allow expert users to reprocess, by their own, parts of the processing if necessary.

Users access the service through a web interface specifically designed for radar interferometry usage (see figure 1). The interface allows the user to interactively choose the study area and the Sentinel-1 data suitable for InSAR processing and to follow the progress of the processing. The generated products are available for download for a limited period of time (a few weeks). A preview of the products is possible directly on the interface.

This service is complementary to another FormaTerre's FLATSIM service [5], providing an easy-to-use InSAR data exploration tool and delivers results quickly, but on limited data volumes. Quantitative exploitation of the results requires a degree of expertise and potentially re-analysis by the user.

The GDM-SAR-In generated products are consistent to those of the FLATSIM service, (see detailed product descriptions <https://formater.pages.in2p3.fr/flatsim>). Most of the products are provided in both radar and ground geometry (in geotiff format), interferograms are available in different versions (wrapped/unwrapped, filtered/unfiltered, with/without atmospheric correction from global model) allowing for user-customized post-processing. A time series of the unwrapped phase is also provided as well as many other auxiliary products allowing advanced analysis of ground displacements by the user. Products are compatible with the catalog and data formats of FormaTerre and of the Thematic

Core Service Satellite Data of the European research infrastructure EPOS.

Examples of applications and products are also available from the service website covering multidisciplinary applications such monitoring of telluric hazards (volcanic eruptions, earthquakes, landslides,), hydrology, etc. A wider opening to the community of EPOS users is planned, but its modalities and its economic model are under discussion.

Index Terms— InSAR, Sentinel-1, on-demand service

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Figure 1. Screen capture of the web interface of the GDM-SAR-In Service

MANGO Toolbox: Mitigating Atmospheric Noise with GNSS Observations

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ABSTRACT

Volcanoes located in tropical environment are among the most challenging targets for radar interferometry techniques due to the high-relief, the temporal decorrelation due to dense vegetation and the presence of atmospheric noise that originates from the ionosphere or the troposphere. Tropospheric signals are often present in interferograms processed on volcanic edifices, which can limit the detection of ground deformation. Tropospheric signals are composed of a stratified component due to the difference of elevation between the base and the summit and a turbulent component at different wavelengths from 1 to few km. Numerous methods have been largely developed for mitigating of tropospheric noise such as empirical approach based on the phase-elevation correlation, spatiotemporal filtering or the use of weather-based models (ECMWF, NARR) [1,2,3]. For Sentinel-1 processing, weather models are commonly used for InSAR routine processing as datasets are available worldwide with only a few days of time latency and the products required (e.g., tropospheric delays maps) are easy to compute. Global weather-based corrections have shown good performance for large-scale studies (e.g., entire country or long fault systems). However, the performance becomes low in environment experiencing rapid spatio-temporal changes in atmospheric conditions such as tropical volcanoes [3, 4]. It is due to the poor spatial and temporal resolution of the weather models that provide hourly solutions on a grid >10 km. Similar to SAR microwaves, GNSS signal is impacted when it passes through the troposphere and therefore tropospheric delays at each station can be retrieved. Here, we

attend to refine the spatial and temporal resolution of the tropospheric delays models by using the information provided by GNSS network.

1. FROM GNSS MEASUREMENTS TO LOCAL TROPOSPHERIC MODELS

On active volcanoes, Volcano Observatories often operate and maintain a network of GNSS stations with the primary aim to detect ground displacements prior to the eruption thanks to high temporal sampling. However, the spatial information provided by a GNSS network is limited by the number and the distribution of the ground stations. For this reason, differential radar interferometry (dInSAR) is complementary to GNSS as it can provide high spatial information after tropospheric noise is properly mitigated. Zenith Tropospheric Delays are processed at each GNSS station. From sparse measurements, we evaluate the stratified and the turbulent component using the Iterative Tropospheric Decomposition [5] to provide a map of the slant-range tropospheric delays for each SAR epoch. An open-source toolbox MANGO (Mitigating Atmospheric Noise using GNSS Observations) is currently in development and available on gitlab upon request.

Figure 1. Tropospheric corrections obtained from GNSS models for two Sentinel-1 unwrapped interferograms at La Réunion Island (left: raw interferograms, middle: corrections and right: corrected interferograms)

2. BENEFIT OF GNSS-BASED MODELS COMPARED TO GLOBAL WEATHER-BASED MODELS

The toolbox MANGO has been tested so far in two end-members: i) Piton de la Fournaise (La Réunion island) a well instrumented oceanic basaltic volcanoes with ~34 GNSS stations over the island and ii) Merapi (Indonesia), an andesitic stratovolcano monitored by only 8 GNSS stations. For both test sites, ERA5 models perform better than GACOS models, which shows that temporal resolution is more important than spatial resolution. For Piton de la Fournaise, GNSS models reduce the tropospheric noise for 80-90% of the interferograms processed, which corresponds to an increase of performance of 25% in comparison with ERA5 models. As expected, the performance decrease for Merapi but GNSS models provide the same performance as ERA5 models.

3. TOWARDS NEAR REAL-TIME INSAR MONITORING ON ACTIVE VOLCANOES

The approach tested here can be applied for all monitored areas with only few GNSS stations distributed at different elevations. Compared to weather-based models, the GNSS local models obtained by the MANGO toolbox can be delivered in near real-time as soon as the GNSS data are available (e.g., <24h for OVPF). Therefore, such auxiliary products are useful for routine InSAR monitoring and as a result the corrected InSAR products will support the interpretation of ground deformation signals by Volcano Observatories during volcanic crisis.

Index Terms— InSAR, Sentinel-1, atmospheric corrections, weather models, GNSS delays

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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ACTIVE STRAINING OF THE BALKANS PENINSULA : INSIGHTS FROM SPATIAL GEODESY (INSAR AND GNSS)

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1. CONTEXT AND PROBLEMATIC

The Balkans Peninsula is best known for its mountainous areas where rugged reliefs govern the lives of its inhabitants, yet it is also one of the most seismic areas in Europe. Over the last decades, large and destructive earthquakes of up to Mw 7 have occurred, causing significant damage and fatalities. The 1979 earthquake in Montenegro (Mw 6.9), which left 136 fatalities, 100,000 people homeless, and 31 billion euros in damage, is a striking example of the catastrophic consequences that such powerful seismic events can cause.

The seismic activity has been important recently, with significant earthquakes (Mw 6+) occurring in Dürres (Albania, 2019), Petrinja (Croatia, 2020), and Tyrnavos (Greece, 2021).

These earthquakes occurred in diverse tectonic context, reflecting the complexity of the regional geodynamic setting. Despite efforts over the past decades, the Balkans Peninsula remains relatively poorly instrumented compared to its counterparts in Italy or Turkey.

The latest study of the regional kinematics (Piña-Valdés et al., 2022) based on a combination of GNSS velocity fields shows that the majority of the peninsula is expected to move at very low velocities ranges, well below 1 cm/yr. However, large areas are not monitored by GNSS stations, and the overall network is too sparse to identify small-scale structures.

2. DATA AND METHODS

Our aim is to take advantage of a new InSAR dataset processed by the FLATSIM service (Thollard et al., 2019) based on Sentinel-1 data. FLATSIM interferograms, displacement time series and velocity maps are available over the Balkans region, covering 360 000 km² (8 tracks acquired along ascending orbits and 6 tracks along descending orbits have been processed), with a ground resolution of about 120m.

With millimeter precision and a 6 to 12 days temporal resolution, this dataset is used to better assess and quantify the current deformation of the peninsula, as complementary to GNSS data.

From the FLATSIM displacement time series, we first separate, for each track, the linear and seasonal components. We then reference the velocities (the extracted linear components) into an ITRF reference frame, adapting the approach of Lemrabet et al. (2023), based on the time series analysis of phase gradients (in range and azimuth) of interferograms (see Fig. 1). This allows us to produce the first large-scale InSAR velocity field for the Balkans Peninsula, referenced in the ITRF with very limited use of GNSS data.

Fig. 1 : GNSS velocities solution from (Pina-Valdés et al, 2022). Velocities referenced in Eurasia-fixed frame.

3. FIRST RESULTS

We then analyze serial profiles of line of sight velocities across major active structures in the region. This reveals, with unmatched resolution, tectonic deformation patterns related for example, to the Dinaric thrusts, the extension of Albanides in their inner part (Ohrid graben) and the normal faults in the Gulf of Corinth.

We next decomposed the velocity field into horizontal and vertical components, which unveils new insights and highlights the added value of InSAR compared to GNSS. We used B-strain software (Pagani et al. 2021) to interpolate via Bayesian inversion the GNSS excepted signal.

Finally, the richness of the dataset leaves much more to explore, such as seasonal signals due to transient deformation of basins or aquifers (Serpelloni et al. 2018) or due to anthropogenic activities such as oil pumping (Métois et al. 2020).

Fig. 2 : Comparative maps of the study region showing GNSS horizontal velocities reprojected in the LOS direction (top) from Piña-Valdés et al. (2022) and the InSAR mean velocity map (bottom) from FLATSIM products. The FLATSIM map is derived using a similar approach to Lemrabet et al. (2023). The left and right panels correspond to ascending and descending tracks, respectively.

Index Terms — InSAR, GNSS, Balkans, interseismic, subsidence, tectonics

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

InSAR data are provided by FLATSIM service, an automatic intensive computation based on Sentinel-1 data, operated by FormaTer and CNES.

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CIEST² support during the ongoing volcanic crisis on the Reykjanes Peninsula in south-west Iceland

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ABSTRACT

Since March 2021, 9 eruptions have occurred on the Reykjanes peninsula in south-west Iceland, and some lava flows have threatened infrastructure. During this period, CIEST² has been activated 6 times, providing useful data both for operational monitoring during the onset of eruptions (maps of the margins and thickness of lava flows), for developing or testing new methodologies (estimation of the elevation and velocity of the volcanic plume, coastal bathymetry) and for improving our understanding of the physical processes at play during this volcanic unrest (characterisation of the large displacement fields induced by the rifting event, effusion rate estimates).

1. VOLCANIC UNREST ON REYKJANES PENINSULA

The Reykjanes Peninsula in south-west Iceland is an oblique rift zone, part of the boundary between the North American and European plates. In March 2021, a basaltic effusive eruption in the Fagradalsfjall volcanic system, in an unpopulated area, ended a period of almost 800 years without volcanic activity. The eruption, which lasted six months and emplaced 150 million m³ of magma on the surface, had been well anticipated due to the precursory signals recorded in the preceding weeks (significant increase in seismicity and ground deformation measured by satellite radar interferometry) [1,2]. The start of the eruption was tracked using daily Pléiades acquisitions scheduled over a ten-day period as part of the CIEST² initiative launched by FormaTerre, which aims to promote the acquisition of

satellite data in the event of natural disasters. Since then, two other eruptions have taken place at the same location, in 2022 (from 3 March to 21 August 2022) and in the summer of 2023 (from 10 July to 7 August 2023). These eruptions also benefited from the activation of CIEST².

At the end of 2023, the activity moved towards Svartsengi with a 15 km long oblique rift propagating under the town of Grindavík in November 2023 and causing significant surface deformation [3]. CIEST² was reactivated. Since then, 6 eruptions have occurred in this area (see Figure 1) and CIEST² has been activated twice. Up to date, a total of >150 million m³ of magma have been emplaced during these eruptions near the Svartsengi/Grindavík area.

Figure 1. Pléiades image acquired the 27th of March 2024 showing the lava flows emplaced during the seven first eruption on the Reykjanes peninsula (Pléiades@CNES 2024 Distribution Airbus DS).

2. BENEFITS FOR OPERATIONAL MONITORING

Pléiades stereopairs are processed to produce a Digital Elevation model at 2 m resolution. The difference in elevation between each Pléiades DEM and a reference, pre-eruption DEM results in a lava thickness map, which is subsequently cropped using the lava outlines. This allow the calculation of the lava volumes, by estimating an average thickness value multiplied by the area of the lavas. When successive volume estimation are available, a mean effusion rate is derived [1]. This information is provided to the Civil Protection less than 6 hours after image acquisition.

Figure 2: Lava flow thickness map derived from the Pléiades images acquired the 27th of March 2024 (area covered by lava: 5.99 km², mean lava thickness: 4.3 ± 0.3 m lava volume (Bulk): 25.7 ± 1.9 Mm³). Information was provided to the Civil protection in less than 4 hours. Figure provided by Ragnar H. Prastarson, Icelandic Meteorological Office.

3. NEW METHODOLOGIES TESTED

Pléiades data have also been used to characterize the intensity of the eruption by providing insight into the elevation and the velocity of the volcanic plume [1] as well as to test a new space-based method to measure shallow bathymetry and possible submarine lava flow volume in shallow water [4].

4. BENEFITS FOR VOLCANIC PROCESSES UNDERSTANDING

Data gathered on lava effusion rates have evidenced an uncommon behavior of the 6 month duration 2021 eruption with an effusion rate increasing during the eruption, where the highest discharge usually occurs in the opening phase [2].

This effusion rate evolution is consistent with a deep feeding of the system during the eruption.

Index Terms— CIEST², Pléiades, DEM differencing, Pixel Offset Tracking, lava flow, coastal bathymetry, volcanic plume.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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**DYNAMICS OF THE HYDROLOGICAL NETWORK IN THE KARST OF FONTAINE DE
VAUCLUSE (SE FRANCE) FROM THE QUANTIFICATION OF THE SURFACE
DEFORMATION USING MASSIVE INSAR ANALYSIS**

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Figure.1. Distinct deformation patterns derived from ascending and descending InSAR stac, using their correlation with the water flow rate at Fontaine-de-Vaucluse, located in the southeastern part of France in the Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur region.

ABSTRACT

This study examines the deformation mechanisms in the karstic region of the Fontaine de Vaucluse using Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) time series acquired in both descending and ascending geometries. The Fontaine de Vaucluse karst system is characterized by its soluble limestone and dolomite formations that have undergone chemical erosion, leading to the formation of underground conduits, caves, sinkholes, and resurgences. These formations result from complex interactions involving geological structures and hydrological processes. The study aims to analyze the time evolution of the ground displacement field by applying two distinct methods: non-parametric methods, including Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Independent Component Analysis (ICA), and a parametric approach that integrates water flow data from resurgence points.

The non-parametric methods, PCA and ICA, are applied to the InSAR time series data to decompose the signal into multiple components, each potentially representing different sources of noise or deformation signals. These methods reveal various types of noise, including atmospheric variations, instrumental errors, and annual seasonal trends that suggest periodic signals that could be partly associated with deformation processes. However, we do not extract a distinct deformation pattern related to subsurface geological processes.

The parametric approach is based on the use of hydrological data, specifically water flow rates measured at resurgence points. We investigate the relationship between the ground displacement and the water flow over time. By weighting the displacement signal at the period of strong water flows, we identify some specific deformation patterns. Using an iterative approach, we quantify

the relationship between the amplitude of the displacement and the water flow, which reveals a saturation level of the hydrological system, above which the deformation cannot increase. We examine potential temporal offsets between the outlet water discharge rate and the surface displacement. Thanks to the ascending and descending InSAR geometries, we are able to quantify the vertical and horizontal movements under conditions of maximum flow and model those with the opening of fissures at depth. Some of these openings are associated with deep-seated overpressures, thus related to the local presence of a sedimentary cover. This brings important constraints on the deep-seated geological phenomena and hydrological dynamics.

The comparison of the two methods shows their respective capabilities. The non-parametric methods effectively identify periodic signals and atmospheric variations, which are important for understanding seasonal deformation processes, despite being less effective in isolating specific deformation signals. The parametric method, by integrating hydrological data, better correlates deformation patterns with external variables, enhancing the understanding of the relationship between surface movements and subsurface processes.

Several directions for future research are proposed to refine the understanding and monitoring of deformation processes in karst regions. First, advanced modeling of the identified deformation patterns could quantify the contributions of geological and hydrological factors more accurately, potentially involving numerical models that consider geological structures, hydrological dynamics, and surface deformations.

Second, incorporating additional environmental parameters such as precipitation, temperature, and soil moisture content could improve the parametric models by capturing more variability in deformation signals. Third, recalibrating atmospheric correction models for InSAR data processing could reduce atmospheric noise influences, leading to more accurate deformation measurements. Developing region-specific atmospheric models or employing advanced computational techniques could enhance signal correction.

This study emphasizes the use of complementary analysis methods to capture the complexity of deformation mechanisms in karst regions. Advancing these methodologies and integrating multi-source data can improve the understanding of processes governing karst dynamics, contributing to water resource management, infrastructure stability, and environmental risk mitigation in karst regions.

KEYWORDS: karst, PCP, ICA, deformation, hydrology.

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A SLOW SLIP EVENT CYCLE ANALYSIS BASED ON INSAR FLATSIM TIME SERIES: CASE STUDY OF THE IZMIT SEGMENT ALONG THE NORTH ANATOLIAN FAULT

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ABSTRACT

Improving the detections and analysis of the transient aseismic slow slip events on major seismogenic faults may enable a better understanding of the seismic cycle and give constraints on the associated seismic hazard. For example, along the North Anatolian Fault (NAF) in Türkiye, two segments are still aseismically creeping decades after major earthquakes: the Ismetpasa segment following the 1942 Mw 7.4 earthquake [1, 2] and the Izmit segment following the 1999 Mw 7.6 earthquake [3, 4]. By using geodetic measurements (Global Positioning Systems (GPS) and Interferometry Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR)), previous studies showed that the Izmit segment is aseismically creeping, with an average velocity of 2.7 cm/year, more than 20 years after the earthquake. Detailed analysis on the dynamics of the Izmit creep enabled the detection of two transient slow slip events affecting the segment in September 2015 [5] and in December 2016 [6]. In this study, we used InSAR time series from Sentinel-1 A and B acquisitions over the extended period 2015-2021, automatically processed in the framework of the FLATSIM project [7], based on the NSBAS processing chain [8]. To extract the tectonic signal of the time series, we applied a specific post-processing sequence. First, we corrected for the annual seasonal components of each track, then we decomposed the residual line of sight signals into vertical and east-west deformation fields by combining ascending and descending tracks, and finally we performed an Independent Component Analysis (ICA) within the Izmit sedimentary basin to correct the time series for a high frequency noise. We decomposed the tectonic signal into a

temporal linear trend corresponding to continuous creep and transient slow slip events, and then we extracted the east-west surface static velocities/displacements associated with each period (Figure 1). Modeling the slip distribution using a 2D fault interface in a layered elastic half space [9], we estimate a locking depth of about 11 km with continuous creep between 2 and 5 km-depth. We extracted the deformation due to two main transient slow slip events, in March 2018 and in November 2019. The last event has also been recorded by two creepmeters along the Izmit segment. According to the slip distributions obtained via the previous method, the slip events occurred within the upper section of the fault (1-3 km-depth) with moment magnitudes of 4.3 and 4.4 respectively, coinciding with the sedimentary basin location. With creepmeter observations at two locations, we characterize a lateral propagation of 6.4 km/day for the 2019 event, like the along-strike propagation velocities of subduction zones slow slip events.

We estimated that along the central part of the Izmit segment, 50% of the total observed creep is occurring during the three 20 day-long slow slip events, and only 25-30% at the extremities of the segment. The establishment of such shallow aseismic creep seems to compensate the slip deficit due to the 1999 Izmit earthquake. The presence of a cycle of slow slip events along the Izmit and Ismetpasa segments of the North Anatolian Fault [1, 2] questions the underlying physical mechanisms and key parameters defining their amplitudes, recurrence intervals and propagation speeds. To precise these mechanisms and key parameters, we need to continue improving the detection methods of transient slow slip events to obtain a more complete catalog of slow slip events along the segment.

Figure 1. East-West velocity field during the continuous creep periods and East-West static offsets during the 2019 transient slow slip event. (A) Surface velocity computed during the continuous creep periods. (B) Fault-perpendicular profile (location of A with the dashed lines) of the East-West velocity and of the mean elevation. (C) Static displacement offsets estimated during the 2019 transient slow slip event. (D) Associated fault-perpendicular profile from the C map.

Index Terms— InSAR, shallow aseismic creep, slow slip event, seismic cycle, North Anatolian Fault

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DETECTION AND RECONSTRUCTION OF ROCK GLACIERS KINEMATIC OVER 24 YEARS (2000-2024) FROM LANDSAT IMAGERY

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ABSTRACT

Historically, the state of the cryosphere has been measured using specific variables defined by Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) such as mass balance for glaciers, snow covered variability for snow and soil temperature for permafrost. Among those variables, glacier mass balance and snow cover variations are relatively well known at global scale [1,2] compared to changes in mountain permafrost, which are still very incompletely monitored [3]. The importance of monitoring rock glacier dynamics is now widely acknowledged within the scientific community following the designation of rock glacier velocity as a parameter of the Essential Climatic Variable permafrost [4]. However, the representation of long-term spatio-temporal patterns of rock glaciers velocity at regional scale remains challenging due to the unavailability of high-resolution remote sensing datasets. Thus, several regions of the world lack of information about the impact of climate warming on mountain permafrost [5].

This study presents a robust methodological approach based on the redundancy of information, joint with the inversion of surface displacement time series [6] and the automatic detection of persistent moving areas (PMA) [7] applied to rock glacier monitoring, using annual open-access, medium-resolution Landsat 7/8 optical imagery. This methodology, applied in the Dry Andes of Chile and Argentina (between 29°20'S and 31°15'S latitude), enables the detection, quantification and analysis of surface kinematics of 382 gravitational slope movements over a 24-years, of which 153 corresponds to rock glaciers, 124 landslides and 105 non-classified objects. The results demonstrate an average velocity of 0.37 ± 0.07 m y⁻¹ overall 24-year for all rock

glaciers, with some exceptions where large rock glaciers and debris frozen landforms exhibit surface velocities exceeding 2 m y⁻¹ (Figure 1).

Validation using satellite Sentinel-1 radar interferometry processed by FLATSIM initiative [8], confirmed the classification, spatial extent and velocity attributes (ranges of velocity between 30 – 100 cm/year) of the PMAs, with 42% also detected on interferograms at 12 days temporal baselines, corresponding mainly to active rock glaciers. This study shows a good agreement with high-resolution imagery (aerial, Pleiades, GeoEye) and recent GNSS measurements [9]. L7/8 imagery tends to underestimate surface velocity by approximately 10-20%. The intrinsic limitations of Landsat imagery make it challenging to interpret annual velocity variations. Notwithstanding, decadal velocity changes can be depicted for the fastest and largest rock glaciers, revealing 10% of the accelerations in one decade. Finally, our study suggests a correlation between surface velocity and local topographic parameters (orientation, slope, elevation) as possible controlling factors.

This study demonstrates for the first time, the feasibility of using medium-resolution optical imagery for monitoring rock glacier kinematics anywhere over the World, providing an alternative to InSAR. Further work is needed to assess rock glacier velocity in other regions in the world, combining heterogeneous dataset like ASTER, Sentinel, and others, with the goal to improve the time series and depict complete regional patterns of rock glacier velocity.

Index Terms— InSAR, Pléiades, Landsat, rock glaciers, FLATSIM

Figure 1: Surface kinematic characterization for all PMAs in the central Andes region. a) Illustrates the spatial distribution of all valid PMAs (rock glaciers = 146; landslides = 115; others = 103) coloured by the ‘Top 50% average velocity’ surface velocity (viridis colorbar) within the PMA surface. The size of the circle is proportional to the rescaled PMA surface in $\text{m}^2/1,000$ for better visualisation. The Red letters correspond to the study cases presented in the following subplots. The remaining subplots b) to g) illustrate mean annual velocity field over the 24 year (2000–2024) for a specific landform (subplots with a suffix of *.1) as well as the corresponding cumulative displacement time series in metres (subplots with a suffix of *.2), extracted on the black (and red) point within the landform. Subplots b) to g) correspond to the following landforms b) Tapado Complex and Las Tolas Rock Glacier; c) Largo Rock Glacier; d) Tapado west Rock Glacier; e) Dos Lenguas Rock Glacier; f) Olivares Complex, g) Olivares west Rock Glacier.

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ASSESSMENT OF SOIL LOSS IN RWANDA BASED ON SATELLITE DATA

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ABSTRACT

The assessment and identification of potential soil loss risks in Rwanda is very crucial to develop adequate and reliable erosion prevention measures for Rwanda.

The satellite data are useful to accurately and timely monitor the soil loss across Rwanda. The Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE) was used to indicate the soil loss spatial variability in Rwanda in 2019 and 2020 based on satellite imageries from Climate Hazards Center InfraRed Precipitation with Station data (CHIRPS), Moderate-Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), Sentinel-2 MultiSpectral Instrument (MSI) Level-1C, and Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM).

The rainfall erosivity, soil erodibility, slope length and steepness, cover and management and support practice factors are remarkably contributing in estimating and detecting the soil loss.

The findings reveal that the severe and slight soil loss were dominant in in Western province and Eastern province respectively. The Western province is very known to have very heavy rainfall and high elevation while the Eastern province with low rainfall and low elevation. This indicates that rainfall erosivity and elevation are the main factors to the soil loss in Rwanda.

There was a significant increase in soil loss amount from 2019 to 2020 in regions located in Rusizi, Nyamasheke, Karongi, Rutsiro and Gisagara districts. The increase in soil loss amount at Lake Kivu and Nyabarongo river shorelines from 2019 to 2020 were resulted from the increase of water level.

There is a need to use the mentioned satellite data in national soil loss risk prevention with useful and effective recommendation to policy makers.

1. INTRODUCTION

The soil erosion is the most threatening environmental problem in many landscapes' areas in Rwanda while the main factors affecting the amount of soil eroded include land use and vegetation cover, topography, soil and climate (IUCN, 2022).

Rainfall erosivity is among the main drivers of soil erosion, which can be characterized by large spatial and temporal variability (Cui et al., 2020; Bezak et al. 2021).

The monitoring and identification of regions vulnerable to soil erosion is very important, as soil loss has a significant influence on reductions in agricultural land, reservoir capacity, water quality, and carbon sequestration (Lal, 2005, Panagos et al., 2016).

The soil erosion is mainly caused by to physical processes (Nearing et al., 1994): a soil particle separation process owing to the impact of the rainfall kinetic energy on the soil surface, and a sediment transportation process owing to surface flows.

2. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

2.1. DATA

The following section indicates the source and description of data used for this study.

2.1.1. Rainfall Erosivity (R)

Climate Hazards Center InfraRed Precipitation with Station data (CHIRPS) was used to calculate rainfall erosivity. CHIRPS incorporates 0.05° resolution satellite imagery. Rainfall Erosivity (R) factor (megajoules millimetre hectare⁻¹ hour⁻¹ year⁻¹) was calculated from CHIRPS data. It is a measure of rainfall energy and intensity.

2.1.2. Elevation

The elevation data based are based on on NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) with approximately spatial resolution of 30m.

2.1.3. Soil erodibility (K)

The soil erodibility (K) factor was calculated from Soil texture from USDA. K is a measure of the relative resistance of a soil to detachment and transport by water. It indicates the soil loss rate in t/ha per erosion index unit for a given soil.

2.1.4. Slope length and steepness (LS)

The slope length and steepness (LS) factor (unitless) was calculated from NASA SRTM elevation data. LS is the expected ratio of soil loss from a given slope. LS indicates the length and steepness of the slope. The longer the slope the greater the volume of runoff.

2.1.5. Crop and management (C)

The crop and management (C) factor (unitless) was calculated from Sentinel-2 MSI MultiSpectral Instrument, Level-1C satellite NDVI data. C is the ratio of soil loss from land cropped under specified conditions to the corresponding loss from clean-tilled, continuous fallow. Sentinel-2 is a wide-swath, high-resolution, multi-spectral imaging mission supporting Copernicus Land Monitoring studies, including the monitoring of vegetation, soil and water cover, as well as observation of inland waterways and coastal areas. C factor indicates the effects of vegetation cover and management techniques which contribute to the rate of soil loss.

2.1.7. Soil texture

The soil texture data are from USDA soil texture classification system.

2.1.6. Support practice (P)

The support practice (P) factor (unitless) was calculated from MODIS satellite data MCD12Q1.006 MODIS Land Cover Type Yearly Global 500m data based on land use land cover. P is the ratio of soil loss with a specific support to the corresponding soil loss with up-and-down hill culture. Support practices include contouring and contour strip

cropping. P factor indicates the effects of soil conservation measures.

2.2.METHODOLOGY

The soil loss (t/ha/year) spatial distribution in Rwanda in 2019 and 2020 was calculated based on the following Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE):

$$\text{Soil loss} = R \times K \times LS \times C \times P$$

3. RESULTS

3.1. Soil Loss

The soil loss spatial variability in 2019 (Figure 1, left) and 2020 (Figure 1, right) in Rwanda indicate that some changes while most of severe soil loss are most dominant in Western, Northern and Southern provinces.

The factors used to calculate the soil loss across Rwanda namely rainfall erosivity, soil erodibility, slope length and steepness, cover and management and support practice factors are remarkably contributing in estimating and detecting the soil loss.

Figure 1. Soil loss (t/ha) in 2019 (a) and 2020 (b)

The findings of this study (Figure 1) reveal that in 2019 and 2020, the severe and slight soil loss were dominant in western province and eastern province respectively. The moderate and slight soil loss were often found in Eastern province at Nyagatare, Gatsibo, Bugesera, Ngoma and Kayanza districts.

It is remarkable that amount of soil loss has increased from 2019 to 2020 in the most areas of Rwanda, especially in the regions located in the southern of Rusizi district, at Lake Kivu shoreline in Western Province (Nyamasheke, Karongi and Rutsiro districts), Southern region of Bugesera district, at Nyabarongo river shoreline in Kigali, and also in Southern province at Gisagara district. The increase in amount of soil loss were highly resulted from the increase of heavy rainfall that has resulted to erosion in those above mentioned regions.

The findings of this study reveal also the importance to consider the water quality level from various water resources while monitoring the soil loss.

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REVEALING LANDSLIDE BI-MONTHLY AND ANNUAL DYNAMICS USING A COMBINATION OF RADAR INTERFEROMETRY AND STRUCTURE-FROM-MOTION: THE STUDY CASE OF GRAND EBOULIS

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ABSTRACT

Landslides are major erosion processes that provide large volumes of sediments to rivers possibly inducing important hazards for surrounding population [1]. Understanding the dynamics and controls of landslides is thus essential to help prevent casualties and damages. Landslides can be divided in two types: (I) the catastrophic ones e.g., shallow landslides, rock falls or larger debris flows, and (II) the slow-moving ones such as slumps or earth flows. Numerous slow-moving landslides are monitored to help prevent risks, using in particular ground-based techniques like GNSS. However, others cannot be instrumented due to their inaccessibility. In these latter cases, remote sensing is the only tool to retrieve landslides behaviour and dynamics.

Located in the northern part of Réunion island in the watershed of Rivière des Pluies, Grand Eboulis is a large and remote vegetated deposit of 1 km² surrounded by steep slopes up to 250 m high (figure 1A). It is interpreted as the result of a debris avalanche and would be now in a remobilisation phase marked by the occurrence of shallow landslides on its flanks [2]. Notably, in March 2002, a flank collapse occurred after extreme rainfall, creating a natural dam in the river, which evacuation resulted in three casualties. To better understand the relationship between precipitation and dynamics, we used a combination of radar interferometry and Structure-from-Motion. Such combination of short- to very short-term techniques helped us establish the pace at which the entire deposit moves and provide sediments to the river.

Firstly, the bi-monthly dynamics of Grand Eboulis is investigated using radar interferometry. Sentinel-1 StripMap images acquired every 12 days between September 2016 and December 2022 are processed using the AMSTer processing chain [3]. Images are first associated into

interferometric pairs using baseline conditions of 50 m and 50 days to avoid decorrelation due to the tropical climate of Réunion. Differential interferograms are then produced from the selected pairs and converted into differential displacement maps. Using an MSBAS approach, differential displacement maps are inverted into cumulated displacement maps in east-west and vertical directions for each acquisition dates [4]. From these cumulated displacement maps, time series are extracted from 22 pixels scattered across the landslide. Atmospheric correction is performed on the final products by subtracting the signal of a stable reference points to the signals recorded over Grand Eboulis. Lastly, to take into account the presence of vegetation on the landslide, a detection threshold is designed using vegetated stable areas. Signals outside the threshold range is considered as interpretable as displacement.

Cumulated displacement maps and time series demonstrate that Grand Eboulis is actually a slow moving landslide with a continuous east and downward displacement with maximum cumulated values of 76.49 cm east and 49.29 cm down which is equivalent to maximum average velocities of 14 cm/year east and 9 cm/year down over the five year period. This displacement is characterised by spatial clustering with the highest values of displacement being recorded near the steepest slopes and by temporal variation with the occurrence of two regime changes: an acceleration in June 2018 with maximum velocities up to 24 cm/year east and 17 cm/year down and a deceleration with a decrease of maximum velocities to 7 cm/year east and 4 cm/year down in November 2020 (figure 1B-C). Between these events, average velocity values of up to 14 cm/year east and 9 cm/year down are recorded.

Secondly, the multi-annual dynamics of Grand Eboulis is obtained using Structure-from-Motion. Aerial images are obtained from ultra-light flight surveys on September 15th 2017, March 12th 2018 and June 19th 2019

and are processed using Agisoft Metashape to produce 3D-point clouds [5]. Georeferencing of the point clouds is performed using Ground Control Points (GCPs), imported and picked for each images in Metashape. To refine ground calibration, each point clouds are aligned on the year+1 campaign with the 2019 point cloud being considered as a reference. Digital surface models and orthoimages are then computed for each campaign based on the final calibration with a spatial resolution of 2 m for the DSM and a spatial resolutions of 8, 7 and 10 cm for 2017, 2018 and 2019 orthoimages respectively. Some residual horizontal and vertical shifts persisting on DSMs, point cloud registration is performed using iterative closest point as implemented in the open3d toolbox of Python [6].

From the comparison of consecutive orthoimages, we studied the slope remobilisation of Grand Eboulis. Thirty shallow landslides are mapped for the period between 2017 and 2018, all located on the steepest slopes of the landslide and a range of their volume is obtained using difference of DSMs (figure 1B). Dates of events are refined comparing cloudless Sentinel 2 images acquired during the period. All scars appear between February 1st and March 12th 2018 (figure 1D). Oppositely, orthoimages comparison between 2018 and 2019 shows no landslide scars but a quick vegetation growth that covers some 2017-2018 scars. These results are verified by the comparison of Sentinel 2 images between the two flights campaigns.

The combination of radar interferometry and Structure-from-Motion shows that Grand Eboulis is a slow-moving landslide marked by a continuous displacement interspersed by regime changes associated with a slope remobilisation phase. When compared to daily, monthly and annual rainfall analysis, these dynamics appear to be driven by extreme meteorological events (figure 1D). This combination of techniques thus allows to obtain a better understanding of Grand Eboulis behaviour and is widely applicable to other settings.

Index Terms— InSAR, SfM, Landslides

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Figure 1. Grand Eboulis dynamics and controls. A- orthophotograph of Grand Eboulis (IGN) with the main structures (polygons) B- East-West displacement maps and location of mapped shallow landslides (red). C- Box plot of east-west cumulated displacement time series with regime changes highlighted in red and blue. D- Daily precipitation and 6 month moving average of the precipitation recorded at 5 weather stations near Grand Eboulis over the studied period (Météo France). The occurrence of shallow landslides is highlighted in orange.

3D GROUND DEFORMATION TIME SERIES AT PITON DE LA FOURNAISE USING ALOS-2 DATA.

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ABSTRACT

In InSAR (Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar), deformation measurements are typically conducted along the line of sight. By combining multiple images, usually from ascending and descending passes, it is possible to determine displacements in the East-West (EW) and Up-Down (UD) components. However, the North-South (NS) component is often considered lost due to the low sensitivity of sub-polar orbits to this direction. At Piton de la Fournaise, between April 2021 and April 2024, a total of 1,626 ALOS-2 SpotLight images were acquired, using 27 different incidence angles from both right- and left-looking modes. This diversity in acquisition modes offers the potential to decompose the displacement field into three dimensions (East-West, Up-Down, and North-South). ALOS-2 in SpotLight mode also provides metric-level spatial resolution, combined with the advantage of L-band SAR that maintain coherence even in vegetated. Thus, the high density of ALOS-2 SpotLight acquisitions allows for the creation of high temporal resolution time series that could enable the detection of low-amplitude, large-wavelength spatial signals typical of the inter-eruptive displacements detected by the GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) network of *Observatoire Volcanologique du Piton de la Fournaise* (OVPF-IPGP).. Finally, the combination of high spatial resolution and high acquisition frequency opens new perspectives for studying inter-eruptive signals at Piton de la Fournaise.

1. ACCURATE CHARACTERIZATION OF CO-ERUPTIVE DISPLACEMENT

Between April 2021 and April 2024, seven seismic crises reported by the OVPF resulted in four eruptions and three intrusions (i.e. ascent of magma within the volcanic edifice that did not reach the surface). For each of these events, interferograms and displacement maps were provided to

OVPF-IPGP as quickly as possible. To achieve this, we used ALOS-2 Spotlight data as well as Sentinel-1, TerraSAR-X, TanDEM-X, and PAZ. The displacement maps produced within the days following the onset of the eruption complement the information provided by GNSS data, which are much more temporally precise but far less spatially dense. For each of these crises, between 14 and 21 independent differential ALOS-2 SpotLight interferograms were computed and used to decompose the displacement field into three components (EW, UD, and NS). Thanks to the wide range of acquisition geometries provided by this exceptionally extensive InSAR database, we achieved unprecedented accuracy in the calculated 3D displacements. The north-south (NS) component of the displacement, in particular, was determined with a level of accuracy not typically attained using InSAR data (figure 1) [1].

The exceptional precision achieved in co-eruptive displacements derived from ALOS-2 Spotlight interferograms, particularly for North-South displacements is made possible by the combination of three main favorable factors: the very high resolution of the ALOS-2 Spotlight interferograms; the very good coherence of the ALOS-2 Spotlight interferograms; and the large number of independent interferograms available for a given eruption, offering a wide variety of acquisition geometries with both ascending and descending passes, as well as right-looking and left-looking views.

This detailed analysis enabled a more comprehensive understanding of the deformation processes preceding and accompanying each volcanic event. In particular, the ability to resolve the full 3D displacement field offers new insights into magma intrusion dynamics and surface deformation, critical for improving volcanic hazard assessments at Piton de la Fournaise.

Figure 1. 3D components (a) E-W, (b) N-S and (c) vertical of ground displacements for the July 2023 eruption at Piton de la Fournaise.

2. INTER-ERUPTIVE DISPLACEMENTS CHARACTERIZATION THROUGH 3D TIME SERIES PROCESSING

Since the early 21st century, radar interferometry used at Piton de la Fournaise could not detect the low-amplitude, long-wavelength uplifts typically recorded by OVPF-IPGP's GNSS stations before an eruption. Measuring and modeling these subtle displacements is crucial for assessing volcanic hazards on La Réunion Island, as they signal the pressurization reservoir in depth, a precursor to magmatic intrusion and potential eruptions. Detecting these movements would enhance our understanding of the magmatic system and improve eruption forecasting. The InSAR data from the ISDeform/OI2 service typically consist of two-pass interferograms, which cannot detect inter-eruptive displacements due to their low amplitude (a few centimeters over months) and their susceptibility to atmospheric artifacts. ALOS-2 Spotlight data (L-band) interferograms maintain coherence not only over the arid summit of Piton de la Fournaise but also across its vegetated outer flanks, making them particularly well-suited for detecting long-wavelength displacements that are hard to capture with X-band or C-band data. We employed the AMSTer processing chain to compute the 3D displacement time series [2,3] using an exceptionally dense ALOS-2 dataset consisting of 1,626 scenes from 27 acquisition geometries, for 2021-2024. This period is ideal due to longer inter-eruptive intervals, clear GNSS-detected uplifts, and enables precise time series calculations, especially for the North-South component.

Our initial calculation attempt revealed that large-amplitude co-eruptive displacements could partially contaminate the time series, complicating the detection of the sought-after inter-eruptive displacements. Consequently, we are currently upgrading the processing chain to eliminate these co-eruptive displacements.

At the time of writing this abstract, the time series calculations are not yet fully complete, preventing us from confirming whether these calculations will allow to successfully detect the inter-eruptive displacements. Additionally, given the low amplitude of these displacements, we anticipate the need to correct for atmospheric delays recorded in the interferograms. F. Albino (personal communication) has shown that using ZTD derived from GNSS data can significantly enhance the signal-to-noise ratio of interferograms. This is one of the approaches we are considering as we continue this work.

Index Terms— InSAR, MSBAS Time series, Northern component, Inter-eruptive displacements.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

ALOS 2 images are distributed by JAXA. AMSTer is available: <https://github.com/AMSTerUsers>. MSBAS was developed by S. Samsonov and is available: <https://insar.ca/multidimensional-small-baseline-subset-msbas/>

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ACCES ET TRAITEMENTS DES DONNEES EN TERRE SOLIDE : LES SERVICES DU POLE FORMATERRE DANS LE PAYSAGE DES INFRASTRUCTURES DE RECHERCHE

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ABSTRACT

Dans le paysage national de la recherche, Data Terra est la e-Infrastructure de Recherche (e-IR) et le centre de référence thématique du domaine système Terre et environnement. Sa mission principale est de développer un dispositif global d'accès aux données et produits d'observation de la Terre et d'opérer une offre de services de haut niveau pour leur traitement et leur analyse combinée. Elle est constituée en cinq pôles de données et de services, Theia (surfaces continentales), Odatis (océans), Aeris (atmosphère), FormaTerre (Terre solide) et PNDB (biodiversité), qui développent une approche intégrée du système Terre en partant des spécificités des écosystèmes de données et de services (standards de diffusion de données et métadonnées, modèles de données, ressources terminologiques...) de chacun des domaines.

Au sein du projet Equipex+ Gaia Data, Data Terra construit, avec l'IR CLIMERI, une infrastructure numérique distribuée permettant de déployer et d'opérer une offre de services aux données de haut niveau (découverte, accès, traitement, modélisation, visualisation...). Data Terra collabore également avec un grand nombre de projets PEPR pour coordonner et rendreinteropérables leurs projets de plateformes de données et de services.

FormaTerre en tant que composante de la e-infrastructure Data Terra, s'articule avec les IR

productrices de données d'observation du domaine Terre Solide (Epos-France, RéGEF et EMSO-FR) et avec les différentes structures labellisées qui développent des services aux données (SNO ISDeform).

La structuration des pôles de données et de services se poursuit au niveau national avec la mise en œuvre des Centres de Données d'Observation et de Services (CDOS), sub-structures des pôles labellisés par l'INSU. A l'échelle européenne, FormaTerre est impliqué avec Epos-France dans la contribution à l'IR EPOS et avec Data Terra dans le projet FAIR-EASE et dans la construction d'un futur nœud thématique d'EOSC.

Durant cette intervention, il sera présenté comment FormaTerre, en tant que composante Terre solide de l'infrastructure de recherche Data Terra se positionne dans le paysage national et européen/international. Un focus sera également fait sur les services aux données que propose le pôle:

- pour la découverte et l'accès aux données, avec les travaux qui y sont associés sur les métadonnées et les ressources terminologiques,
 - pour le traitement de données (GDM-SAR, GDM-OPT...),
 - pour la visualisation,
- et d'autres services en construction.

CRUSTAL UPLIFT IN THE KERGUELEN ISLANDS FROM SENTINEL-1 INSAR: A CONSEQUENCE OF RECENT ICE MELTING?

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ABSTRACT

The Kerguelen Islands (49°S; 69°E), a volcanic archipelago in the southern Indian Ocean, have been significantly impacted by recent changes in climatic conditions. Since 1970, the surface of the Cook ice cap has retreated by 20%^[1].

Recent observations from Sentinel-1 InSAR measurements (2015-2021) reveal (i) active crustal uplift reaching up to 6 mm/yr near the ice cap and extending over 50 km and (ii) short-wavelength signals on the eastern part of the island, characterized by alternating positive and negative line-of-sight velocities. This study aims to understand geophysical processes driving present-day deformation rates in the main Kerguelen Island and explore their potential relationship with the ice melting history.

We first extract short-wavelength signals and identify a strong correlation with topographic slopes in the eastern part of the main Kerguelen Island. The deformation patterns and polarities are consistent with down-slope movements, likely driven by solifluction processes.

We then investigate the role of recent ice mass loss in the archipelago in driving observed deformation rates at long-wavelength. Ice mass loss is mainly concentrated in the Cook ice cap area and is well documented by differencing a succession of digital elevation models acquired via different remote sensing techniques since 2000.

Modelling of the solid Earth deformation associated with present-day ice melting using assumption of a fully elastic medium shows that it cannot entirely explain InSAR deformation rates, although the spatial extent and order of magnitudes of surface velocity are in reasonable agreement. Instead, deformation rates of a viscoelastic medium, including a 30-40 km elastic lithosphere overlying an upper mantle with viscosities ranging from $5 \times 10^{18} - 1 \times 10^{19}$ Pa.s, under 50 years of historical ice unloading of the Cook ice cap, yields a better agreement with recent InSAR observations. This result helps probing rheological properties of the Earth at previously unexplored timescales in the geological context of a hotspot characterized by residual volcanic activity.

Additionally, we investigate a potential volcanic contribution to the observed uplift rates by inverting the InSAR observations for a range of magmatic source scenarios, all predicting a very deep (> 35 km) magma reservoir beneath the archipelago. As such deep magma chambers are usually not detected by InSAR^[2], this result suggests that volcanic activity is unlikely to represent the primary driver of surface deformation in the Kerguelen Islands.

Thus, we favor the hypothesis of a solid Earth's viscoelastic response to recent ice unloading history to explain observed deformation rates today. Our results show that, in addition to the significant impact of climate change on glacier evolution in the Southern Ocean, surface deformation in subpolar regions, at short and long-wavelengths, is also likely driven by climatic variations. Overall, this study demonstrates that the Kerguelen Islands constitute a unique natural laboratory for studying coupling processes between the solid Earth and its fluid envelopes in the context of current climate variations.

Index Terms— InSAR, crustal uplift, rheology, DEM, glaciers evolution.

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TOOLS FOR THE VISUALISATION OF INSAR DATA IN THE CONTEXT OF FORMATERRE

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ABSTRACT

New spatial missions, like the Sentinel-1 radar imaging mission of the European program COPERNICUS, with a systematic acquisition strategy and open data policy, provide unprecedented access to massive SAR datasets. Based on these datasets large-scale InSAR processing chains (e.g. NSBAS chain) has been developed to generate networks of thousands of interferograms from which time-serie analyses produce spatio-temporal data cubes, with a typical size of 4000x6000 (spatial dimensions in pixels) x200 (typical number of images taken since the beginning of the mission).

Fluid, interactive visualization of such large, multidimensional datasets is non-trivial, and some specificities of InSAR (radar geometry, wrapped phase, relative measurement in space and in time...) call for new, dedicated visualization tools.

Beyond these requirements, scientists have expressed the need to be able to cross-analyse the InSAR data with other types of data (for example, soil moisture, meteorology, gnss, ...)

Many actions are currently developed to address these needs:

- On site visualization of data store locally with standalone tools
- Visualization of remote data using either locally available or online tools.

1. VISUALIZATION OF LOCALLY AVAILABLE DATA

The InSarViz project [1] addresses the visualization of locally available data. The project currently focuses on visualization of timeseries stored in datacube format.

It is a collaboration between geoscientists and computer scientists, aiming to produce an open-source, interactive tool to visualize timeseries of InSar data. The recent developments made on InSarViz during the past two years include, in particular, the possibility to easily localize the data using an OpenStreetMap background, a better handling of the reference, an improved visualisation of the data distributions (using comparison of the histograms computed on the global data distribution and the distribution at the current date), the possibility to load and stack different data using gdal vrt files. As the displacements measured by InSar are relative and not absolute, we also improved the ease of the comparison of behaviors between points and a reference region.

Figure 1 proposes a screen shot of InSarViz showing data on the region of Jalisco, Mexico computed by the FLATSIM project [2]. The timeseries was computed on the descending swath (orbit 12).

On the right hand side we can see the subsidence of the Sayula laguna with respect to a reference zone (yellow rectangle).

In the middle we can see two histograms, one of the whole data set (in blue) and one of current band (pink).

On the left hand side, the OpenStreetMap background eases the localization of the data. We can add a map over this data. In the case of Figure 1, we superimposed the Mean Velocity Map.

On the left hand side (bottom) we can see the cumulative displacement on the 2020-04-19 with respect to the first date. Finally, on the top of the left hand side we can see the different layers we are currently using. Each layer can be attached a transparency.

Once the visualization has been set up, we can save the project in order to save set up time.

2. VISUALIZATION OF REMOTE DATA

The second point is addressed by the Gaïa-Data project which aims to provide scientists with an environment enabling the joint analysis of different types of data. In this framework, many use cases have been designed, among which the *Ground-deformation* use case. The technology chosen by the Gaïa-Data project is based on Jupyter Notebooks. This allows the user to use a notebook-based visualization and to extend it to better fit its needs. This notebook is available via Gaïa-Data, and thus via an authentication via the FormaTerre portal.

2. FURTHER WORKS

During the congress we will propose a demonstration of both the insarviz tool and the notebook and will collect feedbacks from the community regarding further features implementations.

Index Terms— InSAR, data visualization.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The InsarViz project is supported by CNES, focused on SENTINEL1, and CNRS.

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CRUSTAL UPLIFT IN THE KERGUELEN ISLANDS FROM SENTINEL-1 INSAR: A CONSEQUENCE OF RECENT ICE MELTING?

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We first extract short-wavelength signals and identify a strong correlation with topographic slopes in the eastern part of the main Kerguelen Island. The deformation patterns and polarities are consistent with down-slope movements, likely driven by solifluction processes.

We then investigate the role of recent ice mass loss in the archipelago in driving observed deformation rates at long-wavelength. Ice mass loss is mainly concentrated in the Cook ice cap area and is well documented by differencing a succession of digital elevation models acquired via different remote sensing techniques since 2000.

Modelling of the solid Earth deformation associated with present-day ice melting using assumption of a fully elastic medium shows that it cannot entirely explain InSAR deformation rates, although the spatial extent and order of magnitudes of surface velocity are in reasonable agreement. Instead, deformation rates of a viscoelastic medium, including a 30-40 km elastic lithosphere overlying an upper mantle with viscosities ranging from $5 \times 10^{18} - 1 \times 10^{19}$ Pa.s, under 50 years of historical ice unloading of the Cook ice cap, yields a better agreement with recent InSAR observations. This result helps probing rheological properties of the Earth at previously unexplored timescales in the geological context of a hotspot characterized by residual volcanic activity.

Additionally, we investigate a potential volcanic contribution to the observed uplift rates by inverting the InSAR observations for a range of magmatic source scenarios, all predicting a very deep (> 35 km) magma reservoir beneath the archipelago. As such deep magma chambers are usually not detected by InSAR^[2], this result suggests that volcanic activity is unlikely to represent the primary driver of surface deformation in the Kerguelen Islands.

Thus, we favor the hypothesis of a solid Earth's viscoelastic response to recent ice unloading history to explain observed deformation rates today. Our results show that, in addition to the significant impact of climate change on glacier evolution in the Southern Ocean, surface deformation in subpolar regions, at short and long-wavelengths, is also likely driven by climatic variations. Overall, this study demonstrates that the Kerguelen Islands constitute a unique natural laboratory for studying coupling processes between the solid Earth and its fluid envelopes in the context of current climate variations.

Index Terms— InSAR, crustal uplift, rheology, DEM, glaciers evolution.

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EXPLORING AN UNSUPERVISED DATA MINING APPROACH TO EXTRACT ASEISMIC SLIP EVENTS ALONG THE IZMIT SECTION OF THE NORTH ANATOLIAN FAULT, BASED ON FLATSIM TIME SERIES

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The North Anatolian Fault (NAF) is known for hosting large earthquakes, but also continuous or transient aseismic slips. Sentinel-1 (S1) InSAR time series analyses revealed the occurrence of several transient aseismic slip events (or bursts of creep) since 2014 [1, 2] along different sections of the fault. More systematic detection and characterization of their spatio-temporal characteristics are essential to better understand their physical mechanisms and their potential impact on seismic hazard.

Here, we use S1 InSAR time series along the Izmit section of the NAF, automatically processed by the FLATSIM service [3], to test an unsupervised spatio-temporal data mining approach [4] (DFTS-P2MINER prototype available at <https://sites.google.com/view/dfts-p2miner>) to automatically detect in time, and locate in space, creep events.

The aim of this unsupervised process is to extract from the InSAR time series pixel evolutions/sub-evolutions, such that the pixels affected by a pixel evolution cover a minimum surface and are sufficiently connected to each other. A pixel evolution is a sequence of pixel states, where these states are discrete values encoding the amplitude and sign of the displacements in the satellite line of sight. The extracted evolutions are the patterns of interest and can be depicted on maps, where the spatial information is given by pixel positions while the temporal information is displayed using color palettes. In this study, we rely on two key parameters of this evolution mining approach to extract aseismic slip events. The first parameter is the minimum surface threshold that ensures that the evolutions reflected by the patterns cover a sufficient area. The second one is a connectivity threshold that guarantees the local spatial coherence of the patterns.

We first work on synthetic displacement time series of 25 images covering 261 x 195 pixels and containing one shallow

burst of creep superimposed with realistic, spatially correlated InSAR-type noise with characteristics similar to the one of real time series in the area. In the cumulated displacement maps, positive (resp. negative) values correspond to motion away from (resp. towards) the satellite. Each map at each time step is discretized using equal frequency bucketing in three levels. These levels represent relative surface displacements across and along the fault (1: strong motion towards satellite, 2: small motion considered as neutral, 3: strong motion away from the satellite).

We first show that a simple workflow allows to detect specific spatial patterns corresponding to the synthetic burst, as well as to pick the beginning and end of the transient event in time. We then apply the methodology to a real time series [5] with similar temporal length and pixel number. This series is composed of 25 cumulated displacement images (202 x 202 pixels) covering an area of about 17 km x 5 km of the Izmit section of the NAF, at the end of year 2019 including a known creep event [5]. The first results appear promising. Spatial patterns likely related to the 2019 burst are clearly identified on both sides of the fault. They are consistent with contours and signs of maximum cumulated displacement previously measured (Fig. 1). We also compare the temporal evolution of the relative displacement of pixels on both sides of the fault, selected near the fault and within the detected « burst spatial patterns », to that computed from a model prediction of the 2019 burst [5] (Fig. 2). This evolution does show the burst despite noise, at the location automatically detected by DFTS-P2MINER, with a creep step across fault consistent with the model.

Future steps will include, based on various sets of synthetic time series, an exploration of the limits of the detection method in terms of signal to noise ratio, which depends in particular on the depth, size and longitudinal extent of the burst events.

Figure 1. Colored patterns show displacement patterns with strong motion toward west south of the fault and strong motion toward east north of the fault, detected by DFTS-P2MINER, superimposed on cumulated displacement map from InSAR time series analysis from [5], corresponding to the 2019 creep burst. Colors encode dates and can be used to estimate the burst period.

Figure 2. In blue: Temporal evolution of the relative displacement of two pixels on both sides of the fault, selected near the fault and within the « burst spatial patterns » detected by DFTS-P2MINER. Red line shows the creep change modeled in [5].

Index Terms— InSAR, Data mining, Tectonic deformation, Spatio-temporal pattern, Satellite image time series.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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MODELLING MAGMA RECHARGE DYNAMICS DURING THE 2016 NEVADO DE CHILLAN ERUPTION

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ABSTRACT

The Nevados de Chillan (NdCVC) is a large composite stratovolcanic complex located in the Southern Andean Volcanic Zone, at the south of Chile (**Fig.1**). Its last eruption occurred over a six-year period beginning on January 8, 2016 and ending in January 2023. Following a period of three years during no deformation was observed, the volcano exhibited phreatic and phreatomagmatic activity. This was followed in June 2019 by an uplift episode, which marked the onset of the magmatic phase. In this study, we analyze InSAR time series and daily GNSS time series from 2015 to early 2022, highlighting the wide range of ground surface displacements observed during the eruption. In-depth analysis of these displacements in conjunction with recent petrological and geochemical finding, suggest the possibility of a recharge mechanism involving a double-reservoir model to account for the observed geodetic activity. We develop an analytical model of dynamic magma flow coupled with a boundary element method. This consists of a shallow elongated source located at 5.8 km depth below the volcanic edifice connected by an incompressible magma-filled hydraulic pipe to a deeper sill like source centered at 15 km depth. We propose that the activation of the system started with a small magma intrusion of one month of duration, which was sufficient to overheat the hydrothermal system and re-mobilize magma in the shallow chamber, thus explaining the lack of deformation during the phreatic phase and the slight subsidence observed during the phreato-magmatic stage. Subsequently, a new and larger magma intrusion occurred in June 2019, which can be identified as the origin of the observed uplift period. This intrusion continued for the following three years of the eruption, exhibiting an exponential decay pattern. Our model indicates that this intrusion was triggered by magma coming from the crust-mantle boundary to the deep reservoir at constant rate of $0.0156 \text{ km}^3 \cdot \text{y}^{-1}$ from June 2019 to Jan. 2022, with small changes to this rate that would explain the small fluctuations observed during this uplift episode. Our results support the hypothesis that the conduit dominated magma transfer between the two reservoirs exerts control over the dynamics of the system. The hypothesis that a deep mafic reservoir recharging an evolved shallow reservoir can explain the mafic enclaves found in the dacites in the latter eruption

is therefore proposed. This hypothesis offers a physical model to jointly explain the observations obtained from petrology, geochemistry and geophysics, thus bridging the disciplines.

Figure 1: Reference map of the study area in southern Chile correspond to the white box in the top right-hand inset map. The green circles and their associated name show the location of the five GNSS stations.

1. GNSS and InSAR time series

Ground deformation at NdCVC is characterized from daily solutions at five continuous GNSS stations installed by the Observatorio Volcanológico de los Andes del Sur (OVDAS) covering a period of six years from January 2016 to early 2022. PCAIM analysis [1] suggests that the first component of the decomposition explains 95 % of the total variance in the GNSS data. While this indicates that the displacements are mostly explained by the first component, there are systematic residuals that are significant. The first component perfectly reflects the temporal evolution of the vertical displacement recorded at the four stations near the summit of the volcano, highlighting the strong spatio-temporal correlation observed between the signals recorded by these stations. However, it does not fully capture the temporal pattern of the vertical displacement observed at the station TRAN station during the uplift period.

SAR imagery at NdCVC was acquired by two satellite missions: C-band Interferometric Wide Swath mode images

from the European Space Agency (ESA) Sentinel-1A/B and L-band Stripmap mode images from ALOS-2 operated by the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA). We assessed the consistency between GNSS and InSAR at geodetic monitoring sites in the study area. Both times series are in good agreement with the LOS-projected GNSS measurements with a rms of 0.4 and 0.7 cm for ALOS-2 and Sentinel-1 data, respectively.

2. Modeling approach

Reverso et al. [2] proposed an analytical model describing the dynamics between two magma reservoirs at different depths connected by an incompressible-magma-filled hydraulic pipe. In this study, we derive an analytical solution based on a similar mass balance of the system, but our model allows for flexibility in the geometry of both reservoirs and accounts for the topography in the zone [3] (Fig 2).

Figure 2. Representative model of the architecture deduced below NdCVC from the most recent petrological study in the area [4]

3. Discussion and Conclusion

The two-reservoir dynamical model we have developed for this study can well reproduce the spatial and temporal evolution of the uplift episode observed from July 2019 onwards. We estimate the volume change of this shallow reservoir was $26 \times 10^6 \text{m}^3$, whereas this deep source ranges from -5.8 to $12 \times 10^6 \text{m}^3$. Assuming a constant basal flow (Q_{in}) the model well reproduces the long temporal behavior associated to an exponential decay over the three years of the magmatic phase of the eruption (Fig. 4).

Accounting for an Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) approach [5] to assess variable basal flow ($Q_{in}(t)$) we find that variations of the magma supply rate around its mean value of $0.0156 \text{ km}^3 \cdot \text{y}^{-1}$ can explain the subtle variation of vertical displacements observed at the GNSS stations located on the summit of the volcano and at TRAN station (Fig.3).

The uplift episode observed can be 97% explained by the change in volume of a shallow reservoir at 5.8 km of depth, whereas the change in volume of a deeper chamber at 15 km depth accounts for the remaining 3%. These displacements triggered by volume changes in the deeper reservoir were not detected by InSAR because they contribute less than 1 cm and were only detected by the continuous GNSS network at NdCVC. Therefore, this GNSS network was indispensable to

detect the subtle signal that enabled us to implement the recharge mechanism proposed associated to the double-chamber model in agreement with recent petrological results.

Figure 3. Evolution of the volume change in the shallow and the deep reservoir considering a constant or a variable basal flow.

Index Terms— InSAR, GNSS, Volcano, Chile

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Capella Space SAR amplitude imagery and LiDAR DEM: an unconventional recipe to map lava flows and measure volcanic deformation

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ABSTRACT

Active volcanoes have complex behaviors and may quickly transition from a state of quiescence to a period of unrest or eruption. The amount of time an active volcano remains in one of these states is highly variable, which makes it very tricky to forecast not only the onset of an eruption but also how long it will last. For instance, the Campi Flegrei volcanic field, in Italy, has experienced uplift and seismicity during the past two decades without erupting. On the other hand, the last eruption of Soufrière Hills, in Montserrat, lasted 18 years from 1995 to 2013, after ~400 years of quiescence.

Such a diversity of time-scales requires a range of temporal resolution of observations for volcano monitoring depending on the process at hand. In the long-term – months to decades before eruptions –, the processes of interest are associated with the storage of magma at depth and its transport toward the surface. The state of the volcano can be evaluated indirectly by measuring ground deformation, seismicity or degassing from the surface. In the short-term – days to hours during an eruption –, direct observations collected by ground instrumentation and operators become crucial to produce hazard maps and track in real-time the evolution of the ongoing eruption. However, access to these critical data may be difficult due to challenging conditions prevailing on most volcanoes, exacerbated by the danger of going physically on a volcano during the course of an eruption.

In this context, satellite imagery could provide a complementary approach for volcano monitoring. Most methods for detecting changes on a volcano rely on the postulate that a reference image is available prior to the event of interest, which is not always the case at very high spatial resolution due to limited archive data. Here, we present a novel method that combines (i) high-resolution (50 cm) SAR amplitude images from the Capella Space constellation collected during or after an eruption, and (ii) high-resolution (1 m) LiDAR Digital Elevation Models (DEM) acquired years before the eruption. Using a dataset acquired at Piton de la Fournaise, La Réunion island, we demonstrate the capability of the method for (1) mapping the extent of lava flows during eruptions and (2) measuring long-term volcanic deformation.

1. Mapping lava flows' growth in near-real time

Mapping lava flows on a daily basis during effusive eruptions is key to estimate the lava discharge rate and constrain numerical simulations used to identify paths that the lava is likely to follow. At Piton de la Fournaise, tracking lava flows in near-real time is, for now, only feasible in favorable conditions by combining remote sensing data of different types [Chevrel et al., 2023]: optical and near infrared imagery (~1 to 10 m resolution), thermal imagery (~100 m to 1 km resolution), or InSAR coherence (~1 to 10 m resolution). In adverse conditions, meteorological clouds and volcanic plumes prevent the use of optical imagery and bias thermal measurements. Besides, thermal imagery has a resolution of ~100 m to 1 km, which is too coarse to map lava flows precisely. Only SAR can reliably deliver high-resolution images during day and night, no matter the weather conditions. The main issue with InSAR coherence mapping is that InSAR necessitates having two SAR images coming from the same sensor with the same acquisition geometry, which prevents having revisit times shorter than several days.

To achieve daily-resolved mapping of the lava flows, we take advantage of the Capella Space constellation, which is able to deliver very high-resolution SAR images (50 cm) within a few hours after tasking. To reach this sub-daily temporal resolution, it is necessary to combine images collected by several satellites of the constellation evolving on different orbits, and observing the ground with variable squint and elevation angles. Therefore, classical change detection techniques do not work.

Our method allows for mapping lava flows from a single SAR amplitude image and a LiDAR DEM of the volcano. The DEM is used for creating a synthetic image with the same geometry as the real SAR image, based on the *radiometric terrain correction* algorithm of Small (2011). Then, we perform the cross-correlation of the synthetic image and the real SAR image, using the MicMac software [Rupnik et al., 2017]. The correlation score is low (<0.1) in places where the surface changed between the date of acquisition of the DEM and the date of acquisition of the SAR image, while it is high (>0.6) elsewhere. At Piton de la Fournaise, surface changes inside the Enclos Fouqué caldera are almost exclusively due to lava flows. Therefore, using 3 successive Capella Space SAR images acquired over Piton de la Fournaise

Figure 1 - (a) Correlation score mapping the lava flows that formed at Piton de la Fournaise between 2018 and 2022. (b) Evolution of the shape of the lava flow that formed during the September-October 2022 eruption.

during an eruption (on October 1st, 2nd and 4th 2022), we managed to track the change of shape of the lava flow through time (Figure 1b). We also used a set of 6 different images of Piton de la Fournaise (acquired in 2021 and 2022) for mapping the lava flows that formed between 2018 (acquisition of the IGN LiDAR DEM) and 2022 (Figure 1a).

2. Measuring long-term volcanic deformation

The cross-correlation not only gives a correlation score for each pixel of the SAR image relative to the synthetic image, but also a shift along the rows and columns of the image. Therefore, with a single SAR amplitude image, our method allows for measuring the projection onto the slant range and azimuth directions of the 3D ground displacement that occurred between the date of acquisition of the LiDAR DEM and the date of acquisition of the SAR image. With at least two SAR images of different viewing geometries it is possible to retrieve the 3D displacement field in their overlapping area. Considering a 1 m resolution LiDAR DEM and Capella Space SAR images with a resolution of 50 cm, we can only detect ground displacements $\gtrsim 10$ cm, while InSAR can go down to displacements $\lesssim 1$ cm. However, unlike InSAR or classical SAR image correlation, our method does not require that a reference image (i.e. acquired prior to the deformation event) is available.

From the 6 Capella Space SAR images acquired over Piton de la Fournaise in 2021 and 2022, we were able to measure the long-term deformation of the volcanic edifice between 2009 (acquisition of the SHOM-IGN LiDAR DEM) and 2021-2022. GNSS measurements of the permanent stations and campaigns of the Piton de la

Fournaise observatory, along with a corner reflector, were used for validating our results.

Index Terms — SAR amplitude imagery, DEM, image correlation, lava flows, volcanic deformation

3. Acknowledgements

The SAR images are distributed by the Capella Space company. The 2009 LiDAR DEM was produced by the SHOM and the IGN. The 2018 LiDAR DEM was produced by the IGN. The processing of the SAR images and the production of the synthetic images is done with the EOS-SAR processing chain developed by KAYRROS. The image correlation is done with the MicMac software and run on the S-CAPAD/DANTE platform of IPGP.

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HOW WELL CAN DISPLACEMENT BE RESOLVED CLOSE TO EARTHQUAKE SURFACE RUPTURES USING OPTICAL IMAGE CORRELATION? A CASE STUDY FROM THE 2019 RIDGECREST EARTHQUAKE

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ABSTRACT

The study of natural hazards (e.g., earthquakes, landslides, volcanoes) relies on precise estimation of ground displacement. When combined with very high resolution satellite images, optical image correlation (OIC) techniques have shown great utility in constraining near-field ground displacements for large surface rupturing earthquakes, with a high degree of spatial detail and precision. Such measurements provide valuable constraints for the mechanics of fault rupture, and the generation of strong ground motions in large shallow earthquakes.

OIC has several advantages over other geodetic or field-based methods for constraining earthquake surface deformation. (1) OIC is generally quite robust to image noise, and thus can yield meaningful displacement data from different kinds of imagery (e.g. aerial vs satellite), which may also be separated by relatively long time-periods [1]. (2) OIC does not readily decorrelate close to the fault rupture (as is the case for InSAR), thus providing rich information in the near-field region (and revealing properties related to the shallow reaches of the fault). (3) OIC has subpixel resolution, meaning that it is possible to retrieve very small displacements (cm-scale) [2]. (4) OIC provides very dense measurements of ground displacement, with high spatial detail, that would be challenging to replicate with field measurements. (5) OIC can detect displacements from subtle features on the ground, which would otherwise be very challenging to identify in the field. This may include long-wavelength distributed displacement signals. Consequently, OIC has been widely used to characterize the near-field displacement for several recent surface-rupturing earthquakes. OIC-derived fault

displacements often exceed field-derived measurements, which is often attributed to the inability of field measurements to resolve smaller distributed deformations occurring away from the primary fault rupture (off-fault deformation).

Current approaches have examined near-field deformation in the context of strain, which is derived from gradients in the displacement data. Strains above ~0.5% are assumed to represent permanent inelastic deformation, while below this threshold, the deformation can be supported elastically and thus does not imply permanent (i.e. non-recoverable) deformation. If some proportion of slip is accommodated on the primary fault plane (on-fault deformation), while some proportion is accommodated off-fault, as permanent inelastic deformation, then OIC displacement data may be used to infer the true fault zone width, i.e. the zone around earthquake ruptures over which both on-fault and off-fault inelastic deformation is occurring.

Recent studies on the 2019 Ridgecrest earthquake have used different high resolution optical datasets (Pleiades, SPOT6/7, and WorldView) ([4], [5], [6]), along with different correlation approaches (Ampcor, COSI-Corr, MicMac) to investigate the near-field displacement characteristics of the surface rupture, leading to different interpretations of fault zone width, and the extent of off-fault deformation. However, it is necessary to understand the impact that different optical correlation techniques may have on the magnitude and expression of near-field deformation. This will help to ensure robust interpretations of near-field displacement, which in turn will inform our understanding of the physics of earthquake slip. (Similar

endeavors have been initiated, e.g. the "Optical Image Correlation Challenge" (OIC2024), to address these issues in a broader geodetic context).

In addition to different correlation approaches, one must also consider the impact of different optical datasets, and how these may influence the resulting displacement maps. Thus, the primary objective of this study is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of various correlation algorithms commonly used to study earthquakes (Cosi-Corr, Mic-Mac, Ampcor, Ames Stereo Pipeline, along with new CNN-based approaches [3]), coupled with different datasets acquired on different dates, with different incidence angles, and at different resolutions. We focus on how the displacement values are impacted by the smoothing effects of the correlation process, and how one may artificially smooth over very discrete fault offsets, thus artificially creating apparent off-fault deformation. Finally, we explore how these various parameters manifest in the final strain maps, from which we infer various along-strike variations in fault properties (e.g., fault zone width), used to inform our mechanical understanding of fault rupture.

We use the 2019 Mw 6.4 and 7.1 Ridgecrest earthquakes as a case study. Several authors ([4], [5], [6], [7]) have already studied the area using different datasets and correlators.

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We supplement existing measurements with a new optical dataset, ADS-80 aerial imagery (40 cm), which provides the best quality optical dataset spanning the Ridgecrest earthquake. We also make use of a new CNN-based correlation approach, which gives reduced displacement bias close to fault discontinuities. Thus, we aim to highlight the extent to which we can use OIC to constrain near-fault characteristics (Fig. 1), such as fault zone widths, damage zones properties, and the partitioning of slip between the primary fault plane and off-fault region. At what level do all the measurements agree, and when do they start to differ, and why? Our study will provide a helpful framework for the correct interpretation of OIC data in the context of near-field studies of fault mechanics.

Fig 1. (a) Displacement maps of the Ridgecrest fault system along the east-west component, derived from two image sets. (b) The black boxes in panel (a) indicate fault-aligned profiles, which have been superimposed for comparison.

USING SENTINEL-1 TIMESERIES FOR LARGE-SCALE TECTONIC APPLICATIONS IN CENTRAL ANDES

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In order to study the large-scale deformation in Central Andes (7–26°S), we use InSAR Sentinel-1 acquisitions, processed in the frame of the FLATSIM-Andes project^{1,2,3,4}. In this project supported by CNES as part of the ForM@Ter Solid Earth data and service center, 17,000 interferograms have been computed over twelve ascending and descending tracks and inverted into timeseries on the 2015-2021 period. These InSAR data are complementary to the GNSS data, with a higher spatial resolution in exchange for a lower temporal resolution, allowing to better define the contours of the asperities or the maximum locking depth.

We modelled the effects of non-tectonic processes such as solid earth tides (SET), ocean tide loading (OTL), and ionospheric electronic content (TEC) on the phase ramps, in order to measure ground deformation in a stable reference frame constrained by a dense GNSS network, allowing vertical and horizontal decomposition. SET and OTL displacements show strong correlation with phase-ramps. Large-scale global IGS-TEC model show good correlation on ascending tracks, that are more affected by ionospheric dispersion because of their acquisition time. A curvature in time of the range phase-ramps on ascending tracks is also observed, correlating well with the TEC evolution and solar activity.

Using these corrected and calibrated InSAR and GNSS datasets, we will present a range of telluric hazards that have affected the Central Andes on the 2015-2021 period and associated with long and short wavelengths of deformation. This includes large crustal and subduction earthquakes, crustal active faults identification, and volcanic inflations. In addition, we are interested in performing joint inversion of InSAR and GNSS datasets in order to refine the interseismic coupling distribution in the area and to update the maximum magnitude assessment.

Figure 1. FLATSIM Sentinel-1 InSAR mean velocity map in the line-of-sight, for seven descending orbits over Central Andes, on the 2015-2021 period. Several features are observed: coseismic displacement, postseismic displacement from large subduction earthquakes, volcanic inflation, salt lakes...

Index Terms— InSAR, Sentinel-1, FLATSIM, tectonic, crustal faults

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The FLATSIM (ForM@Ter Large-scale multi-Temporal Sentinel-1 InterferoMetry) service is developed as part of the ForM@Ter Solid Earth data and services center and operated by CNES³. It allows systematic processing of interferograms from Sentinel-1 data, as well as displacement time series, over large geographic areas. It is based on the InSAR « New Small temporal and spatial BASelines » processing chain NSBAS^{1,2}.

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DYNAMIC TRIGGERING OF MUD VOLCANOES AND ASEISMIC SLIP IN THE FLUID-RICH WEST CASPIAN REGION BY THE 2023 KAHRAMANMARAŞ EARTHQUAKES: A JOINT GEODETIC AND SEISMIC ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The influence of major seismic events on triggering magmatic or hydrothermal activity, as well as the initiation of significant seismic or slow-slip events over large distances (>500 km), is predominantly attributed to seismic surface waves disturbing fluid reservoirs or altering the frictional characteristics of fault interfaces.

Through the analysis of seismic and geodetic data (InSAR and GNSS), we document a large aseismic deformation signal in the Kura basin between the Lesser and the Greater Caucasus in Eastern Azerbaijan, at the diffuse boundary of the convergent Eurasia and Arabian plates. The Kura basin is characterized by a large hydrocarbon field and the regular activity of numerous mud volcanoes. This signal is consistent with the activity of the 170 km-long West Caspian Fault (WCF) and six secondary faults (<70 km in length). Surface displacement fields derived from four tracks of InSAR data constrain the aseismic slip to the period between February 4 and 9, 2023. To better constrain the timing of the deformation and estimate the seismic deformation, we analyzed seismic signals from a single station located at 2 km from the WCF fault. Only 58 high-frequency local events with very low amplitude (estimated magnitude below 3.2) could have been located at the vicinity of the fault at a depth ranging from 10 to 20 km. These events were coeval with the arrival of surface waves of

the February 2023 M7.8 and M7.6 the Kahramanmaraş earthquakes, in Eastern Türkiye, located at a distance of 1000 km from the WCF fault. SAR interferometric and coherence maps revealed eruptions at 56 mud volcanoes, with 22 of them associated with local deformation pattern at the same time with the aseismic slip, suggesting a fluid-mediated dynamic triggering mechanism.

The Inversion of the InSAR displacement fields reveals a complex interaction of shallow and deep source of deformation. We show that the surface wave have perturbed a shallow system of gas/fluids in the Kura basin, with the opening of a horizontal sill at 3 to 4 km of depth and of vertical fissures above it, which is consistent with the flow of mud, gas and hydrocarbon observed at the time of the event. At larger depth, the deformation can be explained by the mainly right-lateral strike-slip motion on the subvertical WCF and the secondary faults. The absence of seismic energy radiated from the fault friction and the other deformation sources at depth makes this event as one of the major crustal aseismic transient slips in a continental collision. Notably, the southern portion of the WCF exhibited the largest displacement where no instrumental and historical seismic activity has been documented up to now.

To further explore the behavior of the WCF and its associated mud volcanoes, we conducted a time-series analysis using descending track 6 Sentinel-1 SAR images from 2016-2023. This

analysis identified continuous fault creep, supported by GNSS time-series data, as well as simultaneous eruptions of more than 20 mud volcanoes between 7-13th November 2017. These eruptions were likely triggered by a regional 11 November, 2017 Mw 7.3 Darbandikhan, Zagros belt earthquake, with the lack of significant surface displacement along the WCF system.

Despite the observed gradual and transient episodes of creeping on the WCF in the Kura Basin, its potential for large seismic events remains uncertain, as it is unclear whether this behavior significantly reduces its slip budget. The lack of seismicity, coupled with complex interactions with regional structures and abundant crustal fluids, highlights the need for further studies into its seismic hazard.

Figure 1. (a) Line-of-sight displacement field from the unwrapped interferogram computed using SAR images acquired between 28 January and 9 February 2023, along descending track 6. Yellow and black triangles represent activated and dormant mud volcanoes during the aseismic slip event, respectively. Black lines indicate fault traces mapped using SAR interferometric and coherence data. (b) Coherence map of the area highlighted in (a) by the blue box, showing loss of coherence at volcanoes and faults. Red triangles indicate activated mud volcanoes, while black triangles represent dormant ones.

STUDY OF ACTIVE COHERENT LANDSLIDES IN LEBANON USING REMOTE-SENSING TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Landslides are among the deadliest and most damaging natural hazards worldwide, particularly in mountainous regions with active tectonics and large-magnitude earthquakes, such as Lebanon. Lebanon's high seismic activity, rugged topography, frequent torrential rainfall, and rapid population growth increase the vulnerability of its mountains to landslides. Despite the high risk, few studies have focused on landslide detection and their causative factors.

To address the gap in landslide understanding in Lebanon, this work aims to assess the present-day landslide hazard in the country by mapping active coherent landslides at a national scale, investigating their causative factors, and monitoring them. To achieve these goals, we employed two main remote-sensing methods: (1) image correlation techniques (Cosi-Corr ^[1] and Mic-Mac ^[2]) using multiple optical data (Sentinel-2, LandSAT-8, SPOT4-5-6-7, QuickBird) acquired between 2000 and 2018, and (2) SAR interferometry (InSAR) and time-series inversion over six years (2016-2021) using open-access Sentinel-1 data. This study uses the time-series products processed by the FLATSIM ^[3] service within the framework of the Levant project using the New Small Baseline Subset (NSBAS) software ^[4]. The same methodology, employing the NSBAS processing chain, was used to process an area around the capital Beirut, at higher resolution, with more specific parameters for landslide investigation for comparison purposes.

From the investigation of the displacement fields, we detected 125 coherent landslides ranging in size from 2×10^4

to 4×10^6 m², moving at 2 to 13 mm/year. Notably, no landslides larger than 10^3 m² moving faster than 15 cm/year were detected. Almost all detected landslides are located in the Mount-Lebanon mountain range, with 86% on its western flank. The spatial distribution of these landslides indicates that lithology plays a crucial role, as nearly all landslides occur in Lower Cretaceous sandstone and clay-limestone formations. Furthermore, time-series analysis conducted over the six-year monitoring period using InSAR reveals variations in activity, including linear and seasonal displacement patterns, and provides insights into the influence of precipitation and microseismicity on landslides in Lebanon. These results highlight the limitations of the applied methods in Lebanon's challenging environment and suggest potential approaches for improving landslide monitoring in similar settings. They also provide insight into the advantages and limitations of FLATSIM products for detecting active coherent landslides in such environments.

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EL PILAR FAULT ASEISMIC BEHAVIOR IN VENEZUELA

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ABSTRACT

Aseismic slip faults are observed all over the world [1,2,3]. Aseismic slip is common during the aftershock period, but is less common during the interseismic period. This phenomenon can be observed along subduction-type plate boundaries, but more also along crustal faults [i.e. 4,5,6,7]. These slips are important to observe and understand, as they not only release some of the accumulated energy, but can also influence the nucleation of earthquakes [8,2]. Their observations seem to indicate that these interseismic slips have spatial and temporal variations, but it is still difficult to understand. Explanations may be lithological, geometrical, hydrological or dynamic, and have been discussed and studied analogically [i.e. 3]. Most of the observations that fuel these discussions are those of two plate boundaries, the San Andreas Fault and the North Anatolian Fault [1,6,7]. Here, we take up another plate boundary associated with the El Pilar Fault in the south Caribbean margin that also shows spatio-temporal creeping behavior [9].

The El Pilar Fault (Venezuela) is the plate boundary between the South American and Caribbean plates. This dextral fault accommodates 2cm/yr of relative movement between the plates. In 1997, an earthquake of magnitude M_s 6.8 occurred along this fault not far from the town of Cariaco. Since this event, it has been studied notably by GPS field campaigns (2003, 2005, and 2013) [10,11,12,13] and with the InSAR (Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar) technique between 2007 and 2011 from 18 ALOS-1 (Advanced Land Observing Satellite) images [9]. These studies have shown that since this earthquake, creep occurred along the fault segment as an afterslip. The creep continued, evolving into a time-fluctuating interseismic creep. Indeed, observations show spatial variations along the fault. Slip along the western part of the fault is of the order of 25.3 ± 9.4 mm/yr while on the eastern part, the rate is of the order of 13.4 ± 6.9 mm/yr [9]. In addition, InSAR observations showed an acceleration of the creep between January 2009 and January 2010, followed by a slowdown. Since those studies, we are wondering if the creep is still occurring or it decreased completely.

We have extended InSAR observations at the El Pilar fault between January 1, 2020 and September 16, 2023, using Sentinel-1A images. Although the wavelength is less favorable than that of L-band satellites, the repetition cycle of Sentinel-1 images provides high temporal resolution. In fact, a greater number of images are available (sometimes every 12 days). We were thus able to use the time series of 167 images from the A062 ascending track.

The processing chain used to process Sentinel-1A data is NSBAS (New Small BASeline Subset method) [14,15]. We focused on the iw2 sub-swath located above the fault at the level of the towns of Cariaco, Casanay and Pantoño. 559 interferograms with small perpendicular (<200m) and temporal baselines (between 12 days and 6 months) were calculated between January 1, 2020 and September 16, 2023. The DEM (Digital Elevation Model) used for the topographic correction is the NASADEM, with a resolution of 30m. The ERA5 model was applied to the interferograms to perform atmospheric corrections and remove noise [16,17]. Orbital and spectral diversity corrections were also applied [14]. Time series were obtained after pixel inversion [18,19]. However, not all interferograms were used. Indeed, many interferograms had too small portion of unwrapping (<4%). As a result, only 259 interferograms were used. Then, we extracted linear displacement velocities (LOS) from the resulting times series. We were only able to get a Time Series over the town of Cariaco. We can observe the fault here for some fifteen kilometers.

We calculated an average slip velocity for the dextral El Pilar fault at this location of around 15-20 mm/year between 2020 and 2023. Indeed, this velocity is similar to previous results obtained in earlier studies [9]. Thus, we were able to highlight temporal variations between 2020 and 2023 with an acceleration between August 2021 and September 2022 on InsarViz [20]. This preliminary study shows thus that the creep has continued since 1998, during probably 25 yrs, accommodating a large proportion of the deformation between the Caribbean and South American plates.

Index Terms— InSAR, El Pilar fault, Sentinel-1.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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Further reanalysis was performed on GRICAD computing environment from the University Grenoble Alpes.

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DEFORMATION AT TROPICAL COLOMBIAN STRATOVOLCANOES REVEALED BY ALOS-2 DATA INTERFEROMETRY

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ABSTRACT

The analysis of deformation at tropical stratovolcanoes presents significant challenges due to dense vegetation cover, steep topography, and strong atmospheric changes. Nevado del Ruiz, Puracé and Galeras in Colombia are examples of this particular volcanic environment. While these volcanoes are monitored by the Servicio Geológico Colombiano (SGC) using ground-based sensors, achieving sufficient spatial resolution remains a significant challenge. To overcome this limitation, this study includes the analysis of ALOS-2/PALSAR images for the period 2014-2023 carried out with the software GMTSAR. We applied different tropospheric noise corrections and estimate their performance. As a result, we show precise maps of cumulative deformation at the volcano edifices and a preliminary time series analysis of the displacements. In the following sections, we present the Colombian volcanism, then we describe the data and methods and finally, we show the preliminary results and discuss future perspectives.

1. COLOMBIAN STRATOVOLCANOES

Quaternary volcanism in Colombia is driven primarily by the subduction of the Nazca plate (NZ) below the North Andean Block (NAB). It is characterized by high conical volcano edifices (>4000 masl) with steep topographic gradients and snow-capped summits (Fig. 1). Due to their tropical location, these volcanoes are impacted by strong climate variations, leading to dense vegetation.

According to the Volcanica report [1], Nevado del Ruiz, Puracé and Galeras are among the most active volcanoes in Colombia with a long record of eruptions. The eruptions of Puracé in 1949, El Ruiz in 1985, and Galeras in 1993, remain among the deadliest disasters in the country. Currently, their activity is monitored through various observations from ground-based sensors managed by the SGC's volcanological observatories. Ground deformation — measured by GPS and tiltmeters — is an important variable

as it relates to the storage or the movement of fluids inside magmatic or hydrothermal reservoirs that might be linked to potential eruptions. Nevertheless, the discrete nature of the data and disturbances of the signal due to tropospheric artifacts limit the accuracy of deformation models.

By implementing the analysis of ALOS-2 data we intend to address previous limitations obtaining accurate cumulative deformation maps. These products will be used as inputs for models that contribute to a better characterization of the magmatic sources.

2. DATA AND METHODS

We analyzed a total of 100 ALOS-2/PALSAR stripmap images (L-band, 24.6 cm) between 2014 and 2023 in ascending and descending orbits. This dataset has important advantages in dense vegetated regions due to the longer wavelength, resulting in coherent interferometric pairs over longer periods in comparison with shorter wavelength missions (X-band or C-band). The quality of the retrieved information is essential to extract accurate deformation patterns on the volcano's surface.

Phase delays on the interferograms due to temperature/pressure and water vapor changes can be decomposed in topography-correlated and turbulent noise [2]. The magnitude of tropospheric noise can mask real deformation signals or be misinterpreted as such [3]. These effects can be large considering mainly the strong variations of water vapor in tropical volcanoes. As a way to reduce the tropospheric artifacts, we first applied empirical corrections by evaluating a linear phase-elevation correlation between the interferogram and a Digital Elevation Model outside the targeted volcano. For comparison, we also applied weather-based corrections through GACOS products to account for both stratified and turbulent component [2]. Finally, we attempt to use available GNSS data at the volcanoes to create maps of Zenith Total Delay (ZTD) to remove residual noise when possible [4].

Fig. 1. Cumulative displacements maps of studied volcanoes: Nevado del Ruiz (north), Puracé (center) and Galeras (south). ALOS-2 time series at the point denoted by the magenta square. Blue triangles and red dots represent values for ascending and descending tracks, respectively.

4. RESULTS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

We generated a total of 58 sequential interferograms corrected by the empirical method. The reduction in standard deviation ($\Delta\sigma$) was modest, with only 22% of ascending interferograms at Galeras and 33% of descending interferograms at El Ruiz showing a $\Delta\sigma$ above 10%. For Puracé, $\Delta\sigma$ is below 10 % for both orbital geometries. This suggests that the turbulent component of tropospheric noise might be dominant at the studied volcanoes. GACOS and ZTD_{GPS} can aid with this purpose and their performance will be evaluated separately. Fig.1 shows the time series of LOS changes after tropospheric correction based on the empirical method. Nevado del Ruiz (top) and Puracé (center) move towards the satellite in ascending and descending orbits. Galeras (bottom) moves away from the satellite in both tracks. Future work will focus on increasing the redundancy of the time series by computing more interferograms, carry out additional noise corrections, and modeling the deformation signals.

Index Terms— InSAR, volcano, ALOS-2, tropospheric noise

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SHEAR STRAIN EVOLUTION ACROSS THE EAST ANATOLIAN FAULT (EAF) RESPONSE TO THE 2020 MW6.8 ELAZIĞ AND 2023 MW7.8/MW7.6 KAHRAMANMARAŞ EARTHQUAKE SEQUENCE

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ABSTRACT

Shallow creep, a widespread phenomenon in the earthquake cycle, plays a significant role in understanding the behavior of faults and seismic hazards. However, it is still debated whether creep is an inherent fault behavior or a form of afterslip following large earthquakes. The recent 2020 Mw6.8 Elazığ, and 2023 Mw7.8/Mw7.6 Kahramanmaraş earthquake sequence, both occurred on or adjacent to creeping segments of the East Anatolian Fault Zone (EAFZ), provide a unique opportunity to investigate the relationship between shallow creep and earthquakes along the strike-slip fault. Here, we use the Sentinel-1 InSAR data to derive shear-strain rates and time-series shear strain along the EAF in three periods: before the 2020 earthquake, between the 2020 and 2023 earthquakes, and after the 2023 earthquake sequence from the InSAR phase gradient. The spatial distributions of the interseismic strain rates, the coseismic slip, and the postseismic strain rates document a tight connection between creep and coseismic slip on recent earthquakes, and also reveal different behaviors of shallow creep on the EAFZ with different pre-seismic states. The stress-driven afterslip model following the 2023 Kahramanmaraş earthquake sequence suggests that the frictional properties and seismic stress change likely control the creep, determining the rate and duration of the exponential decay of the afterslip and whether the long-term shallow slip exists during the interseismic period. Our results shed new light on understanding the mechanism of fault creep and its relationship to large earthquakes during the earthquake cycle.

INSAR TIME SERIES AND SVD DECOMPOSITION UNRAVEL A DYKE INTRUSION AT A TROPICAL VOLCANO, KARTHALA 2021-2022.

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ABSTRACT

With an eruption every 5 to 8 years, Karthala volcano (Grande Comore, Comoros), is the second most active volcano in the Indian Ocean, after Piton de la Fournaise (Réunion, France). Eruptions are mainly effusive, but sometimes also explosive and characterized by phreato-magmatic activity (Bachelery et al, 2016). Projections (ash and pumice), mudflows and lava flows threaten the populations of coastal villages and occasionally the capital, Moroni (55,000 inhabitants), as was the case in 1858. The volcano's last eruptive activity dates back to the 2007 eruption, when 25 cm of displacement was recorded by radar interferometry (Biggs et al., AGU, 2014).

After 14-years of quiescence, in November 2021, the Karthala Volcano Observatory detected the onset of a new seismic unrest, with a daily number of earthquakes reaching 250 events in mid-July 2022. This intense activity continued until mid-August, when the number of earthquakes dropped to a few events per day.

At the same time, displacements were recorded by radar interferometry by the Sentinel-1 satellite in ascending orbit and by a few Cosmo-SkyMed acquisitions in descending orbit.

InSAR time series from the Sentinel-1 (S1) and Cosmo-SkyMed (CSK) acquisitions were computed using the AMSTer processing chain (Derauw et al., 2020; d'Oreye et al., 2021), evidencing quasi symmetric flank displacements reaching a few cm towards each satellite. This displacement is consistent with a buried dike under low overpressure and a failed eruption.

RESULTS

First, the Sentinel-1 displacements spanning different time frames were mapped with classical DInSAR and 1-D Small Baseline Subset (SBAS; Bernardino et al., 2002) deformation time series (May 2017 – March 2023). These displacements were then inverted relying on 3D boundary elements combined with near neighborhood inversions (Fukushima et al., 2005). The sources determined for different cumulated periods were showing shapes and locations that were changing through time in a way inconsistent with a unique volcanic process.

To address this issue, these time series were analyzed with Singular Value Decompositions (SVD), and a seasonal atmospheric contribution was evidenced. A time series of six years was able to properly identify the seasonal oscillations. Only one SVD component had a signal consistent with the onset of seismicity, and this signal ended in September 2022. The other main component showed a periodic signal clearly associated with the oscillations of the Inter Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ).

From that filtered time series, differential deformation maps spanning the crisis were subsequently inverted. A source corresponding to an inflating sub-vertical dyke, parallel to the rift zone, was determined. However, with only the C-band S1 data available along the ascending orbit, the eastern flank of the volcano was poorly imaged and the inverted source had large confidence intervals and hence was not well constrained.

To overcome this, we processed a dozen images available X-band CSK images acquired along the descending orbit between October 2021 and August 2022. Because of high decorrelation due to the dense equatorial vegetation, no

classical DInSAR pairs allowed to map the deformation on the flanks. Nevertheless, a manual selection of the most favorable interferograms allowed to compute a SBAS time series that showed a deformation pattern along the eastern flank that was consistent with the deformation source estimated from the SVD-filtered S1 time series.

Although the CSK time series was too short to be filtered with a SVD decomposition, the agreement with the filtered S1 suggests that the eastern flank is less affected by the seasonal variations than the western flank, which is consistent with the orientation of the Grande Comore Island and its location in the Northern outlet of the Mozambique channel.

Finally inversions were conducted using the S1 time series filtered by SVD and the CSK time series covering close periods. The obtained model was close to the one obtained with only the S1 time series, filtered by SVD, but it was better constrained, with smaller confidence intervals. Using this model and the S1 filtered time series a progressive volume increase of the dyke was evidenced.

2. CONCLUSION

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Sentinel-1 data were obtained from the ESA Copernicus service. We thank Susanna Ebmeier and Michael Poland for helping us obtain CSK data on Karthala through the CEOS Volcano Demonstrator project.

AMSTer is freely available at https://github.com/AMSTerUsers/AMSTer_Distribution under CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 license. The deformation modelling and inversion tools are available for registered users at <http://www.opgc.fr/defvolc/>.

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Classical DInSAR Sentinel-1 images evidenced a dyke intrusion under the Karthala volcano concomitant with seismic swarms.

Only the combined analysis of times series of Sentinel-1 and Cosmo-SkyMed with an appropriate SVD filtering of the Sentinel-1 time series could isolate the deformation pattern from the seasonal artefacts.

The InSAR processing proved to be efficient despite the highly unfavorable environment for radar interferometry (equatorial vegetation, high relief, ITCZ oscillations, unbalanced SAR acquisitions).

Boundary elements combined with near neighborhood inversions (Fukushima et al., 2005) revealed a 6.5 km high vertical dyke. This dyke is 2 km long and parallel to the rift zone. Its top is located 1.7 km below the volcano's summit. The dyke is under low overpressure (1.8 MPa), which is consistent with a failed eruption.

Index Terms— InSAR, SBAS, SVD, , Karthala, Comores

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UNDERSTANDING THE DEFORMATION ASSOCIATED WITH THE DECEMBER 2020 MW 6.4 PETRINJA EARTHQUAKE IN CROATIA THROUGH TIME-SERIES INSAR IMAGES FROM THE FLATSIM SERVICE

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The catastrophic M_w 6.4 Petrinja earthquake, which shook northwest Croatia in December 2020, is regarded as the strongest recorded event in the region and was said to have exceeded previous expectations of the seismic hazard. Recent efforts and collaborations have been initiated after this event with the goal of better understanding the seismic hazards in the area [1, 2]. Insights on the earthquake dynamics have come so far from InSAR standard interferograms that suffer from the dense vegetation in the area, and atypic GNSS displacements measured on civilian networks of benchmarks [2,6]. Because of a relative lack of near-field instrumentation before and during the sequence (seismic and permanent GNSS networks in particular), the discussion is still ongoing about the amount and segmentation of the slip that occurred (one or two main asperities [5]), and of the faults involved. In particular, some author argue in favor of a conjugate fault that may have ruptured simultaneously [6], while simpler models seem to satisfy first order geodetic observations.

In this study, we take advantage of the FLATSIM service's massive processing of Sentinel-1 radar datasets [3] covering the area of the earthquake in the frame of the western Balkans project (<https://flatsim.cnes.fr/doi/>) to gain additional insights regarding the deformation associated with the Petrinja earthquake.

We first extract from the FLATSIM time series, based on a simple parametrization, maps of long-term velocities, seasonal deformation signals, as well as maps of coseismic displacements related to the Petrinja earthquake, taking also into account the 2020 Mw5.5 Zagreb earthquake. We compare our results to carefully unwrapped interferograms produced at 2looks resolution

and automatic LiCSAR processing. Because the first FLATSIM processing stops in June 2021, 6 months after the event, we estimate that the time-series is too short to assess for a potential postseismic signal.

We also show results from an implementation of phase gradient mapping [4] to the FLATSIM products to discuss the potential off-fault deformation associated with the Petrinja earthquake, adapting the approach to the 2-looks wrapped coseismic interferograms. Small-scale features are identified and discussed in comparison of the expected strain field in the rupture area.

Overall, beside not being designed to study in details moderate magnitude earthquakes, the FLATSIM products can provide meaningful insights while processed carefully.

Index Terms— InSAR, Satellite image time series, Earthquakes.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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THE 19 MAY 2023 TSUNAMI NEAR THE LOYALTY ISLANDS CAPTURED BY THE NEW SWOT SATELLITE

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ABSTRACT

During the last decades, trans-oceanic tsunamis have been captured by satellite altimeters on a few occasions. The largest event ever measured by an altimeter was the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami, captured by Jason-1, Topex/Poseidon, GFO and Envisat altimetry missions flying at that time [1, 2].

The new altimetry mission SWOT (Surface Water and Ocean Topography) developed by NASA and CNES, the US and French Space agency respectively, was launched in December 2022. SWOT embarks a novel instrument, a Ka-band Radar Interferometer (KaRIN), providing a 120 km wide swath Sea Level.

On 19 May 2023, SWOT was able to measure the tsunami generated by the M_w 7.7 earthquake, which occurred southeast of the Loyalty Islands (southwest Pacific Ocean) at 02:57:03 (UTC) [3]. SWOT flew over the region about 1 hour after the earthquake and captured the tsunami signature in several locations on its way from the earthquake source, and along a 120-km wide swath range. For the first time, a satellite has been able to map a tsunami propagating wavefield along this satellite swath (Figure 1, right).

The tsunami generation and propagation have been simulated using COMCOT model [4] using source parameters derived from seismic observations and empirical laws. Preliminary simulation results (Figure 1, left) show that a simple fault plane with a uniform coseismic slip allows to reproduce the regional coastal gauge and oceanic DART station records with a relatively good level of confidence, considering that the earthquake rupture was strongly not-double couple according to results obtained at seismological institutes.

An array of virtual gauges was designed to cover the satellite pathway, allowing to extract the dynamic representation of the tsunami wavefield corresponding to the satellite propagation time (i.e., the sea surface deformation is observed over a period of several minutes, instead of being static at a given time). Comparison between the SWOT sea surface measurement and the simulation result is satisfactory, showing a good agreement between the location of the first wave peaks (propagating toward the southwest and the northeast, respectively), their amplitude and phase.

The objective of this presentation is first to show this unprecedented observation, and then to analyze the level of consistency with simulations. The results allows to discuss the consequences in terms of seismic characterization, offshore tsunami monitoring, and a possible future application for operational warning purposes. The current paucity of offshore tsunami measurements, for instance on deep ocean pressure gauges, could therefore be interestingly complemented by such satellite missions in the future, at least for a better tsunami imaging [5]. The perspective of having it during the operational timeline of tsunami warning remains a perspective to discuss.

Index Terms— SWOT, altimetry, tsunami, numerical modeling, Loyalty Islands

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SWOT data have been obtained from repository from CNES. Bathymetry used to model tsunami wavefield is derived from Gebco, 2023.

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Figure 1. Numerical simulation of the tsunami (left) superposed on the SWOT satellite swath (right), for the 19 May 2023 earthquake and tsunami near the Loyalty Islands.

DYNAMIC EARTHQUAKE RUPTURE IN SERPENTINITE: IMPLICATIONS FROM THE MW7.6 ELBISTAN EARTHQUAKE DURING THE 2023 KAHRAMANMARAŞ, TÜRKIYE, EARTHQUAKE DOUBLET

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ABSTRACT

Serpentine is associated to aseismic deformation, also known as creep, along crustal faults, both in context of subduction or strike-slip faulting. However, laboratory experiments have shown that subjected to high slip rate, serpentine could transition from a velocity-strengthening behavior to dynamic weakening, enabling propagation of localized deformation, although this was never documented during an earthquake rupture.

Here, based on very high-resolution deformation measurements derived from optical image correlation along the 60 km-long eastern section of the Mw 7.6 Elbistan rupture, the second shock of the 2023 Kahramanmaraş earthquake doublet in Türkiye, we show that the earthquake rupture was able to propagate through a serpentine formation. Our measurements, however, indicate that the serpentine has a strong impact on the deformation pattern along the 20 km-long serpentine section. The distributed deformation accommodates on average 65% of the total deformation along that section, while in several places it can reach 100% of the co-seismic deformation, explaining why surface ruptures appear to be discontinuous or even absent along that section. Detailed analyzes of displacement profiles across the fault zone suggest that the co-seismic deformation might be partitioned within the S-C fabric of the serpentine unit, making it largely invisible in the field.

These observations demonstrate that although the deformation pattern is strongly affected by the serpentine, the serpentine would not impede propagation of an on-going earthquake rupture and thus does not constitute a definitive barrier for large seismic ruptures.

Index Terms — earthquake, Türkiye, Pléiades, SPOT6/7

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Figure 1. (A) Tectonic setting of the study region. (B) E-W horizontal displacement field, negative towards West, from pre- and post-event Sentinel-2 images (purple dashed frame) and SPOT6/7 and Pléiades images (blue dashed frame). Dark black lines represent coseismic ruptures mapped in this study, while red lines are mapped ruptures from [1]. (C) Extract of the E-W horizontal displacement field from pre-event SPOT6/7 images and post-event Pléiades images. The geometric complexities are labeled and abbreviated as GC, and the small complexities are labeled as SC.

EUROPEAN COASTAL SUBSIDENCE DERIVED FROM THE EUROPEAN GROUND MOTION SERVICE.

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ABSTRACT

We present an analysis of coastal subsidence in Europe based on the recent European Ground Motion Service (EGMS) product. First, we compare EGMS products with vertical land velocities from the permanent Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) network. Overall, we find a reasonable agreement with a correlation coefficient of 0.94 between the vertical velocities estimates from GNSS stations and the collocated EGMS pixels. However, we obtain systematically more negative values (of up to 1 mm/s) from EGMS estimates. These deviations could be related to the different reference frame used to calibrate EGMS (ETRF2000) and GNSS (IGS2014). Second, we combine coastal flood plain defined from the new Copernicus digital elevation model (25m resolution) and the EGMS estimates to identify subsiding coastal flood plains at the scale of Europe.

1. INTRODUCTION

While the understanding and modelling of relative sea level rise (SLR) due to ocean density and mass changes have greatly improved over the past few decades, SLR contributions due to vertical ground motions (VGMs) remain a major source of uncertainty. In particular, land subsidence can strongly exacerbate exposure to coastal flooding locally by amplifying relative sea level rise on the one hand, and lowering elevation of coastal flood plain on the other hand [1].

The aim of our study is to deliver for the first time a picture of the current subsidence state of low-lying coastal zones prone to marine flooding at the European scale. This is done owing to the vertical land motion dataset provided by the InSAR-based EGMS service [2] over the 2015-2021 period. While our analysis allows identifying already well-known coastal subsidence hot-spots, it also paves the way toward the identification of subsiding local scale coastal zones that have

been ignored so far and for which flooding risk may become a major concern.

2. METHODOLOGY

Our study relies on the later Ortho (Level 3) EGMS dataset and its first update covering the period 2015-2021. The dataset was obtained from the EGMS web portal (<https://egms.land.copernicus.eu/>), which provides 100 km x 100 km geotiff rasters of the vertical velocity best estimate over the period 2016-2021 accompanied with a tabular file (format .csv) providing, for each pixel of the raster file, the spatial coordinates, the root mean square error, the mean vertical and horizontal velocities, acceleration and seasonality, and their standard error, respectively, and the full displacement time series.

Temporally, the L3 data is provided with respect to a fixed date and extrapolated (where needed) to align time series from ascending and descending tracks, using the average velocity of each time series. Time series are then interpolated with a regular temporal sampling, excluding long data gaps, as well as the snow covered season where applicable. Spatially, data is derived directly from ascending and descending Level 2b products, thus referenced to the European Terrestrial Reference Frame 2000 (ETRF2000).

In this study, we relied on the mean vertical velocity for each pixel. To cover the entire European coastline, we downloaded 415 EGMS tiles of 100 km x 100 km spatial extent that we merged into one large pan-European raster file and clipped to the DIVA model coastal mask [3].

EGMS Ortho Level 3 vertical velocities are calibrated with respect to EUREF GNSS network in the European geodetic reference frame ETRF2000. In this reference frame, the Southern Europe appears to experience an average subsidence of between -0.5 and -1 mm/yr [4].

By comparing the EUREF GNSS network vertical velocity expressed in the international geodetic reference frame

(ITRF2014) and those expressed in the ETRF2000, we find that GNSS vertical velocities expressed in the ETRF2000 geodetic reference frame are systematically more negative than when expressed in the ITRF2014 and that this effect amplifies toward higher latitudes. Figure 1 illustrates this bias and proposes a correction.

3. RESULTS

Figure 2 summarizes our observations in terms of subsidence/upheaval of the coastal floodplains in Europe. It shows the proportion per country of coastal floodplain area that are, on average affected by subsidence or uplift. Our analysis allows identifying large hot spots of robust subsidence (average subsidence lower than -2 mm/yr) such as the north Adriatic coast in Italy or in Netherlands. Those subsidence areas are well known (e.g. [5]). Nonetheless, we identify also more isolated coastal flood plains with high exposure, such as Thessaloniki (Greece) or Schiavonea (Southern Italy). Finally, comparing our results with land cover at the scale of Europe, we find that urban area and population experience almost a -1 mm/yr subsidence on average (if we discard the uplifting regions due to GIA) and for coastal airports and for harbours, the average land motion drops to a -1.5 mm/yr subsidence.

4. CONCLUSION

Our results imply that many infrastructures and assets located in low-lying areas in Europe are exposed to a larger relative sea-level rise and therefore to a larger flooding risk than previously assess. With this study we demonstrated the major interest of the EGMS data for characterizing vertical ground motion - once corrected the issue due to the EGMS reference system - of

coastal flood plains in the perspective of mapping the relative Sea Level Rise at the continental scale.

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Figure 1. Left: vertical velocity difference between ITRF 2014 and ETRF 2000. Right: correction to apply to EGMS data

Figure 2 : State per country of average vertical land motions trend in coastal floodplain derived from EGMS data. The blue, white and red areas indicate the proportion per country of coastal floodplain area that are, on average, uplifting (> 1 mm/yr), stable (between -1 mm/yr and 1 mm/yr) and subsiding (< -1 mm/yr), respectively. The dark filled contours delineate the coastal floodplains.

ASEISMIC CREEP AND STRAIN PARTITIONING ACCOMMODATING THE NUBIA-EURASIA OBLIQUE CONVERGENCE IN NORTHERN AFRICA FROM INSAR

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ABSTRACT

The seismic and tsunamigenic hazards are significant within the north Africa region due to its location along the Nubia-Eurasia plate boundary zone. The kinematics of the area is marked by a dominant transpressional tectonic regime resulting from the plates' oblique convergence at a rate of ~5 mm/yr [1]. Despite the low straining rates, moderate- to large-magnitude earthquakes are frequent, with several events generating tsunamis and flooding [2]. They involve both inland and offshore tectonic structures distributed within a vast area, making it difficult to assess their role in accommodating the relative plate motion with geodetic, seismic and marine measurements [3]. Therefore, a regional-scale interseismic velocity field constraining the millimeter-lever surface deformation in the area is crucial for the geohazards assessment in the region.

This study uses large-scale multitemporal InSAR analysis to produce the first regional-scale east-west (EW) and vertical interseismic velocity maps for the region east of ~2°W. The analyzed data used include the entire Sentinel-1 satellite archive for the period 2015-2022 along 12 tracks in both the ascending and descending orbits (Fig. 1). The data was processed using the New Small Baselines Subset processing chain (NSBAS)[4] following a processing strategy aimed at (1) interferogram generation, (2) phase unwrapping, and (3) time series of cumulative displacement estimation. We processed an average of ~300 SAR images for each track, generating ~1600 interferograms with temporal baselines ranging between 6 days and 1 year. Due to the challenges associated with measuring low relative surface motions and the vast area under study including vegetation, seasonal snow cover, and sand dunes, special care was brought to tuning the InSAR workflow, corrections, and analysis of the LOS time series. A large portion of the workflow could not be automated, especially the unwrapping of long temporal baseline interferograms, which demanded significant hands-on work.

Our fine-tuned processing strategy yielded time series of cumulative ground displacement that were combined into line-of-sight (LOS) velocity fields using a trajectory model composed of a linear trend and cyclic terms with annual and semiannual periods for each track independently. The resulting velocity maps were aligned into an Eurasian fixed reference frame using the GNSS velocities from [5] and decomposed into EW and vertical components interseismic velocity maps. Justified by the low InSAR geometrical sensitivity to NS motion the velocity decomposition assumes no contribution from the north component to the LOS velocities. After all LOS velocity maps were decomposed into the EW and NS components the tracks were stitched together into continuous surface deformation maps.

Despite the InSAR's limitations in constraining the north-south (NS) oriented motions, our analysis allowed us to constrain the slip rate and mechanisms of strain accommodation of major tectonic structures in the area. The present-day interseismic velocities in north Africa highlight 3 distinct domains of strain accommodation. In Western (west of ~3.5°E) and Eastern Tell (east of ~9°E) the relative plate convergence is primarily accommodated by N60°E-oriented frontal shortening and distributed deformation, respectively. In Central Tell (~3.5°-9.0°E) strain partitioning directs up to 45% of the oblique component of the relative plate motion into the 500 km-long Ghardimaou-North-Constantine (GNC) inland fault. The GNC fault exhibits an aseismic behavior marked by a remarkably shallow locking depth (<5.1±0.5 km) and stands out as one of the slowest (<2.5 mm/yr) continental strike-slip faults ever detected with geodetic data. Our findings highlight the key role of the GNC fault in accommodating the oblique plate convergence, with slip partitioning directing most of the shear aseismically inland. This leaves the offshore thrusts and folds as the region's primary source of seismic hazard, stressing the need for further marine investigations to fully resolve the location and interseismic behavior of the thrust faults offshore.

Figure 1: Ground footprint of the Sentinel-1 SAR imagery used in this study and tectonic interpretation of our main results. Magenta and cyan and boxes mark the area covered by the ascending and descending orbits, respectively. Red triangles show the GNSS station locations used for reference frame alignment (data from Billi et al., 2023).

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QUANTIFYING INTERSEISMIC DEFORMATION ALONG THE MEXICAN SUBDUCTION ZONE FROM INSAR TIME SERIES

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ABSTRACT

Understanding how stresses accumulate and release along subduction zones, the regions hosting the world largest earthquakes, is essential for a better assessment of seismic hazard. Monitoring the surface deformation of the upper plate allows to infer processes taking place along the subduction interface during the different phases of the seismic cycle.

In this project, we focus on the Mexican subduction zone, where large damaging earthquakes frequently occur. This subduction zone also hosts large and frequent slow slip events (SSEs) that are predominantly aseismic [1]. Previous studies [2] have shown the interseismic signal can be extracted from InSAR observation but have been limited to the 2016-2019 period, and were not completely homogeneous in term of processing. The large amount of data needed to cover the whole Mexican Subduction zone was one challenging issue. Here we analyze the extended InSAR dataset, processed through the national FLATSIM facilities (The ForM@Ter LARge-Scale Multi-

Temporal Sentinel-1 Interferometry Service [3,4]) covering the 2016-2022 period. We focus on the descending tracks. The post-processing of the FLATSIM data includes several steps. First, the noisy pixels (i.e., affected by low-coherence, unwrapping errors) or non-tectonic signals (strong subsidence) are masked using the quality indicators of the FLATSIM products. Then, we correct the InSAR time from co-seismic offsets using a parametric model, since several earthquakes occurred during the study period, and estimate for each pixel a linear trend corresponding to the interseismic deformation.

We finally adjust the different tracks in a common reference frame, by correcting, for all the tracks, from ramp to adjust (1) the InSAR signal to the GNSS estimate for the same time period and (2) the coherency between the overlap zones of adjacent tracks.

The result is a map of interseismic deformation (See Figure 1) over the whole Mexican subduction zone for the period 2016-2022. These data will then be used to refine coupling maps for this region.

Figure 1. InSAR interseismic velocities (period 2026-2022). GNSS stations and velocities (projected in LOS) are shown.

Index Terms— InSAR, Subduction, Plate coupling

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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IS STRESS MONITORING ABLE TO FORECAST INTRUSIONS AND SLIP EVENTS AT THE PITON DE LA FOURNAISE VOLCANO ?

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ABSTRACT

At volcanoes, widespread evidence indicates that the stress field and the presence of major discontinuities control the magma trajectory and stability of edifices. These factors affect two major volcanic hazards: eruptions and flank slip events. Here, we rely on a catalog of 57 intrusions at Piton de la Fournaise (Réunion Island), to document the link between stress inherited from intrusions and slip events, and the location of subsequent events. Our study spans two periods, 1998-2007 and 2007-2021, separated by a collapse of the summit crater and a 1.4 meter flank slip in 2007. The 1998-2007 intrusive sequence cannot be simply explained by stress interaction. On the contrary, in the 2007-2021 sequence, the location of intrusions is consistent with a decrease in normal stresses (unclamping) induced by previous intrusions. Progressive rift

zone unclamping, and Coulomb stress increase on previously recognized structures explain the migration of activity from the summit to the distal areas, the alternation between intrusions in the northern and the southern flanks, as well as the occurrence of flank slip events. Stress analysis documents a positive feedback between rift zone and flank slip events. In the long term, both magma intrusions and flank slip events contribute to the occurrence of catastrophic flank collapses through unclamping and Coulomb stress increase at the base of an unstable sector.

Index Terms— InSAR, Piton de la Fournaise, Stress transfer

Monitoring Topographic Changes and Ground Deformation of Semeru Volcano, Indonesia, Using InSAR Time Series and High-Resolution DEMs

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ABSTRACT

High-resolution radar (TanDEM-X) and optical (Pleiades) data are being used to produce DEMs of the Semeru volcano in Indonesia in order to characterise the topographical changes affecting the volcanic edifice between 2016 and 2021. These DEMs are also being used to produce time series of surface displacements from TerraSAR-X and Sentinel-1 data in order to identify the possible presence of precursors of volcanic activity.

Problematic

The patterns of precursor signals associated with volcanic activity can vary widely depending on several factors, including the structure of the volcanic edifice, the behavior of the underlying magmatic plumbing system, and the origin and composition of the magma. These factors can influence whether an eruption manifests as an explosive event, an effusive eruption, or potentially a combination of both dynamics. Understanding the temporal dynamics of volcanic activity, particularly the inter-eruptive periods, is crucial for forecasting the nature and intensity of future eruptions. This relationship between the unrest phase and eruption behavior is complex and requires detailed monitoring in time and space of ground deformation as an indicator of subsurface magma movement.

Context

Explosive volcanic activity in Indonesia, associated with the Sunda subduction arc, accounts for 20% of worldwide reported volcanic fatalities. Here, our study focuses on Semeru volcano, one of the most active Indonesian volcanoes with a constant activity since 1967 [1]. Its daily Vulcanian eruptions can lead to debris flows and lahar activity, posing a threat to crops and infrastructure [2]. A long-term cycle of lava dome formation and destruction punctuates paroxysmal

activity, which led to the 2021 volcanic crisis, resulting in 69 fatalities.

Method and Dataset

Satellite-based Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) data is a powerful remote sensing technique using satellite radar signals to detect and measure ground deformation caused by volcanic activity [3]. This non-invasive technique allows a day and night monitoring independent of the cloud cover. InSAR ground deformation signals on open-conduit volcanoes such as Semeru can be short in time and localized in space; therefore, to be detected it requires the computing of time series with high temporal and spatial resolution. To do so, we propose a multi-data approach using both Sentinel-1 (high-temporal resolution) and TerraSAR-X/PAZ (high-spatial resolution) missions. For this study, we have a total of 29 TerraSAR-X images acquired between March 2022 and September 2023 that are computed using the small baseline NSBAS processing chain [4]. In addition, the volcanic activity in 2021 largely impacted the topography of the edifice, which induce residual fringes on the interferograms. To reduce these artifacts, we process two Digital Elevation Models at spatial resolution of 5 m: one pre-eruptive DEM using a series of 2015-2016 TanDEM-X bi-static SAR images and one just before the 2021 dome collapse DEM in July 2021 using Pleiades stereo optical imagery.

Figure 1: Topographic changes study of the latest dome extrusion leading to the December 2021 eruption jointly analyzing TanDEM-X and Pléiade data from 2016 to 2021. A: Topographic changes map between the TanDEM-X DEM (10/2015 - 02/2016, 5m) and the Pléiade DEM (07/2021, 4m). Zoom on the crater with the hillshade of the Pleiades DEM showing the maximum extent of the lava dome in July 2021. B: AA' profile computed on the top of the dome showing a total of 200m growth between 2016 and 2021. C: BB' profile calculated on the flank crossing the main deposition channel, showing the filling (200m) of the active main channel in 2016 and construction of a new channel eastwards, active in 2021.

Preliminary results

From the difference between the 2016 TanDEM-X DEM and 2021 Pleiades DEM, we were able to evaluate

Index Terms— High resolution, InSAR, volcanic deformation, precursor signals

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the topographic changes during the 2016-2021 period. In 5 years, the 2016 crater has been covered by the extrusion of a 200 meters lava dome (AA' in Figure 1 grey mask) with an extruded volume of $4.55 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ leading to the December 2021 dome collapse. Furthermore, the main channel for deposition of volcanic products has migrated toward the east between 2016 and 2021 due to large infilling (BB' in figure 1). The EDEM products delivered by TanDEM-X provide offers an intermediate DEMs for the year 2018, suggesting that most of the dome's growth occurred between 2016 and 2018. Detailed analysis of InSAR time series will help us to understand how topographic changes and ground deformation are potentially linked to the eruption style.

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FLATSIM service : overview, updates and announcements of Opportunity

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ABSTRACT

The launch of radar satellites like the European Copernicus Sentinel-1 mission (S1) paved the way for free of charge massive amounts of SAR data availability. This huge influx of spatial imaging data means adapting the way we work with the data and associated derived products. Indeed, new specific tools and services must be developed to access, store, manage and use them, including by non-expert users.

In FRANCE, FLATSIM (FormaTerre LARge-scale multi-Temporal Sentinel-1 InterferoMetry) is a service, dedicated to the measurement of ground motion by a massive S1 data processing chain using multi-temporal Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR).

The service, based on the New Small temporal and spatial Baseline (NSBAS) chain, was developed in the framework of the national data center FormaTerre, resulting from a fruitful partnership between the French Space Agency (CNES) and a scientific team from several french laboratories, involved in the development of InSAR tools.

FLATSIM is designed to facilitate Earth science research within the French FormaTerre scientific group and its collaborators, as well as the broader Data Terra Research Infrastructure community. Its primary focus lies on supporting projects encompassing regions larger than 250,000 km² over the full S1 data archive (since October 2014).

The FLATSIM service is enabled to address several scientific topics including seismology, tectonics, volcanology, hydrological cycle...

CNES has implemented and parallelized the NSBAS chain, in its High Performance Computing (HPC) infrastructure. This enables CNES to locally mirror the entire Sentinel-1 SLC data archive from the European Space Agency (ESA). A brief overview of the architecture and strategy to integrate the NSBAS chain in the FLATSIM service will be presented. We will illustrate the amount of CPUs and memory engaged and highlight the major update since the last MDIS conference and the second announcement of opportunity processing, close to completion by MDIS2024. A specific development is a new tool designed to assist Principal Investigators (PIs) in effectively analyzing the entire Sentinel-1 archive for their research projects. We will discuss the incremental strategies implemented for the first two announcements and outline the schedule for the third.

Several talks or posters during this MDIS2024 edition will detail the scientific results obtained thanks to FLATSIM time-series processed in the first 2020 and second 2022 announcement.

Figure : large scale slip on Tibet from multiple passes of Sentinel-1 Satellites, processed with FLATSIM

DEFORMATION OF MAYOTTE ISLAND DURING AND AFTER THE 2018-2021 VOLCANO-TECTONIC EPISODE

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ABSTRACT

In May 2018, an expected episode of volcano-tectonic activity has affected the island of Mayotte (Indian Ocean). A large volume of magma (> 5 km³) erupted on the seafloor, ~50 km to the east of the island, triggering a period of intense seismicity and deformation, culminating in early 2019, and decaying exponentially since then. As a result of re-equilibration of pressure within the deep magma system that fed the eruption, the island subsided by ~25 cm, and moved to the east by ~15–25 cm. This abnormal motion accumulated progressively from 2018 to 2021, and is clearly detected by GNSS and InSAR. However, as seismicity has not yet reached the pre-event baseline, it remains unclear if this episode of transient deformation has ended, or if residual displacement is still affecting the island. Because of the limited amount of geodetic data available before the crisis, understanding the full complexity of the transient deformation experienced by the island during the crisis remains essential for correcting geodetic time-series acquired in recent years.

Using a synergy of GNSS and InSAR data, we first design a strategy for reconstructing the spatial and temporal patterns of deformation affecting the island of Mayotte. A principal component analysis indicates that geodetic data is essentially sensitive to a single source of deformation, and that introduction of second-order complexities (such as motion of the source, or coexistence of a secondary source) would involve degrees of freedom that cannot be resolved by the geodetic data. Although explanation is not unique, the temporal evolution of deformation is consistent with the

response of a linear system composed of a reservoir and conduit, progressively draining into a second reservoir, the latter being presumably situated at great depth and/or great distance from the geodetic network. A bayesian source inversion of the spatial pattern of deformation yields a pressure source situated half-way between the submarine volcano and the island, at ~25 km depth. Combining the temporal and spatial characteristics of the source allows for reconstructing the trajectory undergone by any point onland, which paves the way to creation of a semi-kinematic reference frame for the island.

Thanks to a better understanding of the deformation that affected the island of Mayotte since 2018, we analyze a new ALOS-2 dataset spanning the period 2015-2024. After correcting for the transient volcano-tectonic deformation, vertical deformation can be mapped across the island (Figure 1), revealing the existence of local patterns of deformation affecting a few isolated sites across the island. Nevertheless, the overall stability of sites equipped by GNSS stations is confirmed.

Figure 1: Line-of-sight velocity over Mayotte island deduced from ALOS-2 InSAR analysis (ascending pass) over the period 2015-2024, after correction of transient deformation affecting the area between 2018 and ~2022. Positive LOS velocity (in green) represents motion toward the satellite.

MDIS 2024

Accommodation:

- Orléans Youth Hostel, 3 rue Croix Péchée, 45000 Orléans
- Jackhotel, 18 rue du Cloître Saint-Aignan, 45000 Orléans

If you have requested a room, contact the organizers to find out which room you have been allocated.

Transport:

- To travel to Orléans for the training Tuesday, November 19th, we recommend taking the 8:22 train from Paris Austerlitz to 9:27 at Orléans station.
- To come to the congress from Wednesday, November 20th, we recommend taking the 7:06 train from Paris Austerlitz to 8:20 at Orléans station.

If the journey is too long for you, you can take accommodation the day before at your own expense. Be careful. Don't get off at Les Aubrais station but stay on the train until the terminus at Orléans centre station.

On November 22nd, to return after the ISDform General Assembly, we recommend taking:

- The 15:34 train from Orleans to 16:42 to Paris Austerlitz
- Or the 16:34 train from Orleans to 17:39 to Paris Austerlitz.

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